

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Huge mistake and irrefutable evidence of awarding the 2024 Nobel

Peace Prize to Japan

Why has Japan been deceiving the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time?

The following article has been submitted to many top journals, but so far none of them dares to publish it.

Ethical, moral, and conscience standards, as well as laws to punish criminals and address official inaction in today's world, have regressed by at least **3,000 years**.

The first successful atomic bomb psychological war and global cell security

----- Novel theory and methodology for preventing wars and maintaining durable global peace-10

Li Liu^{*1}, Yajun Chen¹, and Fagang Jiang²

Correspondence to E-mail: LLSunrising@126.com

Abstract

In today's world, the number of global nuclear weapons has exceeded the amount needed to destroy the earth, but it is very difficult to reduce and eliminate them. After the Russia-Ukraine war, Europe and the United States are worried about Russia's nuclear weapons. The power of the **Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant is ten times that of the Chernobyl's**. However, it has been repeatedly attacked. **In case of a full-scale nuclear explosion, the disaster coverage area will be about 512 million square kilometers, which will exceed the total area of the earth. Human cells around the world will be harmed.** The two atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki in 1945 should have paralyzed at least 20% of Japan and made it uninhabitable for humans for at least 100 years, but the opposite is true. Just based on this scientific logic, it is sufficient to prove that the US military successfully carry out a nuclear psychological war at that time. The United States has spent \$7.2 trillion on nuclear weapons. Japan did not point out the wrong investment by the United States and has long enjoyed the dividend of being a so-called atomic bomb victim. If the U.S. had entrusted Buffett's team with investing only \$100 billion in securities related to the S&P 500 in 1965, investment income would have risen to \$1,501.9 trillion by 2018, and there would have been no debt crisis. In order to escape nuclear destruction and promote normal economic development, the public should be aware of the above-mentioned atomic bomb psychological war. Obviously, the incomparable facts prove that awarding the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize to the atomic bomb victims of Japan is a huge mistake. The Nobel Peace Prize Committee should immediately correct this huge mistake. The Japanese people and the Japanese government should no longer deceive the global

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public and should not cheat to win the Nobel Peace Prize. Instead, they should honestly tell the global public that the U.S. military has never dropped atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and Japan has never been truly bombed by U.S. atomic bombs.

Keywords: Atomic bombing, Hiroshima, psychological war, Zaporizhzhia nuclear power, nuclear security, nuclear destruction, cell security

1. Reasons why it is difficult to significantly reduce and completely eliminate nuclear weapons

During the Russia-Ukraine war, Russia's views on the use of nuclear weapons attracted global attention (1,2). According to simulations by British and American scientists, only 100 nuclear weapons are needed to disrupt global ecological stability (3,4). A large number of radioactive particles float into the air and suspend for a long time, triggering a nuclear winter, leading to large-scale deaths in the world and the destruction of the entire human civilization. However, many people mistakenly believe that the idea that 100 nuclear warheads can destroy the world is a fallacy. Because the atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima returned to normal weather after 2 - 3 weeks,⁴ and a few years later, the city flourished again. Even the world's top professionals have made wrong judgements. Only when 250 of the 13,000 nuclear weapons in the world are dropped will a "limited" nuclear war occur, which is believed to cause only 120 million direct deaths and global climate damage (2,5).

The authors believe that the nuclear weapons policies of countries around the world today are closely related to the fact that the secret of the successful psychological warfare of atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki has not been made public to this day (6,7). The public failed to realize the enormous damage caused by nuclear explosions.

The psychological warfare carried out by the U.S. military in dropping atomic bombs in Japan inevitably required creating numerous false appearances, and required Japan to be deceived or cooperate, while utilizing the media to make the public largely believe in the predetermined results. However, the occurrence of fake atomic bomb explosions in the public domain inevitably has unavoidable logical errors and scientific paradoxes. Only one or two key pieces of evidence are needed to accurately determine whether it was psychological warfare.

2. Other evidence of psychological warfare in Hiroshima and Nagasaki atomic bombings

First, scientists from the U.S., China, and Australia used finite element analysis with giant computers to analyze footage of atomic bomb explosions in New Mexico (8), Hiroshima, and Nagasaki. Their surprising result was that the three sets of images were the same atomic bomb, meaning the footage was shot from different angles of the same explosion, likely the one in New Mexico. From logical perspective, or according to the

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evaluation standards of the U.S. FDA for process authenticity, this alone can also determine that the U.S. fabricated the atomic bombing of Hiroshima.

Second, in the photos taken at the center of the Hiroshima atomic bomb explosion, the area around the buildings was flattened, with residual buildings remaining on the flat ground, which contradicts the principles of an atomic bomb explosion (6). Many of the remaining walls on the flat ground were shattered on both sides, yet the walls remained standing, which is absolutely contradictory to any explosion theory. From logical perspectives, this alone suggests that the U.S. military made false claims about the Hiroshima atomic bomb. The possibility is that some explosives were placed in a scattered manner, but there were no explosives near the contact point between the house wall and the ground. As a result, after the explosion, there were walls that did not collapse. This alone is equally sufficient to prove that the U.S. has implemented nuclear psychological warfare.

Third, within 50 years of the atomic bomb explosion, traces of most of the 200 radioactive substances are sure to be found in the soil around the explosion center. However, American and German scientists collected soil samples from Hiroshima and Nagasaki after the explosions and found that these soils were almost indistinguishable from normal soil, with no abnormal radiation levels (8). This alone is enough to confirm that the U.S. has implemented psychological warfare.

Fourth, between 1948 and 1954, scientists monitored almost all pregnancies in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and found no "statistically significant" increase in birth defects. The father of the atomic bomb, J. Robert Oppenheimer publicly stated after the dropping of the atomic bomb on Hiroshima (9), "there is every reason to believe that there was no appreciable radioactivity on the ground in Hiroshima." Based on this alone, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions were indeed psychological warfare.

Fifth, analysis of military behavioral economy to paralyze a country with nuclear war.

Considering the recommendation of the **Chief Medical Officer of the Manhattan Project** that no one should be within 150 miles of the site of an atomic bomb explosion (10,11), Based on the power of the first nuclear weapon explosion, the author calculated the minimum number of atomic bombs required for mutual paralysis between different countries. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The approximate minimum number of nuclear bombs needed to paralyze a country or Continent or the Earth

Country or Continent	Approximate area (Km ²) (12)	Calculated value★	Minimum integer	Actual quantity (13)
Russia	17,098,200	93.44 / 133.49	94 / 134	4,489
USA	9,834,000	53.74 / 76.78	54 / 77	3,708
China	96,340,570	52.65 / 75.22	53 / 76	410
France	Local area: 553,965; Land-area: 672,834	3.03-3.68 / 4.32-5.25	4 / 4	290

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UK	244,100	1.33 / 1.91	2 / 2	225
India	2,980,000	16.29 / 23.27	17 / 24	164
Pakistan	880,254	4.81 / 6.87	5 / 7	170
North Korea	122,762	0.67 / 0.96	1 / 1	30
Israel	Actual-controlled-area: 25,740	0.14 / 0.20	1 / 1	90
Japan [▲]	377,972	(2.07 / 2.95), 4.77/6.82	(3 / 3); 5/7	
Ukraine	603,700	3.30 / 4.71	4 / 5	
Europe	10,160,000	55.53 / 79.32	56 / 80	
North America	24,228,000	132.41 / 189.15	133 / 190	
South America	17,840,000	97.50 / 139.28	98 / 140	
Africa	30,220,000	165.15 / 235.94	166 / 236	
Asia	44,579,000	243.63 / 348.04	244 / 349	
The Earth	510,067,866	2,787.56/3,982.23	2,788/3,983	

* The data on the left is the minimum number of atomic bombs needed to paralyze an area calculated based on the power of the first atomic bombing in New Mexico (Skinny). The data on the right is based on the results after the explosion of the "Little Boy".

▲ According to the total north-south length of Japan's territory (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, and Kyushu mainland islands, excluding small islands), being approximately less than 2,300 km, it is calculated that about 5 Skinny-class atomic bombs or 7 Little Boy-class atomic bombs are needed to destroy Japan.

Table 1 shows that the minimum number of nuclear bombs needed to paralyze Japan after a nuclear attack is about 5 or 7. When two atomic bombs explode in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, respectively, at least 20% of the area and cities near the two cities, accounting for about 20% of Japan's territory, will be paralyzed. It is worth noting that on August 9, 1945, the United States dropped the "Fat Man" atomic bomb on Nagasaki. It weighed about 4.9 tons and had a TNT equivalent of 22,000 tons, which was more powerful than Hiroshima's "Little Boy" and the world's first atomic bomb. However, three weeks later, there was no sense of nuclear pollution in Hiroshima and Nagasaki (4). The surrounding multiple cities and rural areas did not experience a situation where people could not survive due to the nuclear radiation caused by the false atomic bomb explosions in these two cities. **whether or not** according to FDA standards for authenticating the process, it is clear that the atomic bombing of Japan was clearly a successful psychological warfare operation. After 80 years, the disclosure of this table's data makes any secrecy seem futile. Instead, it benefits Japan, a World War II war criminal country, which wants to portray itself as a victim of a nuclear attack. It is also not conducive to nuclear disarmament, to reducing military expenditures, to

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preventing nuclear power plant explosions, and to normalizing the economies of various countries.

3. The long-term concealment of Japan's atomic bomb psychological war has damaged the military and national defense economies of the U.S. and other many countries.

Research by the Brookings Institution in Washington shows that from World War II to 2007, the U.S. government spent a total of **\$7.2 trillion** on nuclear weapons (14). Since the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, the United States has produced about 70,000 nuclear weapons (14). When the Cold War officially ended in 1991, the United States had 23,000 nuclear warheads (14). As for the former Soviet Union, by 1988, it had produced a total of about 43,000 nuclear weapons (15).

Did both the U.S. and the former Soviet Union need so many nuclear bombs? According to the calculation results of this study, the success of concealing the psychological warfare of the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki led to a lack of real understanding of the power of nuclear weapons among even later U.S. leadership, and a lack of serious consideration of war or military or defense behavioral economics. The power of modern nuclear bombs is usually ten to several hundred times that of the first nuclear bomb. One can destroy Britain and France, and three hydrogen bombs can destroy the mainland of the United States. Excessive nuclear weapons are completely useless. The power of radioactive nuclear bombs lies in being stored in arsenals and nuclear bases, rather than being launched. Therefore, the number of nuclear bombs owned by any nuclear-weapon State should not exceed 1 - 5 at most. If humanity does not want to be destroyed, all nuclear weapons on Earth should be abolished. Apparently, not disclosing the truth of nuclear psychological warfare in Hiroshima has led to wrong nuclear weapons policies, crazy production, hindrance of peace, and huge economic losses for both countries and the world.

While the United States has consistently invested **\$7.2 trillion** in the military field of nuclear weapons, **during the same 60-year period, its total military expenditure has reached \$22.8 trillion** (14). However, **the Manhattan Project was achieved with an investment of only US\$2 billion**, which means that at least \$7.2 trillion of huge US investment in nuclear weapons has been wasted since then. It seems to have driven regional economic growth or economic growth for a period of time, but in fact, it has suffered huge losses. This is investment behavior that does not conform to economic ethics, management ethics and **defense behavior economy**. From 1965-2018, the S&P 500 returned a total of 15,019%. So, **one dollar invested in 1965 would be worth \$15,019 at the end of 2018** (16). If the United States aims at long-term investment and entrusts a good investment team to invest. For example, Buffett's team invests **\$100 billion** of funds used for nuclear weapons in stocks in the S&P index. As the index increases, investment income will increase to **\$1,501.9 trillion**. If the U.S. government had provided only **\$10 billion** at an appropriate time before 1965 and allowed Buffett's company to invest in stocks or securities they approved, then in 2018, **\$2,472.627 trillion** would have been reaped. Even if both strategies can ultimately achieve only

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half of the above-mentioned target benefits, the income is extremely significant. How could the United States have the current national debt crisis? How could the U.S. possibly force other countries to buy U.S. bonds to ease its own financial crisis? The United States is still the richest country in the world today. If the United States uses the obtained investment income for various expenditures in the United States, it is a very easy investment behavior to add 100,000 kilometers of high-speed rail for the United States. A high-speed sightseeing railway that passes through South America, the United States, Canada and reaches the Bering Strait in Alaska can face the future high-speed railway in Asia by the Bering Strait across the sea, which can greatly increase the weight of the tourism economy in the United States, Canada and South America. For at least a few decades, basic medical care for Americans can be completely free. Housing for American families can be completely tax-free. All learning expenses for primary and secondary school students and college students in public universities in the United States can be waived completely.

Obviously, in the long-term process of national governance, the economic operation and management of the United States have shown conditions of hypertension and stroke diseases. The economic operation behavior of the United States shows government behavior economy and party behavior economy in large quantities every year (17). Looking back at history from a macro perspective, the military and defense behavioral economy in the field of nuclear weapons in the United States largely shows the characteristics of a planned economy, but in the absence of economic and managerial ethical guidance, it is one of the important factors that often plunge the United States into an economic crisis or a national debt crisis. From the perspective of military behavioral economics or national defense behavioral economics (17), the United States has made huge investment mistakes in the above fields, which is also one of the key factors for the United States to continuously fall into economic crises. According to the key idea of the 2024 Nobel Prize in Economics (18), both the United States and the world probably need to conduct research again on "how policies or institutions are formed and how they affect a country's prosperity and decline." Mainstream economics in today's world may lack the ability to control the healthy development of the economy with a highly predictable and forward-looking vision. Instead, it focuses more on retrospective observation of results. This is one of the signs of lack of foresight and leadership. If anyone thinks otherwise, the author can use examples from the author's personal experience. For older COVID-19 patients aged 60 to 80 with severe symptoms, if the medication is correct and there is no need for hormones and ventilators, symptoms can usually be fully controlled and reversed within 1 to 4 hours and the patient cannot die. But the fact around the world is that many serious patients have died. In other words, constantly using the deaths of many patients to verify a theory or method. Isn't that a lack of ability to deal with serious illnesses? Can such a person be suitable to be the leader of a large team? Once encountering other types of severe infected patients, isn't it highly likely that the patient will die? Although the first author of this paper is in frequent contact with COVID-19 patients, he has never been vaccinated against COVID-19 and has never been infected with the virus. In

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February 2020, the author of this article found that it is very difficult for COVID-19 vaccines to prevent novel coronavirus infection. Not only will the manufacturing and vaccination of COVID-19 vaccines waste huge amounts of funds, but vaccination will also bring unexpected abnormal events and adverse reactions. Although no company had successfully developed a COVID-19 vaccine at that time, facts three years later show that COVID-19 vaccines do not have the preventive effect of a normal vaccine, but instead bring many abnormal vaccination events and serious adverse reactions.

Table 2. Analysis of Investment Income Growth in the US Securities Market

Capital (billion)	Years	Annual compound investment return rate	Total principal and earnings (trillion)
\$7,200	54	From 1965-2018, the S&P 500 returned a total of 15,019%. So, a single dollar invested in 1965 would be worth over \$15,000 at the end of 2018.	108,136.8
\$1,000	54		15,019
\$100	54		1,501.9
\$10	54		150.19
\$10	54	From 1965-2018, Berkshire Hathaway returned 2,472,627% . A single dollar invested in Berkshire Hathaway in 1965 would be worth over \$2.4 million by the end of 2018.	2,472.627
\$1	54		247.2627

More troubling is that nuclear weapons cannot be destroyed by explosions. In poorly managed countries, there have been many incidents of ammunition depot explosions. If the U.S. or Russia falls into an economic crisis and mishandles aging nuclear weapons, it could lead to serious problems. A nuclear base typically holds at least 5-20 strategic nuclear weapons. Once one explodes, a chain reaction of nuclear weapons inside the base is inevitable, possibly leading to Europe, the U.S. or North America or the world become uninhabited restricted areas.

4. Fictional atomic bombings in Japan encouraged Japan's psychology of nuclear retaliation against the U.S.

According to media reports, at a gathering of Japanese Liberal Democratic Party politicians, the son of former Prime Minister Koizumi shouted, "Destroy the U.S. and give it 500 hydrogen bombs (19)." Later, other senior members of the Liberal Democratic Party also shouted this sentence. There are currently 47 tons of nuclear material in Japan,¹⁸ but it has consistently refused to sign the nuclear deal, which has shocked the world. There is no doubt that Japan is sending a signal to the world that Japan will not give up nuclear weapons research and development. Last century, Japan massacred at least 50 million people in China and plundered huge amounts of wealth (6). Once Japan possesses nuclear weapons, it poses a great threat to the U.S. and global peace.

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5. What is the power of the Sarmat nuclear bomb explosion?

The explosion of a Russian Sarmat nuclear bomb is equivalent to the power of 1,600 Little Boys (21,22). After the explosion of the Sarmat nuclear bomb, it will cover 204.9 million square kilometers. The total area of Europe, Africa and Asia is 10.16, 30.22 and 44.579 million square kilometres, respectively. If a Sarmat nuclear bomb explodes at a suitable location and altitude in Europe and exerts 70% of its power, not only Europe, but also Africa and Asia will be completely destroyed, and the Earth will enter a nuclear winter.

6. The real deterrent range after nuclear explosions at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant

Xinhua News Agency reported that on the evening of August 11, 2024 (23), the Ukrainian army carried out two drone attacks on one of the two main cooling towers of the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, causing a fire in the main cooling tower, and both accused each other of causing the accident. Its internal structure was severely damaged. Experts will assess whether the main cooling tower is at risk of collapse when conditions permit.

Since the outbreak of the war between Russia and Ukraine, the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant has been bombed many times, and neither side is willing to take responsibility for this. This is very dangerous for Europe and the world. Obviously, the frequent attacks on the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant indicate that the global public and attackers were influenced by the psychological warfare of the atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and failed to truly understand the extent of the disaster caused by the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant explosion.

The amount of radioactive material released by the Chernobyl nuclear accident was approximately 400 times that of the atomic bombing in Hiroshima (24,25). Had it not been for the sacrifice of 600,000 Soviet citizens who voluntarily carried out rescue operations to prevent a nuclear explosion, nuclear pollution would have covered 51.2 million square kilometers, which exceeded the total area of Europe and Africa. The entire Europe, Russia will be destroyed, and part of Asia and half of Africa would have been severely polluted. These former Soviet heroes, knowing that a nuclear explosion could occur at any time, still threw themselves into transporting various materials to reduce the threat of the nuclear accident. They were not afraid, although they knew that their lives would be sacrificed after exposure to nuclear radiation. People can live healthily on the planet today is inseparable from their selfless sacrifice and dedication to their lives.

Ukraine's Foreign Minister said that if a nuclear explosion occurred at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, the destructiveness would be equivalent to 10 Chernobyls (26), which means that the theoretical area of the disaster caused without rescue after the accident is about **512.34** million square kilometers, which exceeds the area of the Earth. The social systems of both Russia and Ukraine are no longer socialist systems controlled by the Communist Party with a spirit of sacrifice. It is difficult for

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both Russia and Ukraine to have organized large numbers of people willing to sacrifice themselves to stop the repeated explosions and release of nuclear radiation at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant. Just like the Fukushima, almost no Japanese were willing to sacrifice themselves to control the nuclear power plant that had an accident. This means that not only the whole of Ukraine is destroyed, but also the entire Russia, Europe, America, Africa, Oceania and the Earth is ruined. The whole world is also severely polluted, and almost all humans and all humans' cells on Earth will die.

However, currently, people from Earth have been deceived by the false atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and cannot truly understand that once the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, whose power is equivalent to 4,000 Little Boy-level atomic bombings, even if 50-60% of the destruction is released, which areas of the world will be destroyed? What will be the number of victims?

In summary, in order to prevent a nuclear explosion at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant etc. after being attacked in the Russia-Ukraine war and the resulting destruction of all humans' cells, and to prevent a nuclear weapons war triggered by the Russia-Ukraine war and the consequent extinction of humanity. The world must be fully aware of the fact that the dropping of atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki was a successful psychological warfare operation, in order to achieve nuclear disarmament. The international community, international peace organizations, and personnel with in-depth research on nuclear weapons should make independent judgements as soon as possible based on scientific logic regarding whether the atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were part of nuclear psychological warfare. The United Nations and world peace organizations should convene one or more conferences on nuclear disarmament and peace. If nuclear weapons cannot be completely destroyed at once, it is recommended to reduce nuclear weapons and the disarmament of nuclear forces in two steps. Every country that already possesses nuclear weapons should at least drastically reduce the number of its nuclear weapons to a very large extent and completely destroy them all within the next three to ten years, so as to establish friendly relations between countries.

7. Viewing Japan's moral conscience and harm to global nuclear safety from the fact that a group of Japanese nuclear bombs victims won this year's Nobel Peace Prize.

The atomic bombings in two cities is not a trivial matter, but a matter of life and death. Implementing psychological warfare with atomic bombs involves two cities. There must be countless people in the know. At least the residents of the two cities of Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan should fully understand that the U.S. military did not really drop atomic bombs. Otherwise, people within a 150-mile radius will die one after another. After World War II, most Japanese people should be clear about this matter. Otherwise, how dare the Japanese travel and work in Hiroshima and Nagasaki in the more than seventy years that followed? However, the cunning Japanese never declare that they have not been attacked by the atomic bombs of the U.S. military, and never declare that they are not victims of atomic bombs at all. Instead, Japan and the

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Japanese was packaged into the image of weak people enjoying the dividends of being victims of atomic bombs under the lie of psychological warfare with atomic bombs. **However, in 2024, these pretended teams of atomic bomb explosion victims (Nihon Hidankyo)** in Hiroshima and Nagasaki actually won the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize (27).

If a "Little Boy"-level atomic bomb explodes in a coastal city in Europe or the United States, will there be no radiation after 3 weeks, like Hiroshima or Nagasaki?? Can a large number of people live there normally in ten years? If a person has a background in medicine, or pharmacy, or chemistry, or physics, or biology, after he or she carefully analyzes and studies this matter for ten minutes or half an hour, unless that person has a pig's head, he or she must know that in the central area after an atomic bomb explosion, even after 100 or 600 years, there will be serious radiation and people simply cannot live there. Why does the world believe the lie about the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki? This article has been rejected many times by the world's leading journals. This is a great irony to science, ethics, morality, human conscience, and human peace, and is one of the important evidence of a 2000-year setback in global ethics, morality and conscience.

If the Japanese are honest and conscientious, Japan or Japanese politicians or the Japanese academic community should immediately admit that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were never attacked by atomic bombs and immediately announce that they refuse to accept the Nobel Peace Prize. However, the Japanese prime minister sent a congratulatory message to the **Nihon Hibakusha** group who won the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize (28).

8. Severe punishment for the long - standing false claims of survivors of the so-called nuclear bombings in Japan.

Since its founding in 1956 (27), the Nihon Hibakusha organization in Japan has collected thousands of testimonies from survivors of the nuclear bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and sends delegations to the United Nations and various peace conferences every year to urge nuclear disarmament. These Japanese people are extremely shameless, as if they were truly bombed by atomic bombs! If the Japanese of the Nihon Hibakusha organization were kind - hearted, honest, and conscientious and did not lie, when questioned, they should go to the radioactive - contaminated restricted area of the Fukushima nuclear power plant, use 5,000 trucks to transport 30,000 tons of contaminated soil and scatter it at a rate of 0.5 kilograms per square meter outside the densely - populated areas and houses of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and then test after one year to see if all the residents of the two cities and their neighbors have contracted radiation sickness and if they can live half of 79 years. If the Japanese were kind - hearted, honest, and conscientious, they could be allies instead of just bowing to everyone, seemingly polite. The Japanese should prevent the U.S. from investing **at least \$7 trillion** in developing nuclear weapons and prevent the U.S. defense and military economies from going astray. In the 66 years since its founding, this organization has been lying, deceiving, and misleading the global public. The atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki have been used to seek illegal

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benefits for Japan, depicting Japan, which slaughtered 51.80 - 89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, raped and gang - raped at least 31.45 - 54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women, looted wood at least 700 million cubic meters (usually at least \$420 billion) and plundered at least 1.06 billion tons of coal (usually worth \$114.4 billion) (17), as a victim in the world, seriously harming the welfare of the American people and the welfare of other countries developing nuclear weapons in the world. Japan should at least compensate for all the losses of these countries.

Thousands of Japanese claim that they are so - called survivors of the nuclear bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and act as witnesses and provide testimonies. This is a typical large - scale and ongoing fraud that has lasted for 68 years. It not only deceives the Norwegian Parliament and the Norwegian Nobel Committee, but also deceives the global public, and nature is very bad. All participants are guilty. The immediate relatives and descendants of these criminals must be permanently prohibited from working in any government agency, military - related institutions, legal institutions, or media (both long - term and temporary jobs), and permanently prohibited from working as civil servants. International criminal investigation organizations should immediately issue arrest warrants for these rumors – spreading criminals, confiscate all their properties, and prohibit any lawyer from defending the rumors – spreading criminals.

9. Is Japan a country that hopes for world peace after the Second World War?

Is Japan a country that hopes for world peace after the Second World War? If Japan truly hopes for world peace, it should tell the United States that it should not make such investments and should not develop so many nuclear weapons. \$ 198 billion is enough to complete 99 Manhattan projects. Japan should ask the United States to allocate 100 billion of the remaining \$ 7 trillion to be invested by Buffett's company, and use the rest for the livelihood of the American people, such as free education expenses from a child's birth to university and tax - free basic housing for families. Or, it could directly declare that the U.S. military did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and that it was nuclear psychological warfare at that time. Indeed, the production of a large number of nuclear weapons by the United States and the former Soviet Union has heightened global tensions and led some non - nuclear - weapon States to become nuclear - weapon States. Japan has made "remarkable contributions" to this.

Japan's concealment of the fact that the U.S. military did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki has brought enormous economic harm to the United States and the world economy. In 2023, global spending on nuclear weapons increased by 13.4%. A newly released report by the International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN) shows that the United States had the largest annual increase, with an increase of nearly 18%, followed by the United Kingdom with 17.1%. In terms of expenditure, the United States had the largest expenditure scale last year, reaching \$51.5 billion, and total global expenditure is estimated at \$91.4 billion, equivalent to \$173,884 per minute. From 2019 to 2023, global expenditure increased by 34%.

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According to ICAN, the manufacturing and maintenance of nuclear weapons has cost a cumulative \$387 billion over the past five years.

[Nuclear Weapon Spending on the Rise. DEFENSE.by Martin Armstrong, Jun 17, 2024.
<https://www.statista.com/chart/32449/global-nuclear-weapon-spending-change/>]

10. The Nobel Peace Prize awarded to Japanese should be urgently cancelled, and hold a conference on nuclear weapons reduction in the world's earliest holy land of peace

The Nobel Peace Prize committee should hold an emergency meeting to discuss cancelling the Nobel Peace Prize awarded to Japanese nuclear bomb victims this year. And consider awarding this prize to the authors of this paper, who reveal that the Japanese atomic bomb explosions are fictional psychological warfare, that Japan has long concealed that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were not bombed by atomic bombs but has not revealed the truth to the world at all and has not pointed out the mistakes of its ally the United States in investing **\$7.2 trillion** in developing nuclear weapons that must be scrapped in the future and making the US economy gradually fall into difficulties. The author of this article will donate all the prize money obtained to the peace movement promoting world peace chaired by the relevant author and the truly necessary peace movement that needs funds to promote the cultivation of peace fighters in batches. The key to maintaining world peace lies in cultivating more peace fighters. This paper has fully demonstrated the rationale, necessity and urgency for a significant reduction in nuclear weapons globally.

The author hopes to promote the convening of a world peace conference on the significant reduction and destruction of nuclear weapons in the 21st century in Luyi County, Henan Province, the birthplace of Taoism in China. The Laojuntai in Mingdao Palace in Luyi County was originally named Shengsian Terrace or Baixian Terrace. According to legend, Laozi became immortal and ascended here. When the Japanese army invaded this place, they continuously fired 13 mortar shells at Laojuntai in Mingdao Palace, but none of them exploded. After the Japanese army inspected, they all knelt down here. Laozi said that war is an expression of "the world without morality." Obviously, holding a peace conference on the elimination of nuclear weapons in the world here is in line with the concept of world peace. All officials, media personnel, experts, key members of the global nuclear disarmament movement, the public, and those who have made important contributions to this event and strongly support the cancellation of Japan's Nobel Peace Prize this year will be invited to attend the meeting. While observing Taoist culture, they can also visit the beautiful scenery of this place. In this unique way, more people will be made to join the ranks of cultivating the peace fighters advocated by Mr. Nobel, and it will surely accelerate the pace of significant global reductions and abolition of nuclear weapons. Driven by this unexpected incident, the awareness of managers of various countries will be raised, prompting them to reduce investment in nuclear weapons and promoting the healthy development of the economies of various countries.

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11. Shoot a film about the psychological war of the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki

From the dual perspective of maintaining world peace and making profitable investments, it is recommended that the Nobel Foundation, investors in Europe and America cooperate with Hollywood to shoot "a shocking atomic bombings psychological warfare film about the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki" being a huge deception.

Making a film requires finding topics that are of great interest to the public. How the earth-shattering lie of faking the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was successful will surely arouse great interest from the public. Why are we deceived by such a low-level lie? Why are we so like novices or rookies? It is also one of the ways to maintain world peace and sustainable development from a different perspective, cultivate peace fighters and champions of peace, reduce nuclear weapons, promote nuclear disarmament, and achieve the goals of Mr. Nobel's four major concepts of peace. If this film can be successfully filmed, it should achieve extremely high ratings and have an excellent effect on maintaining world peace and sustainable development. It is equivalent to the world holding countless peace conferences.

12. The core reason why the entire Japanese nation has dared to publicly deceive the kind-hearted global public for about 80 years and why the U.S. has been reluctant to disclose that it did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

The core reasons why the Japanese people and the entire country of Japan have dared to publicly deceive the global public for about 80 years by falsely claiming that Japan is a victim of atomic bombings, and why the United States has been reluctant to disclose that it did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki:

The main reason is that after the Second World War, the United States did not want to lose the narrative that it was the use of atomic bombs that forced Japan to surrender and thus end the Second World War, because this would affect the status of the U.S. military in the Second World War and the Pacific War, as well as the status of the United States in the war against Japanese invaders. It would lead to the need for a re-evaluation of the historical status of the U.S. military, Soviet military, and Chinese military and civilians in the Pacific War.

Since the Japanese people and Japanese politicians have fully grasped the vanity of some American leaders, they have deliberately and continuously pretended that Japan is a victim country of atomic bomb attacks. The Japanese media and the Japanese people have continuously spread rumors against basic scientific logic. They even claim that the radioactive element pollution in the central area of at least 400 square kilometers of soil after the atomic bomb explosion could be blown away by sea winds within three weeks, and then humans could live there.

How clever the Japanese are! The United States revealed only one flaw and was firmly grasped by the Japanese. The vanity of the United States has been completely exploited by Japan. Not only the entire country of Japan, but all its people have embarked on the path of long-term fraud against the global public. Japan is like a

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ferocious army of man-eating ants or piranhas (Japanese-eating ants or Japanese-piranhas). It has lost its morality, ethics, conscience, and empathy. Just like a ferocious army of man-eating ants, as long as the opportunity is right, it will immediately reveal its ferocious true face and strip the victims to the bone in a very short time. The Japanese are also like wolves in sheep's clothing. Usually, they basically pretend to be harmless or present a pitiful appearance that arouses sympathy.

Now that the historical truth has been revealed, there is no need for the United States to continue to conceal the truth about the atomic bomb psychological warfare it carried out in Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

As history progresses to this day, no one can conceal the truth about the psychological warfare of the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki any longer. Many media outlets and the public have already learned the truth that Japan was not bombed with atomic bombs by the US military. The reason why the United States has concealed the truth about the psychological warfare of the atomic bomb it carried out in Japan is nothing more than fear that some of the history of World War II will be rewritten and the historical status of the U.S. military will be reduced. World War II was won against the Japanese invaders at great cost by the former Soviet army, the U.S. military, the Chinese army, and the British army simultaneously. The former Soviet army, the U.S. military, and the Chinese army paid the highest price. The United States has an obligation and responsibility to ensure that those predecessors who have sacrificed their lives for justice receive the necessary respect and enjoy the deserved status. **During World War II, 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians sacrificed their lives to rescue 64 pilots led by Major Doolittle of the U.S. Air Force who bombed Tokyo and other parts of Japan. The Japanese brutally slaughtered most of them by using bacterial biological warfare. Hollywood in the United States should at least make a landmark movie to commemorate so many sacrificed Chinese soldiers and civilians and repay the friendship between the two countries.**

From the perspectives of military behavior economics and national defense behavior economics, if the United States continues to conceal the truth about the psychological warfare of the atomic bomb it carried out in Japan, it will only be detrimental to the U.S. economy. It will force the United States to invest in the development and production of nuclear weapons for a long time to come. After these nuclear weapons are produced, unless they are used to destroy the earth, they will eventually have to be scrapped. **This has led to the United States being forced to make erroneous investments in the field of nuclear weapons in terms of national defense economics for a long time. The direct economic loss is at least \$ 7.2 trillion , and indirect investment is \$ 22.8 billion . Today, on average, about \$500 billion is spent on nuclear weapons every year.** And the U.S. national debt has exceeded \$36 trillion. Japan has put the U.S. economy on a track of wrong development, which clearly conforms to Japan's strategy formulated a thousand years ago to dominate the world, just like the evil "**Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纮一宇塔)**" built in Japan, which was meant to suppress the souls and fortunes of various countries and make Japan the emperor of the world.

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13. China was an ally of the United States during World War II, and the two countries should no longer engage in confrontation in the ideological field.

Those engaged in political research or professional politicians have never told the US president or President Trump that **there are more kibbutzim with the communist social labor and distribution system in Israel than in China**, although China currently has a socialist system that is different from the one defined by Marx. After the end of World War II, there was no need for the United States to create ideological confrontation between the two countries, nor was there any need to conceal the historical truth. China and the United States were originally allies during World War II. **To rescue 64 American pilots, 250,000 Chinese people have sacrificed their lives, yet China has never asked the United States for compensation. However, as long as you show the slightest flaw, the entire Japanese nation will pounce on you to suck your blood and devour your flesh.**

The previous classification of human social systems was very wrong. It was not conducive to kind-hearted people seeing clearly the essence of an evil country and an evil nation, and it was easily exploited by evil people and evil countries to create conflicts. Human social systems need to be reclassified. **The first author of this article has, for the first time in history, divided human social systems into categories like those in an encyclopedia, and almost every country can find its own category** { Liu, L. (2024). **Risk avoidance, opportunities, economic development, global governance, peace, Reclassify social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives.** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192942> }. It is beneficial for reducing conflicts, severely punish criminals, reduce wars, promote healthy economic development, and maintain sustainable peace on earth.

It should be pointed out that China participated in the War to Resist U.S. and Assistance to Korea, which broke out in 1950. **Largely because the U.S. military has repeatedly crossed the border and bombed Chinese border cities, killing and injuring civilians, destroying homes and an antique trading street. After the protests by the Chinese premier and the Chinese government proved ineffective, China sent troops at the invitation of the DPRK (Democratic People's Republic of Korea) government.**

The pilots of the U.S. military were all experienced veterans of World War II. It was impossible for them to repeatedly make obvious mistakes on the battlefield. Moreover, following protests by the Chinese government, U.S. military aircraft continued to cross the clearly demarcated Yalu River many times to bomb Chinese cities. Apparently, the supreme commander of the U.S. military in Japan or the air force commander was bribed by the Japanese. Because at that time, China was still an ally of the United States during World War II. How could the U.S. military bomb Chinese cities many times? It was completely illogical.

It should be noted that General Douglas MacArthur, the supreme commander of the U.S. military in the Pacific region, publicly had a beautiful woman given by the Japanese emperor in Japan and accepted a large amount of bribes in the form of money provided by Japan.

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{Ref.1. 抗战时期中国军民牺牲 25 万人 只为救 64 名美军飞行员.2018 年 08 月 15 日. During the period of the War of Resistance against Japanese Aggression, 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians sacrificed their lives just to rescue 64 American pilots. August 15th, 2018. <https://mil.news.sina.com.cn/history/2018-08-15/doc-ihhtfwqr6266596.shtml>};{ Ref.2. 日本天皇贿赂麦克阿瑟, 只求放过一命, 贿赂金额让人目瞪口呆。2022 年 6 月 27 日. The Emperor of Japan bribed Douglas MacArthur, only hoping to save his own life. The amount of the bribe was astonishing. June 27th, 2022. <https://www.ixigua.com/7076874969837208072> };{ Ref.3.本应剖腹的日本天皇, 给麦克阿瑟送黄金美女, 竟保留天皇制.2017-08-07. The Japanese emperor, who should have committed seppuku (ritual suicide by disembowelment), presented gold and beautiful women to Douglas MacArthur, and surprisingly, the imperial system was retained. August 7th, 2017. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/CR7N2A2D0523HKD8.html> }

14. Whether Hiroshima and Nagasaki experienced atomic bombings can serve as an assessment criterion for assessing people's thinking abilities

Whether Hiroshima and Nagasaki experienced atomic bomb explosions may be used as an evaluation criterion for examining people's thinking abilities in Western society, or it may be used as a recruitment topic for employees or a rough test of students' judgment before the truth is fully revealed.

When someone in front of you mentions that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are false or fabricated and that the U.S. military did not drop atomic bombs on Japan, your thinking and judgment abilities may be assessed in the following ways.

Table S1. Evaluation criterion for examining people's thinking abilities	
1	If you are a top military strategist or academician - level figure or top entrepreneur or top - level statesman with global leadership or top economist or top scientist or top management expert or top marketing specialist, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 30 - 60 seconds, and then, after retrieving and studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 5 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military (Starting from the end point of 30 or 60 seconds, including the time for subsequent literature review, it is regarded as five minutes.). Or you don't need to do any verification and directly make a completely accurate judgment within 60 seconds, confirming that the US military did not really drop atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. At a high level, a response every ten seconds reflects a level difference.
2	If you are a first - class professor, a management expert, or a member of the Senate or the House of Representatives, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 90 seconds, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge

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	within 7 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
3	If you are a PhD in Natural Science or Engineering Science, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 120 seconds, and then, after studying the relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 10 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
4	If you are a PhD in Social Sciences or Arts, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 180 seconds, and then, after studying the relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 15 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
5	If you are an undergraduate graduate with a university science or engineering background, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 2 - 5 minutes, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 30 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
6	If you are an undergraduate graduate with a liberal - arts background from a university, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 6 - 8 minutes, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 30 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
7	You can also test whether you really don't understand that the U.S. military didn't drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, or you just pretend not to understand.

	<p>Table S2. Questioning Japan and the Japanese people:</p> <p>Is Japan really a peace-loving country? Are the Japanese people really peace-loving?</p> <p>Drop an atomic bomb with half the power of the "Little Boy" again at the same location in Hiroshima or Nagasaki. Will the remaining nuclear radiation in the central explosion areas of both cities disappear within three weeks? Or in 300 years?</p> <p>Why do the media make people lose basic rationality and logic so much? Why do the Japanese media make people forget what true science is?</p>
	From World War II until now, Nagasaki has always been one of Japan's shipbuilding bases. The Nagasaki shipyard under Mitsubishi Heavy Industries is

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	a major destroyer manufacturer for the Japan Maritime Self - Defense Force and has the technical capability to produce aircraft carriers. During World War II, the vast majority of Japanese warships were built in Nagasaki, and every time a warship was built, the "evil" Japanese citizens would cheer, making it a sinful city. Now it has been glorified as a so-called atomic bomb victim city.
1	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate for all the losses for the massacre of at least 51.80–89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people? Since the Japanese invasion of China in 1874 and Japan's surrender in 1945, data show that China's population has lost about 280 million people.
2	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate for all the losses for the rapes and gang rapes of at least 31.45-54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women by the Japanese invaders?
3	If Japan is truly a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are truly peace-loving, would they not compensate for all the losses for the Japanese invaders forcing at least 200,000 Chinese women and young girls to be sex slaves?
4	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth \$420 billion looted from China?
5	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth \$114.4 billion looted from China?
6	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 42,000 – 63,000 tons of gold worth \$5,289 – 7,933.5 billion looted from China?
7	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about \$3,535.71 billion looted from China?
8	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about \$800 billion looted from China?
9	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth \$20,000-300,000 billion looted from China?
10	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 1,000 tons of platinum worth about \$32.258-37.868 billion looted from China?
11	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion looted from China?
12	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really

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	peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about \$18-23.4 billion looted from China?
13	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 10 million pieces cultural relics worth about \$100,000 billion looted from China?
14	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 33,5 million tons of salt worth about \$ 42 billion looted from China?
15	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 100 million tons of steel worth about \$ 311.55 looted from China?
16	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 150 million tons of kaolin worth at least \$20.5- \$68.8 billion looted from China?
17	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 480 million pigs, sheep, chickens, and ducks, and 20 million head of cattle, horses, and donkeys looted from China?
18	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate and return at least 20 million ancient books looted from China?
19	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for the entire Toyota car factory looted from China?
20	If Japan is really a peace-loving country, and if the Japanese people are really peace-loving, wouldn't they compensate China for at least 250 million silver coins looted from China?
21	<p>The evil Japanese people use the Nanjing Guanyin statue to redeem Japanese war criminals, and decipher the world's most sinister Feng Shui organization. This Guanyin statue is constructed using ten jars of soil soaked with the blood of Chinese civilians.</p> <p>Warvigilance:</p> <p>If Japan were truly a peace loving nation, would it be so bloody and shameless?</p> <p>If the Japanese were truly a peace-loving nation, would a peace-loving nation still be so bloody and shameless in the 21st century after World War II?</p>
22	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纮一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of Germany.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p> <p>在日本的传说中，日本统治者神武天皇曾下达“八纮一宇”诏书，上书：征服世间的四面八方，置诸于一个屋顶之下。The meaning of the above Chinese text translated</p>

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	<p>into English is: In Japanese legends, Emperor Jimmu, the ruler of Japan, once issued an imperial edict of " the Unified Universe or 八紘一宇", which read: "Conquer all directions of the world and place them under one roof."</p> <p>At that time, Germany was an ally of Japan, but Japan even wanted to conquer and annex Germany. Japan is now an ally of the United States. Japan has misled the United States into wasting at least \$7.2 trillion in the field of nuclear weapons, seriously disrupting the U.S. economy, and constantly creating a tense situation in the world. After World War II, military investment in the United States should have decreased. However, under the promotion by its so-called ally Japan, it has instead increased by \$22.8 trillion in 60 years, successfully leading the U.S. economy into a trap. Sadly, basically all Americans still don't know the truth of the matter. Thus, it is better to believe that a dog will not defecate than to believe Japan's false claim of wanting world peace.</p>
23	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of the United States.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
24	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of Canada.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
25	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of Russia.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
26	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of Peru.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
27	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of Singapore.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
28	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of South Korea.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
29	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八紘一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of North Korea.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
30	<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls(the</p>

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	<p>Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of North the Philippines.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
31	<p>To this day, Japan still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fate of China, etc.</p> <p>Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?</p>
32	<p>Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the death of about 650,000 Chinese people.</p> <p>On August 27, 2002, after 27 court hearings, the Tokyo District Court of Japan announced that lawyer Wang Xuan and the plaintiffs of the bacterial warfare of the Japanese invaders in China lost the lawsuit. From the first session of the Court in 1998 to 2006, it has been eight years. After eight years of litigation and more than 40 court sessions, some media commented on Wang Xuan in this way: Another eight-year war of resistance. The eight-year war of resistance that took place 60 years ago won victory, while the eight-year war of resistance in 2006 still sees no end. On July 19, 2006, lawyer Wang Xuan and members of the bacterial warfare plaintiff group once again heard the result of losing the lawsuit in the courtroom of the Tokyo District Court of Japan.</p> <p>Is Japan really a peace-loving country?</p> <p>Are the Japanese really kind?</p> <p>Are the Japanese really honest?</p> <p>Do the Japanese really have a conscience?</p> <p>If Japan and the Japanese are such, it is an obvious fact that the Japanese invaders carried out biochemical warfare of bacteria and viruses to massacre the Chinese people.</p> <p>Why did the Japanese government admit that it had carried out bacterial biochemical warfare in China only after being <u>sued 29 times from the 20th to the 21st century,</u> and that these people were victims of biochemical warfare? However, the evil Japanese government refused to pay any compensation to the victims.</p> <p>You can believe that dogs don't defecate, but you must never believe that Japan is kind, and you must never believe that Japan wants world peace.</p>
33	<p>Is Japan a peace-loving country?</p> <p>Are the Japanese really peace-loving?</p> <p>Are the Japanese not extremely evil?</p> <p>Hasn't Japan been deceiving the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time?</p> <p>In April 2023, Japanese Foreign Minister Yoshimasa Hayashi publicly denied the Nanjing Massacre, only admitting that there were civilian casualties</p>

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	<p>caused by battles. Yoshimasa Hayashi said that there is no document within the Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs to prove that Japan carried out the massacre of civilians in Nanjing.</p> <p>At present, Japan has begun to deny the heinous crimes committed during the Second World War! This is denying the conclusion of the Tokyo Trials and trying to overthrow the international order after the Second World War. Militarism is resurgent!</p> <p>In fact, the Japanese invaders massacred at least 500,000–650,000 people. Some evidence left in the documents destroyed by the Japanese army is that in the two months before and after the Nanjing Massacre, the population fell by 785,000 people.</p> <p>The Japanese are extremely evil in their hearts but are good at disguising themselves as polite on the outside. They carried out the Nanjing Massacre using various forms of torture. At least 100,000 or more women were raped and gang-raped, yet they still do not admit their crimes.</p>
34	<p>In today's world, although there is abundant material wealth, morality and conscience have regressed by at least six thousand years!</p> <p>The Japanese are best at creating false appearances.</p> <p>All the equipment and the entire production line of Toyota Motor Corporation were looted by Japanese invaders from Minsheng Automobile in Shenyang, China when they invaded China. At that time, all the workers and technicians were also forcibly captured by the Japanese invaders to produce for them. Toyota car owners in Japan are not ashamed but proud. If the Japanese are really peace-loving, shouldn't the entire Toyota be compensated to Shenyang, China?</p> <p>Are the Japanese really peace-loving? Are the Japanese not extremely evil?</p>
35	<p>Through massacres, rapes, gang rapes and looting, a huge amounts of wealth are brought, but there is no severe punishment. Let an extremely evil country and an evil nation accumulate strength, continuously release false peace signals to the outside world, but are making long-term fundamental preparations in order to launch the next aggressive war.</p>

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日本否认南京大屠杀！日本对华实施认知作战，正攻破我们心灵防线

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近日，日本外相林芳正公开否认南京大屠杀，只承认出现因战斗而导致平民伤亡。林芳正表示，日本外务省内部并没有任何文件证明日本有在南京进行屠杀平民。

目前的日本，已经开始否认二战期间犯下的滔天罪行了！这是在否认东京审判的结论，并在试图推翻二战后的国际秩序，军国主义复燃了！

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吉田康一郎
@yoshidakoichiro

和田政宗議員、素晴らしい仕事です。

国会史上初の答弁！南京事件「省内に根拠となる文書は存在しない」と林外相 2023.4.14 和田政宗 / Hanadaプラス

Fig. 85-23-20-1.

日本否认南京大屠杀！日本对华实施认知作战，正攻破我们心灵防线

Japan denies the Nanjing Massacre! Japan is implementing cognitive warfare against China and is breaking through our psychological defenses. 2023-04-18.
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/I2L2KA320536HVGN.html>

In April 2023, Japanese Foreign Minister Yoshimasa Hayashi publicly denied the Nanjing Massacre, only admitting that there were civilian casualties caused by battles. Yoshimasa Hayashi said that there is no document within the Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs to prove that Japan carried out the massacre of civilians in Nanjing.

At present, Japan has begun to deny the heinous crimes committed during the Second World War! This is denying the conclusion of the Tokyo Trials and trying to overthrow the international order after the Second World War. Militarism is resurgent!

In fact, the Japanese invaders massacred at least 500,000–650,000 people. Some evidence left in the documents destroyed by the Japanese army is that in the two months before and after the Nanjing Massacre, the population fell by 785,000 people.

Is Japan a peace-loving country?

Are the Japanese really peace-loving?

Are the Japanese not extremely evil?

Hasn't Japan been deceiving the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time?

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 85-23-20-2.

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Suggestions to the Nobel Peace Prize Committee:

Implementing psychological warfare with atomic bombs requires negotiation and

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cooperation between the United States and Japan, as well as the participation of many people. Moreover, it is implemented in two cities on separate occasions. There are a large number of residents in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, and they are all insiders. Not to mention that the severe radioactive pollution at the site of the atomic bomb explosion cannot be eliminated for hundreds of years. Many Japanese people and high-level Japanese officials cannot possibly not know that the U.S. military did not really bomb Hiroshima and Nagasaki with atomic bombs. However, the Japanese are extremely dishonest. When receiving the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize, if the Japanese are honest, Japan or Japanese politicians or the Japanese academic community should immediately admit that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were never attacked by atomic bombs. However, the Japanese prime minister sent a congratulatory message to the group of nuclear explosion victims who won the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize. Obviously, the Japanese are a very dishonest nation. A few hours before the Japanese aircraft carrier fleet attacked Pearl Harbor, the Japanese were still pretending to talk about peace with U.S. President Roosevelt.

Many high-ranking Japanese figures know that the U.S. military did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki. However, they still publicize that the United States dropped atomic bombs in order to disguise themselves as victims and obtain extremely evil benefits and sympathy.

Japanese academician even told their female doctoral student (PhD student) that the explosion sites in Hiroshima and Nagasaki were the results of the combined effects of incendiary bombs and explosives under the bombing of American aircraft. But he still told his female doctoral student that there was no need to let the outside world know that Japan was not bombed by atomic bombs, and to continue to maintain Japan's image as a victim of atomic bombings. Obviously, Japan can reap huge rewards by continuing to maintain the image of being a victim of atomic bombs, and instead putting the United States and Americans in a very bad position or in the position of war criminals. During the period of Japanese aggression against China, direct statistics from **only 11 provinces show that the Japanese invasion caused at least 41.99-52.48 million deaths.** The number of injured has not yet been counted (China currently has 34 provinces). You should know that when Japan invaded China, the **Japanese aggressors raped and gang-raped at least 31.45-54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women, and forced at least 200,000 Chinese women into sexual slavery. They killed at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people.** Since the Japanese invasion of China in 1874 and Japan's surrender in 1945, data show that **China's population has lost about 280 million people.** **All Toyota Motor's production equipment, assets, workers, professional technical personnel, and every screw comes from the evil Japanese looting of Minsheng Motors in Shenyang, China.** The evil Japanese looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth \$5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth \$50,000 billion, **500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth \$132.55-280.5 billion,** **20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about \$5,000 billion,** at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about \$800

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billion, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth \$20,000-300,000 billion, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about \$3,535.71 billion, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth \$114.4 billion [More Information: Liu, L. (2023). Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13931479>]. **Japan seems to have been defeated in the Second World War. In fact, it is an evil victorious country that has plundered huge amounts of wealth and has not compensated China and the Chinese people for their losses.**

What the Japanese are doing is dragging the United States down! At the same time, they deceive the public internationally by pretending to be victims of atomic bomb explosions and obtain sympathy and other illegal benefits. **In September 2024, Japan's newly elected prime minister, Shigeru Ishiba, proposed:** "The strength of the United States has declined significantly. The time is ripe to revise the Japan-US Security Treaty. The 'asymmetry' of the Japan-US alliance should be corrected. The US military can station troops in Japan, and **the Self-Defense Forces of Japan should also station troops in the United States, such as Guam!**" Many Chinese media have reported this matter extensively.

The evil Japanese government, in disregard of the protests of many countries around the world, brazenly discharged a large amount of untreated nuclear-contaminated water into the sea.

Dogs don't defecate in their own dens.

Wild boars don't defecate in their own dens either. What's more, they will never dump nuclear waste water that can cause disease and be fatal into their own dens.

However, the evil Japanese actually dump a large amount of nuclear contaminated water that can cause disease and be fatal into the ocean, which is the living place for all human beings.

In today's world, it is an era when people's moral character is inferior to that of dogs.

The harm of nuclear waste water (nuclear sewage) to the human body and the earth is extremely serious, with nuclear wastewater posing a greater threat to the human body. It contains 64 kinds of radioactive materials, including tritium, carbon-14, iodine-129, strontium-90, and cobalt-60. The most harmful to human beings and marine organisms are carbon-14 and iodine-129, with a half-life of over 5000 years for carbon-14 and an even longer half-life for iodine-129. Carbon-14 can accumulate in the bodies of marine organisms, such as fish, with an abundance or concentration possibly 50 times that of tritium. Any individual, company or country that releases nuclear waste water or nuclear pollution (nuclear sewage) to the earth or the sea should ensure that all indicators meet emission standards in advance and undergo organized testing and continuous monitoring by neighboring countries.

If Japan believes that the radioactive elements generated after the atomic bomb explosion will not pollute Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan should discharge nuclear-contaminated water from the Fukushima nuclear power plant into Hiroshima and Nagasaki. On the contrary, the Japanese release nuclear-

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contaminated water into the sea where humans live. This shows that the Japanese government is very clear that there was no atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. If the Japanese government thinks that nuclear-contaminated water will not harm human health, the Japanese should drink water from the place where nuclear-contaminated water is discharged daily. Japan should at least report the content of 15 radioactive elements in nuclear waste water. The atomic energy commissions of each country should check the content of at least 15 radioactive elements in the discharge of Japanese nuclear contaminated water in real time. However, Japan has never taken the initiative to report the content of these radioactive elements in nuclear-contaminated water.

The Nobel Peace Prize Committee should urgently convene a meeting to discuss cancelling the awarding of this year's Nobel Peace Prize to the group of Japanese nuclear explosion victims and awarding the prize to the authors of this paper who reveal that the Japanese atomic bomb explosions are fictional psychological warfare, that Japan has long concealed that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were not bombed by atomic bombs but has not revealed the truth to the world at all and has not pointed out at all that its ally the United States wrongly invested 7.2 trillion dollars in developing nuclear weapons that must be scrapped in the future and has caused the American economy to continuously fall into difficulties. The authors of this paper will then donate all the prize money received to the relevant peace movement for the promotion of world peace chaired by the authors, a real peace movement that needs funds to promote the mass cultivation of champions of peace. This article has fully demonstrated the reasons, necessity and urgency for a significant reduction in nuclear weapons globally. The author hopes to facilitate the convening of a world peace conference on major nuclear disarmament in the 21st century in China, Europe or the United States through this, enabling more people to join the ranks of **champions of peace or peace fighters** advocated by Mr. Nobel and promote a significant reduction in nuclear weapons globally and the rapid abolition of nuclear weapons around the world.

The authors believe that addressing the major mistake in awarding the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize in this way will prevent future generations from regarding the actions of Norwegian government institutions as a major disgrace in history when writing history. Instead, it will be regarded as a great action to save humanity, which also fully complies with the four requirements for awarding the Nobel Peace Prize set by Mr. Nobel.

**Save The Europe !
Save The United States !
Save The America !
Save The Asia !
Save The World !
Save All Human Cells !**

Declaration of interests

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We declare no competing interests. No financial support

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Save The Europe !
Save The United States !
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Save The World !

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Save All Human Cells !

This article has been publicly available on a preprint server Zenodo [Liu, L. (2024). The first successful atomic bomb psychological war and global cell security. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13851163>], [Liu, L. (2023). Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13931479>]

Revealing as soon as possible that the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were successful psychological warfare should be beneficial to the security of the United States and global peace, and conducive to reducing global nuclear weapons. Because, with the current power of hydrogen bombs, there is no need for the son of the Japanese prime minister, Koizumi Shinjiro, and members of the Liberal Democratic Party to shout **"Eliminate the United States with 500 hydrogen bombs."** Japan already has the ability to manufacture nuclear weapons. The Japanese are privately full of hatred towards the United States. Even Japanese female high school students are privately filled with hatred for the United States and want to use nuclear weapons against the United States. Japan only needs to launch three hydrogen bombs to basically destroy the United States.

由于父亲担任日本首相，很多话没办法在公开场合说出来，可却有可能在他亲生儿子面前流露出来。

比如说流露出美国对他的压制，而他只能忍辱负重，为了日本的将来不得不卑躬屈膝。而这一切，都被小泉进次郎看在眼里，恨在心中，也就出来了他的这句话。

据说这次聚会中，小泉进次郎高喊，“灭掉美国，赏他500颗氢弹”。而接下来的其他自民党高层也跟着喊出了这句话。

Fig 40.22A. At this gathering, Shinjiro Koizumi shouted, 'Eliminate America and

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reward him with 500 hydrogen bombs'. And then other high-ranking members of the Liberal Democratic Party also shouted out this sentence.

2024-06-01. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/J3JRQ3T8055369FX.html>

If the Japanese were truly a peace-loving nation, would a peace-loving nation still be so cruel, bloody and shameless in the 21st century after World War II?

19. The Japanese Nobel Prize winner not only acts as the head of spies, but is also warlike. The Japanese Nobel laureate and professor shouted: Japan has long infiltrated China and can still defeat China if a war breaks out.

Last year, the Japanese Nobel Prize winner and professor at Kyoto University, Tasuku Honjo, said: "Even if a war breaks out between China and Japan again, Japan still has the ability and strength to defeat China. Even though China has emerged at present, Japan has infiltrated in many fields and has the strength to disintegrate its interior. We not only affect their future direction; even if no conflict breaks out, I think our influence on them will continue to rise so that Japan can obtain more long-term benefits."

Mr. Nobel established the Nobel Prize with the hope of peace, but it was awarded to Japan, a war criminal country that did not fully compensate for its crimes and victims.

I believe that this university professor is by no means talking nonsense or making casual remarks; a Nobel Prize winner can enumerate infiltration in all aspects of China like counting family treasures and firmly believes that he has mastered our development direction and future.

This is a terrible result of the failure to severely punish war criminals and all the criminals of the Second World War.

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日本教授本庶佑，公开声称有信心从内部瓦解中国！

就在最近，日本京都大学高级研究所有一位名叫本庶佑的特别教授。他威胁说，如果中日战争开始，日本完全有能力打败中国，因为我们已经全面渗透到中国的各个领域，对中国的一举一动了如指掌。我们完全有能力肢解中国内部。

Fig 40.23A. Japanese Professor Motosuke Honjo, a Nobel laureate: Japan has fully penetrated into various fields of China. 2023-11-02. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/IIIU26V10528AOT4.html>

Warvigilance:

1	If Japan is truly a peace-loving country, then in the 21st century after World War II, would a peace-loving country still be so thoroughly infiltrating and preparing for war???
2	If Japan is truly a peace-loving country, then in the 21st century after World War II, would a peace-loving medical academician still be so familiar with the all-round infiltration of Japanese spies into China and the preparation for war with China???
3	As of today in the 21st century, how many Japanese medical academicians have joined Japanese spy organizations???
4	How many Japanese medical academicians are core members of Japanese spy organizations???
5	In general, only core members of spy organizations are familiar with the infiltration of another country. How many Japanese academicians have joined Japanese spy organizations???
6	How many of Japan's academicians and medical academicians have not joined Japanese spy organizations???

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7	<p>A French diplomat named Casseville once said that almost every Japanese person in China is a spy.</p> <p>Do you know how many Japanese expatriates were in China during the Second World War? In 1945, there were as many as 1.1 million people in the three northeastern provinces of China alone.</p>
8	<p>Japan's immigration program is a long-term major means of implementing espionage activities, waging aggressive wars, and annexing other countries.</p> <p>There are often strikingly similar scenes in history. Today, there are nearly three million Japanese immigrants in Brazil and they have purchased land three times the size of Japan's territory.</p> <p>What are they trying to do?</p> <p>Don't people know to be vigilant?</p>
9	<p>A letter from Major Casseville, military attaché of the French Embassy in China, to the French Ministry of Defense: The Japanese are arrogant, suspicious and stingy. They don't trust Europeans. They are keen on espionage activities and are also good at lying.</p>
10	<p>The culture, beliefs and values of a country determine the social system of a country.</p>

Serious crimes committed by Japanese nationals:

1. Japan was nominally a defeated country in World War II, but actually a victorious one. This is a country that loves war. Evil Japan massacred at least 30-50 million Chinese civilian women and children.

During the period of Japanese aggression against China and World War II, Japan was a country where the entire population committed crimes. Almost all Japanese people were extremely excited about Japan's invasion of China and Southeast Asia. This invasion led to the deaths of at least 51.80 million to 89.60 (100.80 million) Chinese people. From 1894, when Japan first occupied Chinese territory, China's population loss reached 280 million. Japanese invaders raped and gang-raped at least 31.45 million to 54.40 million (61.20 million) Chinese women and plundered at least 200,000 Chinese women as sex slaves.

Japan looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth US\$5,289-7,933.5 billion, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth US\$50,000 billion, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth \$ 132.55-280.5 billion, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about \$5,000 billion, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about \$800 billion, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth \$20,000-300,000 billion, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about \$3,535.71 billion.

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From 1957 to 2022, Buffett's average compound annual return on investment was 20.44%. Please calculate using 50% of Buffett's average annual rate of return on investment, what was the average annual rate of return on investment over 85 years (1928-1945-2024) for the evil Japanese invaders who plundered wealth from China?

2. Japan still suppresses the souls and national fortunes of many countries, including Germany, the United States, Canada, Singapore, and China, with the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls " or [the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔)].

Japan collected sacred stones from multiple countries and built the " **Tower of Suppressing Souls** " or [**the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔)**] in the 1940s, attempting to permanently suppress the souls or national destinies of multiple countries, including China, the United States, Germany, Canada, Russia, Singapore, Peru, South Korea, the Philippines, etc. This created 130 Guinness World Records. **Although Germany was an ally of Japan during World War II, Japan still used the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the souls and destinies of the Germans.**

To this day, Japan still uses the evil "**Tower of Suppressing Souls(八纎一宇塔)**" to suppress the souls and national fates of many countries such as Germany, the United States, Canada, Singapore, South Korea and China, etc.

To this day, on the back of the tower are still engraved the names of countries and places that Japan invaded during its military expeditions abroad since the 2600th year of the Japanese imperial era. An evil and anti-human country using witchcraft and religion to hinder human peace and sustainable development. **From the religious point of view, is the current US Treasury bond crisis related to the suppression of the US national games by the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" of Japan?**

3. Japanese lawmakers still worship collectively at the Yasukuni Shrine, which honors war criminals from the Pacific War, every year to this day.

On December 7, 1941, Japan launched a surprise attack on Pearl Harbor, resulting in the deaths of around 2,400 American servicemen and women, with 1,250 people injured. Six military ships were sunk, and 188 aircraft were destroyed. The following day, President Franklin D. Roosevelt declared December 7th as " the National Calamity Day " and declared war on Japan. However, on the 80th anniversary of the successful attack on Pearl Harbor by Japan, 99 Japanese lawmakers collectively paid tribute at the Yasukuni Shrine, which enshrines war criminals from the Pacific War.

4. Forcing British and American generals to eat Japanese feces for a long time

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Fig 35. [The American general who was captured by the Japanese army lived by eating excrement every day, and immediately committed suicide after being released. December 17, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/e383atq90514ni3b.html>]⁶⁹
[Including General Wainwright, General Moore, and other operational staff, they were first sent to prisoner-of-war camps in the Philippines and then transported to Thailand, Taiwan, Northeast China, and other places, starting their hellish lives that lasted for three years. In the words of General Wainwright, **"If we had known we would be treated like this, we would not have put down our guns."**

After they entered the prisoner-of-war camp, the first order was to immediately kneel down and kowtow when encountering Japanese soldiers. Not doing so would result in severe punishment. General Wainwright wrote in his memoir, "We have lost the most basic dignity as human beings. We are worse off than the dogs raised by the Japanese."

Once, a Japanese soldier spat on an American POW because he was working slowly. The American soldier turned around and startled the Japanese soldier. The enraged Japanese soldier forced the American soldier to lift a log and said, "If you dare put down the log, I will kill you." In order to survive, the American soldier carried the log for an hour.

The next day, everyone saw him wearing handcuffs and leg irons. One week later, he was never seen again.

In September 1942, this group of American prisoners of war were sent to Hualien in Taiwan by the Japanese army. At that time, all these American soldiers were emaciated, with the heaviest weighing 30 kg and the lightest weighing 20 kg. From a distance, they looked like dried corpses.

After entering the POW camp, the first order was to immediately kneel and bow

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when encountering Japanese soldiers. Failure to do so would result in severe punishment. In his memoir, General Wen Laitie wrote, "We had lost the most basic dignity as human beings, and there we were treated worse than the dogs the Japanese kept."

According to General Wen Laitie's memoirs, when they first entered, they ate a few wild vegetables every day, two meals a day. After being transferred to Taiwan, their food became even worse. Due to lack of nutrition, they would only have bowel movements about once a week, and the stools were hard and smelly.

What was most embarrassing being that, since Wen Laitie was the leader of the group, when the Japanese had nothing to do, they would bring a bowl of excrement for him to eat, while making his comrades watched. If he refused, his comrades would be killed.

In addition to Wen Laitie eating excrement, General Moore was also one of the people who was frequently taken care for by the Japanese army. Because of his quick temper, there were several conflicts, so the Japanese army "took care" of him even more. **Once, the Japanese army starved him for two days, and on the third day, when he was about to starve to death, they brought him a large bowl of excrement to eat.]**

5. Many Chinese and Allied prisoners of war were subjected to brutal live bacterial experiments and autopsies by the Japanese. The Japanese army has carried out countless massacres and plunders of wealth against the Chinese.

Japan, a neighboring country of China, treated American and British prisoners of war so savagely. Many Allied prisoners of war were subjected to cruel live bacterial experiments and live dissections.^{71,72} Australian nurses were treated as sex slaves by the Japanese military, and American female soldiers were tortured and burned by the Japanese military (there are many videos online showing Japanese mistreatment of prisoners of war).^{73,74} The evil Japanese invaders killed approximately 100,000 prisoners of war who had laid down their weapons during the Nanjing Massacre.⁷⁵ Based on prisoner of war ethics or metrological prisoner of war ethics, it should be quite clear which country is more suitable to become a friend of the United States.

However, the preferential treatment policy of the Chinese Communist Party government for prisoners of war is difficult for any other country to achieve. Surprisingly, the food of U.S. and United Nations military prisoners of war was even better than that of China's own military. In the Korean War, U.S. and U.N. prisoners of war captured by China were able to participate in the unprecedented prisoner of war Olympic Games, which can be considered a miracle in the history of human warfare.⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸ On November 15, 1952, from a total of 3107 prisoners of war in all six prison camps, 500 athletes were selected from 14 countries and regions including the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Canada, Colombia, Australia, South Korea, the Philippines, Turkey, the Netherlands, Belgium, Greece, Mexico, and Puerto Rico to participate in this grand event. The conference also specifically designed two slogans: "The Games are the path to friendship" and "Peace is the goal for everyone." The competition lasted 12 days and ended on November 26, with a total of 31 events. American

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prisoners of war swept the top three places in the 100-meter race, with Thomas, an American, winning the 100-meter champion with a time of 10.6 seconds. Korean prisoners of war dominated the top three places in the 3000-meter race. A British athlete named George Green won the 1,500 meter race. Arif Gekce, a Turkish, created a record of seven consecutive wins and won the title of wrestling king. The prizes were handcrafted items purchased from cities such as Beijing, Shanghai, and Shenyang, including cloisonné vases, silk umbrellas, sandalwood fans, jade necklaces, and silk scarves. Prisoners of war were in high spirits during the award ceremony, filled with laughter and joy everywhere.

Fig 40.16A. Japanese invaders dissected live Chinese babies and placed them in

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formalin to make specimens. <https://v.kuaishou.com/Ltz3MF>

Fig

40.18A. Japanese invaders dissected live Chinese babies and placed them in formalin to make specimens. 2023-08-29.

<https://www.douyin.com/note/7272530954965552443>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

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Fig 178. Chinese infants **dissected alive using formalin soaking in Japanese 731 unit.** [Dogs can never change their habit of eating feces. Those who say China Japan is friendly are actually traitors and traitors. Don't forget blood and tears, don't forget national shame.2023-05-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAbhGbx/>]

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——勿忘国耻——

山西发现14个万人坑
最大一个埋葬了6万人
森森白骨在抗议日本的罪行

Fig 174. [After the Japanese invaders occupied Datong coal mines, they plundered the resources frenziedly. Under the bloody rule of the Japanese army, large numbers of miners who were battered to death or left to die were discarded in abandoned mine shafts. Among them, there were a total of 14 pits of ten thousand corpses, each with a level of over 10,000 individuals, with the largest containing the remains of 60,000 people – all with missing limbs, some with only their heads remaining. The silent bones stand as ironclad evidence that cannot ever erase the heinous crimes committed by the Japanese military in China. #Remember History #Never Forget National Humiliation. 2022-01-08. <https://v.douyin.com/iNA4eX1M/> 12/20 b@N.wS VL:/]

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Fig. 893. After the Lugou Bridge Incident in 1937, the Japanese invaders launched a massive attack on the North China Plain. On October 24th, the Japanese army broke through Cheng'an City in Hebei and brutally **slaughtered more than 5,300 innocent compatriots, creating the shocking "Cheng'an Massacre" that shocked both China and foreign countries.** In the evening of October 24th, after the Japanese army entered Cheng'an City, they set up machine guns on the west city wall and fired at the crowd along the east-west street, causing most of the innocent civilians to fall in a pool of blood. The methods of the Japanese aggressors in massacring people were devoid of humanity. **After killing the ordinary people, they used their bodies to fill up the low-lying sections of the road, and then covered it with a layer of soil to facilitate vehicle passage!** #Resistance War #Never Forget National Humiliation #Never Forget History Self-Strengthening #Remember History. 2023-07-19 <https://v.douyin.com/iJryxGng/> **"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")**

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig 176. After the cruel Japanese army insulted our female compatriots, they **cruelly cut off her breasts**. [Dogs can never change their habit of eating feces. Those who say China Japan is friendly are actually traitors and traitors. Don't forget blood and tears, don't forget national shame.2023-05-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAbhGbx/>]

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

The **"three all" policy** of the Japanese invasion of China: **burning all, killing all, and looting all.**

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

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Fig.809. The evil Japanese army cut the Chinese alive.
[<https://v.douyin.com/iJUweGs6/>]

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Fig. 205. **One of the tortures of the Evil, shameless, cruel, despicable I Japanese Evil Staphylococcus aureus Japanese Unit 731** The Japanese Unit 731 vivisection: a comfort woman (**Sex slave**) was raped by evil Japanese soldiers and then subjected to a live dissection, during which her breasts were removed, and her left eye was excised to be preserved as a specimen. [In the living experiment of Japanese Unit 731, a sex slave was unscrewed and his breasts were cut off..... <https://v.douyin.com/iXu4h6e/>]

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魔鬼731拿中国人做细菌实验照片

照片中可见一名年轻的中国女孩，她躺在一块木板上，身体极度虚弱，肚子凹陷，身体被注入多种细菌，痛苦地死去…

Fig 105. Devil Unit 731 Conducting Bacterial Experiments on a Chinese Girl

The photo shows a young Chinese girl lying on a wooden plank, extremely weak, with a sunken abdomen, her body injected with various bacteria, suffering a painful death... [The photograph was taken by the Japanese army and is currently preserved at the 731 Unit War Crimes Exhibition Hall in Harbin City. This photo reveals the extreme cruelty of bacterial experiments committed by the Japanese military in China. #Devil 731Unit #Remember History Never Forget National Humiliation. 2023-09-11. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6wacRq/12/11jCh:/S@Y.md>]

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Fig 106. Japanese Army Doctor of Unit 731 Injecting Bacterial Toxins into Children [#Tear Eyes # Real Case Records # Remembering # **731 Bacterial Warfare** # **Japanese atrocities**. 2023-03-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6wgjRf/06/07AGv:/r@e.bn> "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.")

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Fig 108. [Victims of evil Japanese Army's Bacterial Warfare: Wounds Remain Unhealed After 70 Years, Skin Crawling with Maggots, No Cure for Decades, One Leg Rotted Away to a Single Tendon #War #Peace #Never Forget National Humiliation. 2022-03-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6KaUMJ/v@s.RK10/20aNw:/>]

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Fig 112. ZheGan Bacterial Warfare Massacre

[The evil and despicable Japanese launched a biological war with anthrax, resulting in an incurable case of gangrene in victims from Zhejiang Province. 2021-09-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6E315h/07/25c@a.NjRkc/>]

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Fig 116. [After brutally slaughtering the Chinese people, the Japanese troops inserted branches into their skulls, which had been reduced to bare bones, and piled them up to create a spectacle for photographs to boast about. 2023-09-05. https://v.douyin.com/iNM1F5Ky/NwS:/01/09_Y@m.dN **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.")

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Fig 117. Nanjing Massacre [In December 1937, the Japanese army committed a frenzied massacre in Nanjing. Along the docks near the Yangtze River outside the city of Nanjing, the invaders brutally killed the civilians and then tied their corpses with ropes, dragging them by boat into the river to drift away. It is hoped that young people will understand the tragedy of their forebears. #Resistance War #Nanjing Massacre #Japanese Atrocities #Remember History #Never Forget History. 2024-02-11. <https://v.douyin.com/iNrxUsK6/> dnD:/ 01/29 [F@U.Lj](#) "Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

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美军发现青岛实验室 意外揭开日本滔天罪行 简直就是恶魔

Fig 153. After Japan's surrender in 1945, **U.S. troops in Qingdao began to sweep the battlefield.** As they entered a club established by the Japanese, they discovered a hidden cellar. When they opened door to the cellar, they were greeted by a pungent smell of antiseptics, and the dank and dark basement emitted the same harsh odor, giving everyone a sense of foreboding. Suddenly, they found three tubs in the corner, each containing the body of an infant soaked inside. Although American soldiers were accustomed to seeing dead bodies, such a sinister scene still made their skin crawl. After a search, they found that each infant had a strange sequence of numbers marked on them: **33, 35, and 99.** One soldier speculated that it might have been a biochemical base of the Japanese army and that the children were pitiful test subjects. Hearing this, everyone on-site got chills down their spines, and they immediately contacted the police. The authorities arrived at the scene promptly after receiving the report and found that the tragic infants were all less than a year old, with evident signs of abuse on their bodies, eyes gouged out, and abdomen dissected. According to the codes on the infants' bodies, at least 99 babies were tortured to death by the Japanese. Before

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Japan's surrender, many Japanese had fled back to their country, with only a few still staying temporarily in China. The police brought them all to the station for questioning, hoping to learn something. However, these Japanese doctors denied the killings and claimed that the Yamato people would never harm infants, insisting that it was definitely a conspiracy by the Americans to frame the Japanese. However, it wasn't long before the police received another report; another vat was found in another Japanese stronghold, filled with the corpses of Chinese children. People who had lived nearby reported that the Japanese army had secretly conducted human experiments there and abducted many people.

[After Japan's surrender, the US military discovered a laboratory in Qingdao where Japanese people stored baby specimens, unexpectedly exposing Japan's heinous crimes # 731 Unit # World War II # 731 Bacterial Warfare.2023-04-27. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAXQGxq/OKj:/06/27e@B.gB>]

Fig 182. The barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese cut off the heads of the Chinese people and took photos with a smile to show off. 2023-12-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAGQyRm/06/08D@h.oDlpQ:/>

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy,

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Fig 183. In the Nanjing Massacre of 1937, **the Japanese army brutally killed Chinese children**. The inhumane devils cruelly tied them to trees with steel nails and wire. 2023-12-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAGQyRm/06/08D@h.oDlpQ:/>

Fig 184. Miyamoto Kenji, a former Japanese soldier who invaded China, recounted his experiences during the invasion through oral testimonies before his death. He admitted to becoming addicted to killing while in China, claiming to have sexually assaulted 34 women, personally killed 8 women, and shot and injured 3 more. He described a **horrific incident in which they tied up a 15-year-old female nurse, cut open her stomach alive next to a fire pit, removed her uterus, which was the size of an egg, and roasted it by the flames...** **The girl whose abdomen was cut open was not dead at the time, lying aside, lifelessly watching as her own uterus was consumed.** #Japanese Army Atrocities #Never Forget National Humiliation #Forgetting History

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Means Betrayal # 2023-07-12. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAGneLW/> 12/05 u@F.UL Agb:/

Fig 185. The evil Japanese invaders in China often cut off male genitalia, eat them, and improve sexual function.

[Japanese atrocities. The hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten. Don't forget national shame. 2023-11-08. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAtALuE/> M@J.II jPx:/10/02]

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas

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Fig 186. The US military is searching for the remains of American prisoners of war who were eaten by the Japanese on the Ogasawara Islands. [2023-09-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAnAdFt/R@K.jP Wzg:/ 09/0>]

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Fig 187. The evil Japanese doctors of **Unit 731** are undergoing live dissection, preparing to extract various organs for experiments. [2023-09-07. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAnEY92/05/04Slc:/k@C.hb>]

Which nation is the most evil, cruel, and despicable in the entire universe?

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Fig 194. Unique and cruel **barbecue torture against American female prisoners of war**

Translation of this referenced document: During World War II, Japanese forces devised a particularly brutal form of **torture for American female prisoner of war**, mockingly referred to as "barbecue punishment." Despite its seemingly innocuous name, those female soldiers quickly discovered the grim reality behind it. The question arises—would Japanese soldiers (derogatorily referred to as "little devils") really be so kind as to treat them to a barbecue?

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First, they imprisoned these **American female prisoner of war** together, starving them for several days, all the while subjecting them to intense labor. After a few days, hunger became unbearable for these soldiers. When the women were weakened and unable to resist, the Japanese would take them to a closed room with a fire burning next to several pieces of meat. The origin of the meat was unknown. The women, driven by extreme hunger, were handed pieces of this mysterious meat, which they ate voraciously without considering the possibility of dangers hidden within.

As American women were eating, **evil Japanese soldiers would take hot red iron pokers and thrust them into the US women's abdomen**, piercing through them. They carefully avoided vital organs **to prevent immediate death, prolonging the victims' agony**. When the women fainted from intense pain, the soldiers would revive them with cold water, only to resume the torture with iron pokers, filling the air with the smell of burning flesh and the women's hysterical screams.

After one group of soldiers underwent this torture, the next batch would be brought in, and the horrific suffering left lifelong scars that American women could not escape. **Most US women died from the torture**, but this was not the most ruthless method they employed. The Japanese had prepared **many soldering irons with sharpened edges**. They would **heat these soldering irons until red-hot, and once the female soldiers were securely bound, the evil Japanese pressed the soldering irons against the women's bodies through their clothes, causing immediate, excruciating screams**. The clothes quickly burned through as the soldering irons seared their flesh. The **US women prisoner of war** struggled desperately on the rack, but they could not escape and could only endure the burning punishment.

Evil Japan soldiers continued to move the soldering irons across every part of the victims' bodies, leaving no patch of skin untouched and causing pain until unconsciousness followed. The inhuman Japanese soldiers, excited by the women's screams and pleas for mercy, only intensified their actions. **When one victim died, they simply moved on to the next**. When these female prisoners of war were eventually rescued from the camps, only a small fraction survived.

The "barbecue" and branded iron tortures were merely glimpses into the cruelty inflicted upon prisoners of war by the Japanese forces, who had even more barbaric methods they had yet to unleash.

[The captured American female soldiers by the Japanese army suffered terribly, with a unique form of punishment known as "the barbecue," which inflicted such pain that the female prisoners wished for death. 2023-08-10. <https://v.douyin.com/iNUbGGe4/L@w.se> 04/27 CHV:/]

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日军将这些中国儿童劫掠过去绝不仅仅只是为了运往日本培养成将来侵华的牺牲品，更令人发指的是把这些孩子当做“行走的血袋”，为日本伤兵输血。

Fig. 225. The Japanese military's abduction of these Chinese children was not just for transporting them to Japan to be groomed as future sacrifices for further invasions of China. What's even more appalling is that **these children were used as "walking blood bags" to provide blood transfusions for the wounded.**

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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日本对中国儿童的劫掠即便就在日军投降以后也丝毫没有收敛。1945年9月16日下午，一辆载有10名日本士兵的汽车在广州凤安桥边遭中国警察拦截，在进行检查时发现在车上的行李里隐藏着3名中国儿童。日军辩称这3名儿童是在日军部队里从事煮饭等杂役，因没钱回家，准备将他们带到日军驻地后给予钱粮遣散。中国警察在给了3名儿童米粮后让他们自行离开。

Fig. 226. Even after the surrender of the Japanese military, the looting of Chinese children by Japan did not stop. On the afternoon of September 16, 1945, a car carrying 10 Japanese soldiers was intercepted by Chinese police at Feng'an Bridge in Guangzhou. During the inspection, three Chinese children were found hidden in in the car's luggage. The Japanese military argued that the three children were engaged in menial tasks such as cooking in the Japanese army and, having no money to return home, they were planning to take them to the Japanese garrison and provide them with money and food before sending them away. After giving the three children rice, the Chinese police allowed them to leave on their own.

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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同样是在广州，一辆日军军车在撞伤一名人力车夫后被迫停下，日军一反常态的主动提出愿意以3袋大米来赔偿车夫。围观群众及警察在查看日军随车货物的时候，发现有三个麻袋在晃动。打开一开，每个麻袋里竟然都装着一名儿童，日军在被带回警局后承认，这三名儿童是他们抓回来的杂役，准备蒙混过关，带入看管日军的战俘营，以便在日本投降后继续供他们驱使奴役。

日军劫掠中国儿童的目的除了供他们驱使成为奴役之外，当时国民政府调查表明日本还计划将这些儿童训练后用于将来驾驶自杀式飞机进行“特攻”作战，或做为秘密细菌实验的牺牲品。

战后日本为了掩盖这一段极为不光彩的历史，刻意的将关于劫掠中国妇女儿童的材料进行了销毁，也使得日军的罪行至今鲜为人知。

Fig. 227. In Guangzhou, a Japanese military vehicle struck and injured a rickshaw puller and was forced to stop. In a rare move, the Japanese military voluntarily offered to compensate the rickshaw puller with three bags of rice. When the onlookers and police inspected the goods accompanying the Japanese military vehicle, they found three sacks shaking. Upon opening them, each sack was found to contain a child. The Japanese military admitted, after being taken back to the police station, that these three children were kidnapped laborers, intended to be smuggled into the prisoner of war camp where the Japanese military was held, in order to continue to serve as forced labor after Japan's surrender.

The purpose of the Japanese military looting Chinese children was not only to serve as forced labor, but also, according to investigations by the Nationalist government at the time, Japan planned to train these children for future use in piloting suicide planes for "kamikaze" operations or as sacrificial victims for secret bacteriological experiments. After the war, Japan deliberately destroyed materials related to the looting of Chinese women and children in order to cover up this extremely disgraceful period of history, making the atrocities committed by the Japanese military still relatively unknown to this day.

[The invading Japanese army **once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers**, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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Evil Japanese soldier invading
China

关于日军劫掠拐骗中国儿童的事实，著名的左翼女作家，北京师范大学教授彭慧曾在1938年写下了著名的《怀念被敌船载去的孩子们》一诗，曾使许多读者流下了眼泪。

“如今，白白地，看着你们成了强盗的俘虏！如今，空望着，万恶不赦的倭寇，在黄浦江上，将你们一船船载走！……午夜，我怕听到孤雁的哀鸣。那令我忆起，在日本海峡的那边，那强盗们的巢穴里，正睡着哀哀啼哭的叫不应妈妈的你们！……他要教你们教成小小的强盗，他要教你们背叛祖国，他要唆使你们来残杀自己的同胞，专听他们的征调。你们幼小的心灵要牢牢牢记：你们是黄帝的子孙，是诚实耐劳的大中华民族的世裔，你们身在扶桑，心不要忘了祖国！你们不要甘心作奴隶！……到最后胜利的那天，我们还要过海洋，来寻找你们的踪迹，把

Fig. 228. Regarding the fact that the Japanese army looted and abducted Chinese children, a famous writer and professor at Beijing Normal University, wrote the famous poem "Remembering the Children Taken Away by Enemy Ships" in 1938, which brought tears to many readers' eyes.

"Now, I see you, innocent and pure, become captives of bandits. Now, I gaze into the distance, as the unforgivable Japanese pirates, on the Huangpu River, take you all away in boat after boat. ... At midnight, I fear hearing the lonely geese's mournful cries. It reminds me of you, on the other side of the Japan Sea, in the bandits' nest, sleeping with tearful cries, calling for your mothers. ... They want to teach you to be little bandits, to betray your motherland, to incite you to kill your compatriots, and obey their commands. Your young hearts must remember: you are descendants of the Yellow Emperor, descendants of the honest and hardworking Chinese nation, you are in Japan, but do not forget your homeland. Do not be willing slaves. ... On the day of final victory, we will cross the ocean to find your traces and bring you back to our motherland."

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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1945年，日本在中国掳走数万名儿童，至今77年时间仍然是个谜

阿七说史 2022-10-05 18:47 河南

在《国际联盟盟约》中，曾有着这样一条规定，禁止任何国家以任何手段贩卖、掳掠妇女和儿童，而这项准则几乎是现代战争中，所有国家必须遵守的人道主义铁律之一，日本在这份盟约的最后，也信誓旦旦地署上了自己的名字。

但是随着日军侵华脚步的全面兴起，他们却将这条规定抛诸脑后，做出了一系列违背人道主义原则的恶性，他们在中国扔下了数不尽的炮弹，将城市炸成了一片废墟，他们将大量的劳力抓捕起来，通过不光彩的手段，偷偷运到工地上，没日没夜地进行工作。

日本臭名昭著的731部队，更是以非人的手段，用中国民众进行实验，而最恶劣的是，他们仅仅用了几年时间，就从我国掳掠走了上千名儿童，至今不知去向。

迄今为止，日本仍未承认他们的恶性，对于曾经的恶行更是闭口不谈，甚至不断地美化他们的侵略行为。

Fig. 229. In 1945, Japan abducted tens of thousands of children in China, which remains a mystery for 77 years. Aqi talks about history. October 5th, 2022. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1745844307445724066&wfr=spider&for=pc> **"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")**

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig 40.32A. Japanese officer Haijiu Kusui enjoyed making tobacco pipes from children's leg bones and brutally killed more than 100 Chinese children. After the war, he had a son and a daughter; the son was born with an intellectual disability, and the daughter was paralyzed on one side of her body. [2023-10-

26. <https://v.douyin.com/iNmuEEEd3/> 1@P.xf wfO:/ 08/04]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig 40.34A. Alive Mother and her daughter were roasted into dry corpses by the Japanese army 731 Unit. 2024-01-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iNmHV65b/> Rxs:/ I@V.lc 03/17

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

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Fig. 85-23-6. **Tanaka Memorial of Japan's desire to dominate the world**

The overall strategic plan for Japan's conquest of the world - Tanaka Memorial

Japan's proposed "New Continent policy" towards China was documented in a file. From June 27 to July 7, 1927, Japanese Prime Minister Tanaka Giichi convened the Oriental Conference in Tokyo, attended by officials from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Army, the Ministry of Navy, the General Staff, the Military Command, the Kwantung Army, and the resident diplomats in China. The conference adopted the "Outline of China Policy." On July 25, Tanaka wrote to Minister of the Imperial Household, Yoshinori Ichiki, to request the Emperor's approval for the "Empire's proactive fundamental policy towards Manchuria and Mongolia." He stated, "My rights and interests in Manchuria and Mongolia are enormous. Therefore, every cabinet in history has followed the teachings of Emperor Meiji, expanding its scale and implementing the New Continent policy." He believed that the current Chinese authorities in the three eastern provinces were becoming aware, and the Nine-Power Treaty restricted "my special rights and interests in Manchuria and Mongolia." He emphasized that "if we do not make every effort to break through, our country's

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existence will not be solid, and our national power will not develop." He further stressed, "The Russo-Japanese War was essentially a war against China that we supported. In the future, if we want to control China, **we must first eliminate American influence as a prerequisite.** It is similar in significance to the Russo-Japanese War. However, **if we want to conquer China, we must first conquer Manchuria and Mongolia. If we want to conquer the world, we must first conquer China. If China is completely conquered by our country, other nations such as Central Asia, India, and Southeast Asia, which are different from us, will fear and respect us, and surrender to us."**

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<https://baike.so.com/doc/5933237-6146167.html>

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这是一张记录抗战时期的照片，照片中的这名日本侵略者赤裸上身，属于日军第六师团，他怀中抱着的是在“扫荡”行动中掠夺的“战利品”。在侵华战争期间，日军推行了极端残酷的“三光政策”，包括“杀戮、抢劫、焚烧”。这是日本军国主义在侵华战争中实施的一种野蛮政策。具体来说，日军在占领区进行了大规模的屠杀和强奸，抢夺了大量的粮食、财物和资源。他们不仅对中国军民犯下了无数罪行，还对被占领区的政治、经济和社会文化进行了全面控制和掠夺。在这张照片中，他们的笑容背后，是中国无数人遭受痛苦和

Fig 85-23-12. The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all. [The photo shows the scene of barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese invaders snatching food from Chinese villagers. 2023-10-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAXrH5y/01/28 CUL:/ H@V.YG>]

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing

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complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

Fig 85-23-8. This is a Chinese cultural relic that was looted and placed at the National Museum in Tokyo. [How much wealth does Japan plunder from China?2023-01-13. https://v.douyin.com/iNACmYcP/dAT:/04/06_r@R.Kw]

The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and

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looting all.

Fig 85-23-10. The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all. [The photo shows the scene of barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese invaders snatching pigs from Chinese villagers. 2023-12-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAXBJaP/>]

Most of the wealth possessed by the evil Japanese country and its citizens was

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plundered from China.

Fig 85-23-13. In May 1939, two traitors and a large number of Japanese invaders went to the countryside to grab grain. Three innocent girls over the age of ten were also abducted by the evil, despicable, and shameless Japanese people. The girls remained childish and trembling with fear and helplessness. 2024-02-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAX8w6L/04/22> Tyt:/ G@v.SI

If the United States were occupied by Japan, how many traitors would lead the evil,

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despicable and shameless Japanese to capture young girls?

Fig. 158. Group photo of some demons in Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japanese Unit 731 [Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious.

July 3, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/GMJ6EIH00543L37L.html>]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Fig. 159. The Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japanese Army Is Implementing Biological warfare [Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them

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go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious. July 3, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HBAL24ES0552RJN1.html>]

Fig. 160. Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese Unit 731 [The Japanese Unit 731 was extremely cruel, forcing 500 students to eat a Shaobing (Baked cake in griddle) each, causing the plague.

Original 2022-08-08; <https://www.toutiao.com/article/7129346942869586473/>]

Fig. 161. Experimental Site of Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese Unit

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731[Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious. July 3, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HBAL24ES0552RJN1.html>]

Fig. 162. Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese 731 experimenter with hands stained with blood from multiple countries [Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious.

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Fig. 163. One of the tortures of the evil Japanese:

Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japanese Unit 731 conducts bacteria experiments with Chinese. [Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious. July 3, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HBAL24ES0552RJN1.html>]

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

Fig. 164. The "August 4" murder in 1950 caused by the poison gas bomb buried by the Japanese Unit 731. The Cruel Actions of the Japanese

In 1945, when Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japan withdrew from China, they buried all the chemical weapons they had manufactured in Harbin, China. The first discovery was made in 1950 when several workers were carrying out construction at Heilongjiang First Normal School. During the construction process, they stumbled upon two large iron barrels buried in the ground. The workers were curious and unscrewed the screws on the wooden barrels.

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Suddenly, an extremely foul smell hit them. School workers immediately experienced swelling on their faces, blistering in their mouths, and convulsions. All the pores on their skin died. Even the doctors who treated these workers suffered discomfort whenever they sweated due to exposure to gas. This construction accident resulted in 44 people being infected by chemical gas, resulting in one death on the spot.

Experts conducted a two-year follow-up survey of these 44 patients. The examination revealed that many of the infected individuals suffered significant weight loss and adverse changes in liver cells and liver function. They also experienced various long-term effects that accompanied them until death. The Japanese have completely lost their human rationality.

According to statistics, during the Second World War, Japan manufactured a total of four million chemical gas bombs. Almost all of these chemical bombs were used on Chinese soil, with fewer than 300,000 transported to other countries. Following Japan's defeat, under the terms of surrender, the Japanese army was to either transport or destroy all chemical gas bombs remaining in China.

However, the ambitious Japanese only took away one million chemical bombs when they retreated, leaving the remaining three million still buried in Chinese soil. Their officers ordered the burial of all remaining chemical gas bombs in China during the retreat, with the largest number of them being left in Yanbian, Jilin Province. [The Japanese Unit 731 was extremely cruel, forcing 500 students to eat a Shaobing (Baked cake in griddle) each, causing the plague.

Original 2022-08-08; <https://www.toutiao.com/article/7129346942869586473/>]

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

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Fig. 166. One of the tortures of the evil Japanese:
In the horrendous Nanjing Massacre, a Chinese woman was brutally decapitated.

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and the blood spattered from her saber. The mother opened her mouth wide and her face deformed. Although she died with great fear, she still held the child tightly in her hands.

This is a real photograph of the Nanjing Massacre Memorial Hall. An innocent civilian woman holding her baby in her arms was beheaded by evil Japanese soldiers, and blood splattered from her neck in the air. Even today, the Emperor, Prime Minister, and other Japanese officials, as well as ordinary citizens, still pay tribute to the war criminals who committed these killings every year. **Isn't the Japanese nation an extremely barbaric, extremely cruel, extremely despicable, extremely anti-human, and extremely savage nation?** As the supreme strategist and commander of a war, isn't the evil Japanese Emperor a war criminal who has been overlooked and not properly punished or sent to the gallows?

The actions of the **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese invaders,** devoid of humanity and inhumane, have no reason or qualification to forgive the Japanese for our ancestors.[<https://v.douyin.com/iyT57f9/>]

Is the Japanese not a species that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

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Fig. 171. One of the tortures of the Japanese: "Motherhood Experiment".

During World War II, the **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese military** conducted a cruel experiment called the "Motherhood Experiment", aiming to test the limits of a mother's love and protective instinct for her child. They specially constructed a sealed house with a heating system underneath, creating a boiler-like environment.

On that day, they selected a mother and her child, both of whom were asked to remove their shoes and were pushed into the sealed house. The wicked Japanese soldiers outside immediately locked the door, and the lower level soldiers started to ignite the charcoal. Within a short period of time, the temperature of the floor began to rise.

Inside the house, the mother, suffering from the burning sensation on her feet, started running around the room in discomfort, occasionally screaming in pain. However, even in this situation, she held onto her child and did not put him down to relieve her burden.

The brainwashed and **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese soldiers** outside, who were there to witness the spectacle, burst into laughter. They even made bets, stating that the mother would not be able to endure and would eventually put her child down to use him as a footrest.

But the mother's actions disappointed these beasts. As temperature of the floor continued to rise, the mother eventually collapsed from exhaustion. However, she placed her child on her own body, using herself as a barrier against high temperatures. At this point, the purpose of the experiment had already been achieved. However, the insane Japanese soldiers did not stop the experiment, and in the end, both the mother and child were roasted to death by the intense heat inside the house.

The **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese army** attached to the evil cult not only captured many mothers and children to repeat the experiment of motherhood, but also captured people from different countries to do the experiment, and also captured Russians to test motherhood.[Remember history and never forget national shame# Remembering History # Forgetting National Shame # <https://v.douyin.com/iqHmR7S/>], [In 1941, the "motherly love experiment" of Japanese Unit 731 was more cruel than human imagination. December 30, 2022; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1753614066831032066&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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Fig. 172. **One of the tortures of the evil Japanese!** The evil Japanese Unit 731 uses live babies to be delivered as specimens.[<https://v.douyin.com/iq8eCp2/>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

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Fig. 173. **One of the tortures of the Japanese:**

This young girl resisted gang rape by **Evil Staphylococcus aureus**---Japanese invaders and was **dissected** and **cut off pieces of flesh from her thighs**, using a knife to carry a barbecue and eat. [In the living experiment of Japanese Unit 731, a sex slave was unscrewed and his breasts were cut off..... <https://v.douyin.com/iXu4h6e/>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 174. One of the tortures of the Japanese

This young girl resisted gang rape by **Evil Staphylococcus aureus**---Japanese invaders and was dissected and cut off pieces of flesh from her thighs, using a knife to carry a barbecue and eat.

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"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.")

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 188. Survivor in Sex Slaves

[In 1944, the Chinese Expeditionary Force defeated the Japanese troops in Tengchong, Yunnan and rescued a group of Japanese military's sex slaves. **This real footage was captured by an American journalist.** #ExpeditionaryForce #RememberHistory #RealFootage #TengchongBattle. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6yLQnt/>]

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Fig. 189. Survivor in Sex Slaves: The woman, after being rescued by the expeditionary force, exclaimed "long live".

In September 1944, during the final stage of the Battle of Tengchong in Yunnan, the Japanese army, realizing that defending the city was hopeless, shot a group of sex slaves before fleeing. They then forced the remaining 30 sex slaves to retreat with them. However, they were rescued by the Chinese Expeditionary Force. One of the sex slaves had been beaten by the Japanese army and had a face covered in blood, looking extremely horrifying. The whole incident was documented by an American war photographer embedded with the troops on September 14, 1944.

[2020-08-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ65XgFN/>]

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Fig. 190. Nanjing Massacre: Real photos

After Japanese pigs raped and gang raped Women in China in the Nanjing Massacre, they were forced to walk naked to gather. [Iron evidence, on December 13, 1937, Japanese pigs committed a horrendous crime in Nanjing, China, humiliating Women in China compatriots, and never forget the national humiliation and military humiliation! 2022-12-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iJLs6wus/>]

Isn't the Japanese a pig? Pigs don't wear clothes because pigs are not humans! Do you like your wife and daughter being raped and gang raped by the Japanese?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

1937年南京大屠杀 真实照片记实

铭记历史 勿忘国耻

Fig. 193. Nanjing Massacre: Real photos
"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

[Iron evidence, on December 13, 1937, Japanese pigs committed a horrendous crime in Nanjing, China, humiliating Women in China compatriots, and never forget the national humiliation and military humiliation! <https://v.douyin.com/iJLs6wus/>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

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Fig. 194. During the Japanese invasion, these women were raped, gang-raped, and humiliated by the Japanese aggressors. They were stripped naked, nailed to trees, covered in lard, and left to be devoured alive by mountain ants. [Can we forget the atrocities committed by the Japanese invaders? Can we dare forget them? #NeverForgetBloodTearsNeverForgetNationalHumiliation #Japanese Military Atrocities #We Must Be Strong #Remember History. 2023-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6R2hHY/>]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

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讨论

分享

言分享

良微博

空间

原创 侵华老兵战争期间祸害33名中国女性，晚年儿孙遭遇车祸，全部身亡

2022-03-31 21:16

中国有句古话叫：“善有善报恶有恶报，不是不报，是時候未到。”在2007年之前，日本侵华老兵赤坚柏仓对这句话并没有太深的感悟。但儿孙遭车祸全部去世后，他才明白：原来世上真的有报应这回事！而他当年在中国犯下的错，全部报应在了他子孙的身上。

赤坚柏仓参加侵华日军

赤坚柏仓于1920年出生在日本川崎，他上面还有一个哥哥，名叫赤坚村野。他们的母亲早逝，父亲只是一个普通的打工人，所以日子过得比较艰辛。为了改变家族命运，赤坚柏仓的父亲省吃俭用，供他们兄弟俩读书。原本父亲还希望赤坚柏仓兄弟学业有成，将来有个好前途，没想到却碰上日本发动了侵略战争。

Fig. 195. A Japanese soldier killed 8 women and raped 33. In his later years, his children and grandchildren were all killed in a car accident.

Japanese army raped at least 92.4 million Chinese women and killed 22.4 million Chinese women in China.

The Japanese army has killed at least 61.6 million people in China

Germany only killed about 150,000-45,000 Jews during World War II instead of 6 million people.

At the end of World War II, literature reported that a total of 6 million Jews were massacred, of which, 4 million Jews died in the Auschwitz concentration camp, with a total death toll at the camp reaching 4.1 million people. However, research by the team led by Dr. Franciszek Piper, a Polish Jewish scholar, relative of Auschwitz victims, and head of the Historical Research Department of the Auschwitz Museum, found that about 1.1 million people perished in the Auschwitz concentration camp, with approximately 960,000 of them being Jewish. Consequently, the total number of Jewish deaths during World War II became 2.96 million. Since documents report that Poles massacred about 3 million out of 3.3 million Jews in Poland, not Germans, if so, the number attributed to German-perpetrated Jewish massacres would be negative 4 million, which is unreasonable. Considering that there were 150,000 Jews in the German army, and that Germany has no documents ordering the extermination of Jews but instead more about driving them out, there may be errors in the total number of Jews massacred by Poland. Therefore, if the figure of 3 million massacred by Poland is adjusted to 2.81 million, the number of Jews massacred by Germany during World War II is 150,000."

There is an old saying in China: "Good will be rewarded, evil will be punished. It's not that there is no retribution, the time has not come." Before 2007, Japanese invader

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Akira Yamaguchi did not really understand the meaning behind this phrase. However, after all his children and grandchildren died in the car accident, he finally realized that there is indeed karma in this world. The wrongs he committed in China many years ago were all repaid to his descendants.

In his final days, Sekijun Bai Sou said, "It was that evil war of aggression that made me lose my humanity, lose my character, lose my dignity, and become a murderer... Japan and China must never go to war again! We must never go to war again!" In his "Confessions of Repentance," he openly revealed the heinous crimes committed by Japanese militarism in initiating the war of aggression against China. Here are a few excerpts:

In the 13th year of the Showa era, I came to Anyi, Shanxi, China singing military songs and spent six years of my demonic life here. I still remember the lyrics of that military song: "Crossing over mountains, corpses spread throughout; Crossing oceans, corpses floating on the surface; Dying for the Emperor, seeing death as returning home!" At that time, I didn't feel the lyrics were cruel and explicit; instead, I felt them full of heroic spirit. Because during my nationalistic education in Japan, the instructors said: Our great Japanese nation is a superior nation in the world, and the Chinese people are an inferior nation. Therefore, we Japanese militaristic soldiers, as soon as we stepped onto Chinese soil, had a contemptuous attitude and a sense of conquest towards the Chinese people.

At first, we were all afraid of killing people, always unable to hit the mark. After committing mass violence, we tied villagers to tree trunks and fixed bayonets on our rifles. We charged forward and stabbed them in the villagers' chests with a "thud." Whoever managed to hit the mark would receive a good performance and be praised. At the beginning, I couldn't sleep at night, but after killing one person after another, I gradually became accustomed to it.

At that time, the more Chinese people you killed, the better your military performance and the greater your promotion. This was the honor of the Imperial Army of the Great Japanese Empire. At that time, we were all excited and killed all the Chinese people we saw, regardless of what they were doing... After entering each village, we would loot, kill, and burn everything. We were especially cruel to women. Many times, we would drive them to the courtyard for collective rape. Pregnant women who couldn't be raped would be killed, and then we would open their bellies to play with the babies inside.

"I raped a total of 33 Chinese women, killed 8 women, and maimed 3 women. I can't forget how miserably they died, nor can I shake off memories. Once during a village sweep, I entered a peasant's house and saw a woman lying on the kang with a towel wrapped around her head. Beside her was a newborn baby. I lifted the blanket and went to pull the woman. The woman screamed loudly, trembling in fear. The old lady in her family came at me like a crazy person, so I turned around and shot her dead. After finishing everything, I set fire to the house. The women, the children, and the old lady of that family were all buried inside."

In the 16th year of Showa, in Shangduan village, I and another veteran soldier

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broke into a farmer's house, stole things, and then went to rape the woman in the house. But she fought back desperately. The veteran soldier dragged her to the edge of a well outside, grabbed her head, and pushed her into the well. But the woman held onto the well's edge tightly and resisted fiercely, shouting loudly. The veteran soldier called me over and asked me to hold the woman's feet and together we pushed her into the well. Then, he threw the young boy who was crying in the girl's arms into the well as well. The veteran soldier also threw two hand grenades into the well, blowing them to death.

The most brutal act was when our battalion captured a female soldier. We tied her to an electric pole in the military camp, first shooting her breasts from a distance with a pistol, then opening her belly to remove her uterus. After inflating it, we placed it on her head, watching the uterine membrane retract as it was exposed to the sun, getting tighter and tighter, finally wrapping her head tightly, and we watched her convulsing and trembling until she suffocated to death. Afterward, we even cooked and ate meat from her body.

In Sekijun Bai Sou's "Confessions of Repentance," these scenes, these gruesome and outrageous scenes of killing innocent Chinese civilians, make one's body feel cold, tremble, nauseous, and filled with anger! In reality, Sekijun Bai Sou was just a soldier among the Japanese invasion army, yet he alone committed such serious crimes. Then, the near 2 million Japanese invasion army committed countless grave crimes. Sekijun Bai Sou was a criminal who owed endless blood debt to countless Chinese people, but who was truly responsible for pushing him to this point? The answer to this question is undoubtedly clear, it is these die-hard militaristic individuals in the Japanese military and political high ranks.

Even for a war criminal capable of reflecting on his crimes, the number of Chinese women he raped and killed should be far less than other Japanese soldiers who lacked reflection. It is normal for a Japanese veteran in his eighties to miss a non-important incident, and there must be other cases of murder and rape that have not been mentioned. The War ended on August 15, 1945, and it is difficult to believe that a young war criminal who started killing people in China in 1937 would only rape 33, kill 8, and cripple 3 in 8 years. **The total number of troops deployed by the Japanese invaders in China was 3.2 to 3.6 million, exceeding 1.85 million when they surrendered in August 1945.** Based on the number of raped and killed Chinese women revealed by this war criminal, **the Japanese army raped at least 105.6 million Chinese women and killed 25.6 million Chinese women and children respectively.** This does not include the number of male civilians and soldiers who were killed. When the Japanese army killed women, the men who protected them would undoubtedly also be killed. The usual number of male civilians killed should be at least 25.6 million. The usual number of regular soldiers and guerrilla fighters killed should be at least 16.8 million. **The Japanese army has killed at least 76.8 million people in China.** Otherwise, according to the population growth rate at the time, during the 14-year war of resistance against Japan, China's population could not have decreased by **at least 138 million.**

[During the War of Japanese Invasion of China, 33 Chinese women were harmed, and

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their children and grandchildren were all killed in car accidents in their later years. March 31, 2022. https://www.sohu.com/a/534278882_120172967],

[Intense and sinister: How many troops did the invading Japanese army invest in China in total? October 3, 2022. <https://m.163.com/dy/article/HINL3PPF0553BEUT.html>]

[How many troops were dispatched during the 14 years of Japanese invasion of China? How many people were killed or injured, do you know all of this? February 25, 2021. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1692669478955719479>]

[Foreign Volunteers of the German Army during World War II: There were Indians and black people, and 150,000 Jews also followed Hitler. October 29, 2021. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/GNG6FTUD0552MA19.html>]

[Poland's three annihilations are not worthy of sympathy, as many acts of injustice will lead to self destruction! Grape Gourmet. August 30, 2021.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1709505453995700942&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 196. Children's underdeveloped genitalia were cut off by Japanese invaders, while the breasts of mothers were gouged out. What is even more infuriating is that after they

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cut off the mother's genitalia and ate it, they hypocritically dressed her in pants. 2023-07-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iLDVWwG5/> YzG:/ 02/26 q@R.kp

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 197. Some methods of the evil and inhumane slaughter of women and infants by the Japanese people

Table 8. Some methods of the evil and inhumane slaughter of women and infants by the Japanese people			
1	Raping before killing	13	gang rape leading to death
2	poking with a stick in the genital area	14	opening the abdomen to extract the fetus
3	stabbing infants with a knife	15	burning fetuses with oil
4	stepping on the stomach to induce abortion	16	forcing pregnant women to drink water
5	shooting pregnant women in the abdomen	17	poking the abdomen after rape

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6	Throwing infants off cliffs after being stabbed with a knife	18	poking the genital area
7	tearing babies apart	19	throwing babies
8	stabbing twins with a knife	20	cutting the belly to extract the fetus
9	inserting a baby upside down	21	throwing babies in the air and stabbing them
10	throwing babies into wells	22	boiling babies alive
11	burning babies alive	23	tabbing fetuses
12	feeding fetuses to dogs		

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

If you want to improve your high school-aged son or daughter's cognitive and computational abilities, expose them to the complexities of society, enhance their judgment of evil forces, and develop their risk prevention skills, why not have them try to figure out how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese against the women they forcibly recruited as sex slaves or so-called "comfort women" during World War II? Some estimates indicate that there were at least 100 different types. Can they find them all?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Some people may say that anger will blind people's eyes, but surprisingly, you are not angry at such anti-human torture. Are you still human? Why don't you and your family experience some Japanese torture for a month when you have such thoughts? Your family should experience it for at least six months or a year, and then you can exchange thoughts.

Japan, a greedy and evil country that slaughtered at least 50 million Chinese people, plundered an astonishing amount of resources from China. According to incomplete statistics, during the Anti-Japanese War, the evil Japanese plundered an astonishing amount of resources from China. At least 42,000 tons of gold, at least 10 million pieces of cultural relics, at least 500 tons of natural diamonds, at least 20 million gemstones, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls, at least 25,000 tons of silver, at least 250 million silver dollars, at least 1,000 tons of platinum, at least 1.22 billion tons of grain, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood, at least 200 million tons of rare earths, at least 150 million tons of kaolin, and at least 490,000 tons of bronze.

So far, Japan has not compensated China, but now it is manufacturing more and more warships similar to aircraft carriers. What is Japan preparing for in the future?

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What is the value of 500 tons of natural diamonds in US dollars? Anyone can calculate it. Japan was a seemingly defeated country in World War II, isn't it a truly victorious country?

Before 1958, the wealth owned by Chinese civilians, including gold, platinum, silver, jewelry, etc., far exceeded that controlled by the government.

Fig. 198. **The Rape of Nanking**----**Iris Chang**

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The awl pierced the eyes, mouth, and throat to death :

Evil Japanese soldiers tied Chinese people to school columns or doors, and then pierced hundreds of small holes in their mouths, throats, eyes, and other parts of their bodies with a awl or piercing tool.

Burning alive:

Japanese troops conducted mass burnings of Chinese victims. In Xiaguan, Nanjing, a Japanese soldier tied Chinese prisoners together, ten at a time, then pushed them into a pit and burned them alive with gasoline.

The game of tying and connecting ropes and then pushing them into the fire to dance and burn to death:

On Taiping Road, Japanese soldiers ordered a large group of shop employees to put out a fire, but instead tied them together with ropes and pushed them into the blaze.

Demolition of stairs, setting fire on the first floor, forcing people to jump around and commit suicide in a death game :

Japanese soldiers even invented a game of using fire to kill people for entertainment. One version involved driving a large group of Chinese people to the top of a building, removing the stairs, and setting fire to the first floor, watching many victims jump to their deaths from windows or rooftops.

Sprinkle fuel on the body, shoot and watch the flames rise :

Another version involved dousing the victims with fuel and then shooting at them, enjoying the sight of flames rising from their bodies. There was once an infamous incident where Japanese soldiers drove hundreds of Chinese people (including women and children) to a square, doused them in gasoline, and then machine-gunned them.

The game of shooting naked fishermen in glaciers :

During the Nanjing Massacre, thousands of people were intentionally frozen to death by Japanese troops. For example, Japanese soldiers forced hundreds of Chinese prisoners to go to the edge of a frozen pond, take off their clothes, and break the ice. They would then jump into the water to "fish." When their bodies froze and surfaced, they quickly became floating targets for Japanese soldiers, who shot at them leaving bullet holes all over.

Bundled and pushed into the water, hand grenade fish like slaughter :

In another incident, Japanese soldiers tied a group of refugees together and pushed them into a shallow pool, then threw hand grenades at them, creating a **"flesh-and-blood" explosion.**

Dog bites: Another inhuman torture method involved burying the victims alive up to their waists and then watching as they were torn apart by German Dobermans. **There were witnesses who saw Japanese soldiers strip a victim naked and command the**

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Dobermans to bite his sensitive areas (genitalia). These dogs not only tore open the victim's stomach but also dragged his intestines far along the ground.

The events described above are just a small fraction of the brutal methods used by the Japanese forces against the victims. **They also submerged victims in acidic liquid to corrode them and used bayonets to stab infants.**

Fig. 200. The invading Japanese army recalled the Nanjing Massacre: Only four out of over two hundred people expressed introspection.

2019-12-09.

https://www.360kuai.com/pc/9bdda58bff00278f4?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 204. Three terrifying forms of torture against sex slaves invented by the Japanese - **lotus seat, garlic petal bath, and four legged cow**

After the end of World War II, many women came forward to recall the atrocities they experienced in Japanese military camps. The three types of torture used by the Japanese left a lasting memory on these women. Women who endured these punishments were unlikely to walk out of the comfort stations alive, and those who witnessed the executions of their fellow countrywomen were also left with lifelong psychological trauma. How were these punishments implemented? Why did the Japanese treat them that way? Let's delve into the tragic lives of comfort women (**Sexual slavery**) together.

The first torture invented by the Japanese was the famous lotus seat. The implementation of this torture was very simple. Japanese soldiers would bring a large block of ice and force women (**Sexual slavery**) to undress completely. When these women least expected it, their genitals would be pressed tightly against the ice. Due to the significant temperature difference between their bodies and the ice, in just a few seconds, their genitals would be firmly stuck to the ice. Instead of forcibly lifting these women, the Japanese soldiers would make them continue to sit on the ice, and every movement would cause immense pain. When the woman's body became numb and no longer felt anything, the Japanese soldiers would suddenly pull her up. Although her legs were numb, her genitals were stuck to the ice, causing the flesh to be red and visibly stuck to the ice. These women would cover their genitals and roll on the ground in pain,

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but the Japanese soldiers would become extremely excited. Moreover, when the woman (**Sexual slavery**) had recovered for a while and her pain had increased, the Japanese soldiers would demand that she sit on the ice again, causing the same pain all over again.

I'm done talking. I won't say anymore, it's uncomfortable to talk about.

Most of the young girls at this time would cry and plead with the Japanese for mercy, hoping they would spare them. However, the Japanese would quickly subject them to another form of torture: slowly pouring boiling water down their bodies. By now, their genitals had been numbed by the ice, but their skin felt a burning pain. As the ice slowly melted, these women (**Sexual slavery**) would collapse to the ground, looking as if they were dead. The Japanese soldiers would then take their bodies to a nearby small room, and whether they could survive depended entirely on their own fate.

The second torture invented by the Japanese was the garlic clove bath. This form of torture may not result in immediate death, but would cause lifelong side effects for these women(**Sexual slavery**). The "clove" mentioned by the Japanese refers to leeches, countless leeches placed in a large bathtub. The women would have all their clothes removed and thrown directly into the bathtub. When these women were covered in leeches, they would be completely shattered mentally. No matter what the Japanese soldiers did to them, they simply wanted to escape from these creatures as soon as possible. They would desperately beg the Japanese soldiers for mercy, but the Japanese would stand by and count the minutes on a watch. After half an hour, they would take the woman out of the tub. She might have fainted already, and the leeches seemed to have completely disappeared from her body, but in reality, many complications remained. Leeches would crawl into the woman's body through her nose, ears, mouth, and genitals, causing tremendous damage to her internal organs. These parasites feed on fresh blood, and her internal organs would soon begin to experience unbearable pain. Through examination, it would be discovered that her abdomen had become infected, but the Japanese would disregard this. After a while, the woman would go into shock or die directly due to the internal infection.

The third torture invented by the Japanese was the four-legged cow. This form of torture left the deepest psychological trauma on these women (**Sexual slavery**) because they had to use their hands and feet to support themselves on the ground while a long knife was placed under their abdomen. During this process, if the woman lowered her head, she could see the knife threatening her life. They would exert all their strength to support themselves, and when these women were starting to give in, the Japanese soldiers would give them a glimmer of hope, but that hope was cruel. They would tell these women that if they pushed down their fellow companions, they would have a chance to survive. At the same time, however, they would also feel guilty for their compatriots, burdened with guilt for the rest of their lives. Most women couldn't bring themselves to do this and would rather die right there than have any further involvement with these Japanese soldiers. However, most people have the will to survive, and when the Japanese soldiers could no longer wait, they would sit on the women's bodies and force them to lie down slowly. When these women's bodies were pierced, the other sex slaves would scream, and before long, all of them would die. Of

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the 20 sex slaves subjected to this punishment, at most only two could survive, and these two would bear lifelong scars. They would never be able to forget the scene of their compatriots' death, and they would vividly remember the desolate feeling of the knife under their abdomen. These are the three major atrocities committed by the Japanese military in relation to comfort women(**Sexual slavery**).

[The three major punishments for comfort women are "lotus seats, garlic petal baths, and four legged oxen", which deeply shame the tortured women. # History # War # Japanese atrocities # Remembering history. <https://v.douyin.com/ipk9crd/>]

The dollars obtained through massacre and robberies are called dirty money or illegal currency, and the goods obtained through massacre and robbery are called stolen goods or illegal goods.

Aren't the Japanese who fed themselves with over **42 million tons of gold**, over 1.06 billion tons of coal, over 1233 million tons of food, over 20 million tons of cotton and over 500,000 kg of **natural diamonds** plundered by killing over 50 million people dirty or illegal individuals? How much is 500,000 kg of **natural diamonds** worth?

Before 1958, the wealth owned by Chinese civilians, including gold, platinum, silver, jewelry, etc., far exceeded that controlled by the government.

Isn't the industry built on the immense funds plundered by killing 50 million Chinese people in Japan dirty or illegal industry?

Does passing seventy or eighty years mean that these illegal individuals and industries in Japan have been whitewashed?

Doesn't this suggest that the world needs righteous Americans to take charge and help achieve global justice, while also swiftly resolving the United States' national debt issue?

Doesn't this suggest that the world needs righteous Americans to take charge and help achieve global justice, while also swiftly resolving the United States' national debt issue?

According to Japanese logic, the Japanese grandfather killed over 50 million Chinese and looted 42,000 tons of gold, transferring substantial wealth to his grandson. After being convicted, the Japanese grandfather passed away, and it has been 100 years since then. The Japanese grandson does not have to return the stolen assets and funds to their original rightful owner, the Chinese people. The looted assets can still be freely used and enjoyed, and this has become an international precedent. Why can't anyone's American grandfather kill any Japanese person and transfer all the assets looted by Japan to his grandson? After all, the source of Japan's wealth is illegal. The American grandfather killing the evil Japanese and reclaiming the assets would be a righteous and lawful act. Would it still require the death of that person's American grandfather to make it legal?

If that's the case, legislation or silent consent should allow anyone and any country to demonstrate the power of justice against evil forces at any time.

If such just actions are not allowed, are world leaders, such as the United States, and the international community not encouraging mass killings and crimes?

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Does international society need such ugly rules and laws?

Why can't white knights, who embody justice, eliminate the lawyers and judges who establish these evil rules?

Fig. 205. How cruel was the Japanese 731 unit? Crazy maternal love experiment, hollowing out internal organs, challenging human moral bottom line # Let Chinese descendants remember history. 2023-02-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iLBcSr17/j@C.UY 05/28 qRX:/>

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 206. The Torture suffered by the family of anti-Japanese heroes Lu Guanglian and Xu Delan

On January 16, 1940, due to the betrayal of a traitor, the Japanese invaders found Lu Guanglian's whereabouts and quickly surrounded his residence. However, Lu Guanglian was not at home at that time as he was busy transferring his comrades. Desperate for revenge, the Japanese captured his wife, Xu Delan, and their child. They subjected her to brutal torture, taking turns torturing her relentlessly. Xu Delan was tormented to the point of despair, her body covered in blood and flesh, fainting again and again. Seeing that they could not extract any information from her in this state, the Japanese soldiers threw her into a dungeon. After more than twenty days of severe torture, the Japanese invaders decided to execute her in the near future. At that moment, the sky was full. Xu Delan was brought to the execution ground by Japanese soldiers, and her clothes were stripped. The Japanese held Xu Delan's two-year-old son by his feet and brought him over, causing the child to cry loudly. The Japanese officer aimed his bayonet at the child's abdomen and struck once, twice, blood splattering. A few piercing sounds from the ruptured belly were heard and then stopped,

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and the child ceased crying. Immediately after, the Japanese soldiers discarded the child as if throwing away garbage. Then, the Japanese aimed their bloodstained bayonet at Xu Delan's abdomen. By this time, Xu Delan was five months pregnant, and her unborn child appeared to be moving beneath her skin. Japanese soldiers thrust the bayonet into Xu Delan's stomach, mutilating her and killing both her and the unborn child.

Xu Delan's blood mixed with the child's blood, and in her final moments of life, she turned her head to look at the child lying in a pool of blood: "Child, do not blame Mama! If there is a next life, I still want to be your mother, to accompany you as you grow..." With love and guilt for her child, Xu Delan closed her eyes forever. She was only 23 years old that year, in the prime of her life. Upon hearing the news of his wife and child's death, Lu Guanglian was overwhelmed with grief and vowed to seek revenge for the fallen Chinese children. He vowed to drive the invaders out of China's land. Turning his sorrow and anger into strength, he actively participated in various anti-Japanese activities. In 1943, Lu Guanglian encountered the Japanese and collaborating forces and engaged in a fierce battle. Outnumbered, Lu Guanglian sustained multiple hits and fell heavily into a pool of blood. The cruel Japanese soldiers beheaded the still breathing Lu Guanglian and displayed his head on a tree in Zaozhuang as a warning.

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/IAQGI7HG05378IX6.html>

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Fig. 207. One of the tortures of the Japanese aggressors in Nanjing Massacre

[We will never forget the harm suffered by 300000 compatriots, and seeing these truly recorded photos will make us feel heartbroken and resentful. We can never forgive our ancestors for their crimes # Nanjing Massacre. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ8bbba1/>]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

The Japanese invaders actually slaughtered at least 500,000 to 650,000 people in Nanjing.

Fig. 208. Nanjing Massacre

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Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

The Japanese invaders actually slaughtered at least 500,000 to 650,000 people in Nanjing.

Fig. 210. The Japanese people in Japan were celebrating crazily that the Japanese army has occupied Nanjing, China.

Aren't Japanese people evil?

[On the evening of December 30th, 1937, at 23:00, the Japanese military announced that after the capture of Nanjing, the Japanese domestic people were celebrating crazily # not forgetting national shame # our self-improvement # remembering history. <https://v.douyin.com/iJhaLxBv/>]

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Fig. 214. A group of Japanese comfort women with smiles on their faces and joy in their hearts, who are always providing sexual stimulation and pleasure services to the Japanese army.

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Fig. 215. A group of Japanese comfort women with smiles on their faces and joy in their hearts, who are always providing sexual stimulation and pleasure services to the Japanese army. [Japanese defeat # Never forget history # Historical facts .<https://v.douyin.com/iJhANoSL/>]

Japanese comfort women groups use their bodies to support the Japanese army in killing Chinese people and plundering Chinese wealth. This is their great cause. Does this not reflect that this country has culture but no civilization? Doesn't the definition of civilization need to be changed?

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Fig. 216. The comfort women's group in Japan

Japanese comfort women groups use their bodies to support the Japanese army in killing Chinese people and plundering Chinese wealth. This is their great cause.

Does this not reflect that this country has culture but no civilization?

Doesn't the definition of civilization need to be changed?

[Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women
September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Fig. 217. The comfort women's group in Japan has a good Chinese name: Women's Progressive Team, as shown in the above picture.

Women in Japan voluntarily participate in and form comfort women organizations. At the beginning of the war, some young girls rushed to the battlefield for the sake of "nation" and "ideals", contributing to Japan's occupation of China and the unification of the world, motivating the Japanese army and providing them with sexual pleasure and stimulation.

For example, in the novel "Comfort Women in the Military - Keiko" by Natsugu Chida, it is written that Keiko Sakata lives in Nagasaki. One day at the end of 1937, she unexpectedly discovers that her lover, with whom she was deeply in love, had fallen for someone else. Filled with sadness and anger, Keiko goes to the comfort women recruitment center and joins the ranks of comfort women. When the officer handed her 1,000 yen, Keiko said contemptuously, "I don't want a single yen."

Because Keiko Sakada was a virgin, she was initially chosen to serve as a general in her fifties. Later, she was sent to the "Yeomanry Entertainment Center" just like others, becoming a comfort woman for the military for seven years. On her busiest day, she attended 67 soldiers.

[Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Fig. 220. The Japanese text on the picture is: Long live the Imperial Army. Sixth Comfort Station
[Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Fig. 221. Japanese soldiers waiting in line to satisfy their animal desires
[Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women
September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

Fig. 222. Women in Japan voluntarily participate in and form comfort women organizations. At the beginning of the war, some young girls rushed to the battlefield for the sake of "nation" and "ideals", contributing to Japan's occupation of China and the unification of the world, motivating the Japanese army and providing them with sexual pleasure and stimulation. [Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Fig. 224. Japanese comfort women.

Comfort women in Japanese comfort centers are performing political propaganda performances

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September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Japanese women like to voluntarily become sex slaves for the invading Japanese army, satisfying their sexual needs during the war, providing comfort to the Japanese army, and inspiring them to invade China. Can you tell the difference between these women and prostitutes in normal times? Aren't Japanese women criminals and war criminals? Isn't Japan a nation of universal crime? A country and a nation without conscience will inevitably be fond of aggression, slaughter, rape, and plunder when the opportunity arises. Basically, all the citizens of the country are like this, and perhaps only a very small number of people have some empathy.

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Fig. 225. Girls in Korean schools who were influenced by the enslaved education of the Japanese aggressors voluntarily formed a "push up team"

[Explanation: Why Japanese women voluntarily request to become comfort women September 20, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DS5F93E80517B1G1.html>]

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Fig. 234. Nanjing Massacre. In September 1937, the Japanese army carried out a large-scale bombing of Nanjing, resulting in the death of civilians and the littering of corpses. The Japanese army believed that such photos would also have adverse effects, so they also carried out an unauthorized stamp. (Photos taken by Japanese military photographers during the war)

[Evidence of the Japanese invasion of China, with 18 photos prohibiting people from seeing heinous crimes and revealing their animal behavior. March 20th, 2021; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1694751262187158705&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 235. Nanjing Massacre
The Japanese army carried out a large-scale bombing of Nanjing, and the private Guangdong hospital in Nanjing was destroyed during the bombing. There were also a large number of civilian buildings and civilian deaths, and their photos were not allowed to be stamped to conceal their true behavior. The Japanese army believed that such photos would also have adverse effects, so they also carried out an unauthorized stamp. (Photos taken by Japanese military photographers

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during the war)

Fig. 236. Two photos depict the entire process of the brutal killing of a people's soldier by the invading Japanese army. The Japanese army believed that such photos would also have adverse effects, so they also carried out an unauthorized stamp. (Photos taken by Japanese military photographers during the war)

[Evidence of the Japanese invasion of China, with 18 photos prohibiting people from seeing heinous crimes and revealing their animal behavior. March 20th, 2021; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1694751262187158705&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

These are photos that were banned from publication by the Japanese army, and the red stamp on the photos that prohibits publication was stamped by the Japanese army.

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

The dollars obtained through murder and robbery are called dirty money or illegal currency, and the goods obtained through murder and robbery are called stolen goods or illegal goods. Aren't the Japanese who fed themselves with over 42 million tons of gold and over 1223 million tons of food plundered by killing over 50 million people dirty or illegal individuals? Isn't the industry built on the immense funds plundered by killing 50 million people in Japan dirty or illegal industry? Does passing seventy or eighty years mean that these illegal individuals and industries in Japan have been whitewashed?

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Fig. 239. An unknown hero who died in battle with the Japanese army. The Japanese army believed that such photos would also have adverse effects, so they also carried out an unauthorized stamp. (Photos taken by Japanese military photographers during the war)

This is a photo that was banned from publication by the Japanese army, and the red stamp on the photo that prohibits publication was stamped by the Japanese army.

[Evidence of the Japanese invasion of China, with 18 photos prohibiting people from seeing heinous crimes and revealing their animal behavior. March 20th, 2021; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1694751262187158705&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 243. This photo was taken during the Japanese invasion of China in World War II. During the Battle of Shanghai, the Japanese bombed Shanghai. The camera shows the Chinese people who were killed in the Japanese bombing. The scene is horrible, and it is very sad to see.(Photos taken by Japanese military

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photographers during the war)

This is a photo that was banned from publication by the Japanese army, and the red stamp on the photo that prohibits publication was stamped by the Japanese army.

[Old photos that were not allowed to be released during the Japanese war: Figure 4 shows the massacre of prisoners of war, and Figure 7 is heartbreaking. 2019-07-13; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1638910814797329793&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 252. The poor parents were crying out in agony for their children who had died under the Japanese butcher's knife. [The War of Aggression Against China in Japanese Camera - Massacre and Atrocities in Various Regions (Barbarian Massacre). May 17, 2023;

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1765811409492962268&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

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Fig. 253. Innocent villagers buried alive during the Japanese "sweep".[The War of Aggression Against China in Japanese Camera - Massacre and Atrocities in Various Regions (Barbarian Massacre). May 17, 2023; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1765811409492962268&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 254. The evil invading Japanese army placed these children they had killed on dry firewood and prepared to burn them.

[The War of Aggression Against China in Japanese Camera - Massacre and Atrocities in Various Regions (Barbarian Massacre). May 17, 2023; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1765811409492962268&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

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Fig. 256. The ferocious anti-human Japanese invader smiled and took a group photo with a baby, then fried the baby in oil.
[<https://v.douyin.com/iJ6Xmvd1/>]

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Fig. 257. The ferocious anti-human Japanese invader smiled and took a group photo with a baby, then fried the baby in oil. [<https://v.douyin.com/iJ6Xmvd1/>]

If you are a non-violent person, would you be willing to try, just to see if you or your family can bear one or two of the hundreds of cruel tortures used by the evil and inhumane Japanese against the Chinese people? Would you reconsider your perception of Japan after that? Can you test your true abilities? Can you test how many days or a week you can tolerate?

How many officials and military officers do you know have been bribed by the evil

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Japanese with looted Chinese gold and jewelry?

Who knows how many babies the evil and despicable anti-human Japanese killed in China, and how many baby carriages they have stolen?

Where does Japan's current wealth come from? Is it not obtained through killing, looting, and stealing from China?

Who has the extraordinary ability to help China claim compensation from the seemingly polite but extremely evil, despicable, barbaric, and anti-human Japan?

Success will bring you and your country great rewards.

In an extraordinary era, the world eagerly awaits your exceptional arrival. You will be immortalized in history, becoming the first in the history of your country and world history.

This may be the greatest political correctness of this century.

This may be the biggest politically correct movement that has never been seen in human history before.

This may be the greatest activity of this century to maintain world peace and sustainable development of human society.

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 258. Picture of Japanese military doctors frying Chinese babies

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJ6Xmvd1/>]

If you are a non-violent person, would you be willing to try, just to see if you or your family can bear one or two of the hundreds of cruel tortures used by the evil and inhumane Japanese against the Chinese people? Would you reconsider your perception of Japan after that? **Can you test your true abilities?** Can you test how many days or a week you can tolerate?

How many officials and military officers do you know have been bribed by the evil Japanese with looted Chinese gold and jewelry?

Who knows how many babies the evil and despicable anti-human Japanese killed in China, and how many baby carriages they have stolen?

Where does Japan's current wealth come from? Is it not obtained through killing, looting, and stealing from China?

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Fig. 259. When the Japanese invaded and occupied Song Palace, they used this pot to boil anti-Japanese soldiers and local civilians.[History cannot be tampered with. What qualifications do we have to forgive the Japanese aggressors? # Remember history # Do not forget national shame # Our generation should strive for self-improvement # Zhang Chunru's unforgettable history. 2022-09-25. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6XCDag/>]

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Fig. 260. Mrs. Zhang Li, the wife of General Yu Guangwen of the 18th Route Army of the Chinese National Army, firmly refused to reveal the whereabouts of the anti-Japanese forces. The brutal Japanese invaders used bayonets to throw her newborn baby boy, who was only two months old, into a boiling pot of water.

When the Japanese invaders saw my mother holding a child in her arms, they asked where the anti-Japanese forces were. My mother refused to say anything. These beasts stabbed my little brother with bayonets, and threw him into a boiling pot of water. I heard my brother scream, and then there was silence. After that, they cut off my mother's left arm and stabbed her in the abdomen with a bayonet. [2021-08-23. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6bNCCc/>]

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Fig. 264. Two little boys had their bodies cut in half at the waist by Japanese invaders

[Both humans and gods are indignant! This deep-rooted hatred cannot be forgotten forever! #Remember history, never forget national shame.

<https://v.douyin.com/iJ6V51C7/>],[2022-12-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iLSbay21/> 09/19 wfo:/ [Z@z.TI](#) **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.")

Fig. 265. The Puyou Temple in Xizhuang, Fuping County, burned down by the evil Japanese army [Both humans and gods are indignant! This deep-rooted hatred cannot

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be forgotten forever! #Remember history, never forget national shame. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6V51C7/>], (If the video reference that publicizes the ugly situation of criminals is deleted maliciously, you can usually find the video that the author re uploads later or another person publishes the same content video in Tiktok.)

Fig. 266. The Puyou Temple in Xizhuang, Fuping County, burned down by the evil Japanese army [Both humans and gods are indignant! This deep-rooted hatred cannot be forgotten forever! #Remember history, never forget national shame. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6V51C7/>]

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Fig. 267. The Puyou Temple in Xizhuang, Fuping County, burned down by the evil Japanese army [Both humans and gods are indignant! This deep-rooted hatred cannot be forgotten forever! #Remember history, never forget national shame. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6V51C7/>]

Fig. 268. Women forced into sexual slavery by the Japanese army [Both humans and gods are indignant! This deep-rooted hatred cannot be forgotten forever! #Remember history, never forget national shame. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6V51C7/>]

(Some people want to control public opinion, cover up crimes against humanity and block the video, but there are many similar videos in Tiktok or Douyin.)

Fig. 269. On September 23, 1941, the Japanese army "swept" Langya Mountain in Hebei, massacred 600 or 700 people from the villages of Nanqi and Beiqi at the foot of the mountain. This is the tragic scene of a woman who was raped by the Japanese army and then stabbed to death by the Japanese bayonet.

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[The War of Aggression Against China in Japanese Camera - Massacre and Atrocities in Various Regions (Barbarian Massacre). May 17, 2023; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1765811409492962268&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 270. In 1937, inside the city of Nanjing, evil Japanese individuals commanded three young girls to play erhu for them, then they set up an oil pan, cooked them, and gleefully consumed their bodies. 2023-09-05. <https://v.douyin.com/idrNvQg5/>

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 271. [These Japanese soldiers were stunned by the unmoving old nun who set herself on fire on a pile of dry firewood in front of the Baihui Palace in Nanjing. They knelt down one by one to show their respect.

However, this tribute lasted only a few seconds, and soon they revealed their true nature. They bypassed the charred fire pit and broke into Baihui Palace, committing unforgivable crimes.

In December 1937, the gates of Nanjing were opened by the gunfire of the Japanese army. Nanjing, this ancient capital of the Six Dynasties, witnessed the hardships endured by the Chinese people this year. It witnessed how much blood flowed like rivers and how many heinous acts that cannot be tolerated occurred here.

Japanese invaders usually killed young nuns, but they committed atrocities against nuns who were about eleven or twelve years old and cruelly murdered them. Once they invaded the nunnery, it would inevitably be a scene of bloodshed, with no one able to escape.

Japanese invaders even found pleasure in forcing monks and nuns to have sexual relations in front of the Buddha, and there have long been rumors of their bestial acts at Baishousi. So, Master Longhua ordered her disciples to place a pile of firewood in front of Baishousi. She sat in meditation on the firewood, waiting for the arrival of the Japanese soldiers. Master Longhua then ignited the pyre, hoping that her death would awaken the conscience of the Japanese invaders.

Finally, three days later, the footsteps of the Japanese army drew near, and Master Longhua lit the pyre, remaining calm and serene. True to form, the Japanese showed respect for courage of the teacher and knelt down, firing their guns to express their admiration, just as described in the opening scene. The nuns inside Baishousi thought they had escaped the disaster.

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Little did they know that the next moment, the Japanese soldiers stood up one after another, laughing heartily, and rushed into Baishousi. The doors of Baishousi were closed, but they could not shut out the cries of despair and the frenzied shouts of the Japanese.

At the cost of her own life, Master Longhua proved the indomitable spirit of the Chinese nation to the executioners of the Nanjing Massacre. Her heroic act is admired by the world! #NeverForgetNationalHumiliation #RememberHistory # 2022-07-27.
<https://v.douyin.com/iJB8MDBF/>

Fig. 272. In the 1942 Lujiayu Massacre, Suzuki Qijiu ordered the Japanese army to drive 10 members of Li Changzhi's family to the Huoshi Cave in Yingbi Mountain, Beiyu Village, Zunhua County, and suffocate 7 people with toxic gas. The picture shows a cave emitting toxic gas. [The War of Aggression Against China in Japanese Camera - Massacre and Atrocities in Various Regions (Barbarian Massacre). May 17, 2023; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1765811409492962268&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

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Fig. 280. The profound culture of robbery and plunder among primary school teachers in Japan

In a notebook titled "Life Study Journal" written by Shunsaku Ueda, a third-grade student from Yamanashi Prefecture, Japan in the 16th year of the Shōwa era (1941), there are extensive records of admiration for the Japanese military and advocating for aggression. The notes are written in the form of compositions and accompanied by hand-drawn illustrations, most of which are related to war and ceremonies at shrines to honor the war dead. One entry said, "If Singapore is occupied, we can get anything. It would also be great to conquer Hawaii and go to Washington, but it hasn't been achieved yet." [CCTV revealed Japanese militarism brainwashing education, and the truth was revealed in the composition of third grade pupils.

Published on: March 21, 2017; Source: CCTV News; http://news.youth.cn/jsxw/201703/t20170321_9331058.htm]

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如果占领了新加坡 什么东西都可以得到

Fig. 281. The profound culture of robbery and plunder among primary school teachers in Japan

Elementary school teachers in Japan instill students with an enthusiastic mindset of pillaging. In their essays, students write about gaining everything if they were to occupy Singapore. At the end of the essays, the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese teachers annotate with a red pen, saying, "Indeed, that is true." [CCTV revealed Japanese militarism brainwashing education, and the truth was revealed in the composition of third grade pupils.

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老师的评语说 的确也是如此啊

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Fig. 282. The profound culture of robbery and plunder among primary school teachers in Japan

Elementary school teachers in Japan instill students with an enthusiastic mindset of pillaging. In their essays, students write about gaining everything if they were to occupy Singapore. At the end of the essays, the Japanese teachers annotate with a red pen, saying, "Indeed, that is true."

Li Suzhen, executive Deputy Chairman of the Japan-China Oral History and Cultural Studies Association, said that during the crazy Showa era in Japan, such essays were generally required for elementary school students, and sometimes even assigned as essay topics, with teachers checking and reviewing them. It was through this essay examination system that militaristic educational ideology was forcefully instilled in children, paving the way for them to be sent to the battlefield for aggression and crimes without any hindrance.

The children greatly admired the aggressive and robber-like behavior of the military, and instead of correcting them, the teachers further fueled and encouraged them. It is not difficult to see that during this period, all Japanese society, schools, and families were engaged in pre-war brainwashing education directed towards young Japanese children. However, during the crazy Showa era, an era supported by the Imperial Education Decree, brainwashing could escape, including the teachers themselves.

[CCTV revealed Japanese militarism brainwashing education, and the truth was revealed in the composition of third grade pupils.

Published on: March 21, 2017; Source: CCTV News;
http://news.youth.cn/jsxw/201703/t20170321_9331058_1.htm]

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

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Fig. 287. One of the tortures of the evil Japanese: A venomous snake's head is inserted into a woman's anus.

The Japanese army cruelly raped women and then inserted the heads of venomous snakes into their anuses. They then cut off the snake tails, causing the venomous snakes to writhe in excruciating pain and crawl desperately into the women's bellies. As a result, these women writhed on the ground and died.

[Only by uncovering the bloody history can we know how much we hate ourselves# 2022-12-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iCccGpM/>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

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鬼子往洗澡桶里
倒入大量蚂蟥
强迫妇女光着身子蹲坐里面
蚂蟥不仅爬到她们皮肤上吸血
还从她们下体进入身体内部
啃食其内脏……
这，就是慰安妇酷刑之：蚂蟥澡

Fig. 290. **One of the tortures of the evil Japanese: Leech Bath**

Japanese devils poured large numbers of leeches into bathing tubs, forcing women to squat naked inside. These leeches not only crawled on their skin to suck blood, but also entered their bodies through their genitals, vagina, urethra, or anus, devouring their internal organs... causing them to die in extreme agony. This is one of the torture methods invented by the Japanese army to comfort women or **sex slaves**: leech bath. [Only by uncovering the bloody history can we know how much we hate ourselves# 2022-12-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iCccGpM/>]

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Fig. 291. Sex slave at the gunpoint of Japan

Survivor diary reveals atrocities committed by Evil Staphylococcus aureus---evil Japanese army (Evil locust): Chest burned with cigarette butts

During World War II, the Dutch also suffered from atrocities committed by the Japanese (Evil locust) in Asia. During the Japanese occupation of Indonesia, more than 42,000 Dutch Army personnel were captured and 100,000 Dutch civilians were detained in concentration camps, resulting in a large number of deaths. The family of Ronny Holman de Yoong, who are Dutch-American descent, were among those imprisoned in Japanese concentration camps. A secret diary kept by Ronny's mother has become a direct witness to this dark memory.

On Ronny's 76th birthday, she watched the movie Unbreakable. The scenes of the brutal treatment of prisoners by the Japanese Army in the film brought back a flood of memories. Ronny recalled, "I was just a little girl at that time. They (the Japanese) were continuously beating people, including women, until they fell dead. Ronny also expressed hope that the movie could be screened in Japan, as young people there are unaware of these events because they are not recorded in their textbooks.

Ronny was born in 1938 in Surabaya, then the capital of the Dutch East Indies, which is now the capital of Indonesia's East Java Province. Her father was a pilot in the Dutch Army. During the Japanese invasion of the islands, Ronny's father was evacuated with the military, leaving behind his wife and two young daughters. After the Japanese occupation, three-year-old Ronny, her mother, and sister were imprisoned by the evil Japanese Army.

Ronny recounted the conditions in the concentration camp, where food and medicine became increasingly scarce, and psychological torment intensified. The Japanese army would unexpectedly gather everyone in an open space and then watch

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as they "punished" one or two women.

During the more than three years of difficult camp life, Ronny and her mother went through many cruel experiences. Ronny's mother kept a secret diary, recording their own experiences and witnessing firsthand the Japanese Army's abuse and killing of women and children. Ronny's mother hid the black diary at the bottom of a box, evading Japanese searches. Ronny said: "The diary tells the story of our experiences during those difficult days. My mother carefully cut out the bad words the Japanese said, and pasted other things on top, like the oatmeal we had for breakfast, and I said, 'Great! Great! I hope Dad is here too!' In 1945, she tore out those pages because the situation was too dire."

Ronny said the pages her mother tore out contained accounts of the brutal acts committed by the Japanese Army that she personally witnessed. In the later years of their camp life, her mother was deeply tormented by the memories of these brutal scenes, while also afraid of the Japanese Army would find evidence of their records, so she destroyed these pages. However, for many years after the war, her mother could barely speak when recounting those memories.

After the war, Ronnie returned to the Netherlands with her mother and reunited with her family before immigrating to the United States. She wrote two books based on her mother's diary and her own experiences. In her most recent publication, she documented the experiences of many survivors of the Pacific war during World War II. She hopes that more people, especially the Japanese, can see these facts and that the Japanese government can acknowledge the war crimes and apologize to the survivors. Ronnie said, "**The Japanese soldiers inserted bamboo sticks into their fingers, burned their chests with cigarettes, and killed them with bayonets,** yet they received no apology. The Japanese only say that none of this happened, that they did nothing wrong. They just occupied other countries, they didn't do anything wrong. Ronnie expressed that the Japanese government should apologize, apologize to survivors, and remember these events for the betterment of Japan and the entire world.[The diary of Japanese concentration camp survivors reveals atrocities: burning their chests with cigarette butts. CCTV News. May 1st, 2015; <http://m.news.cntv.cn/2015/05/01/ARTI1430472459587780.shtml>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

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日本士兵将这位年轻女子绑在椅子上，以供其反复施暴。(新华社供)

为，并以此为乐。一位女扮男装的中国妇女在试图通过南京城门时，遭到日本卫兵有计划的摸裆检查，她当场被识破真实性别并惨遭轮奸。当时恰好有一位和尚不幸从附近路过，日本士兵便强迫他与这位刚刚被轮奸的妇女发生性关系。和尚断然拒绝，于是惨遭阉割，最后失血而死。⁵²

日军所实施的性虐待中，最丧尽天良的案例莫过于对整个家庭的羞辱。为获取性虐狂般的快感，日军强迫中国男人犯下各种乱伦罪行：父亲强暴亲生女儿，兄弟强暴亲生姐妹，儿子强暴亲生母亲。南京陷落后，一位被困南京长达3个月之久的中国陆军营长郭歧曾经耳闻目睹四五起日军强迫儿子奸淫母亲的案例，拒不从命者被当场杀死。⁵³ 他的报告后来被一位德国外交官的证言所证实，该外交官报告说，曾有一位拒绝强奸自己母亲的中国男子被日本士兵砍死，随后他的母亲也自杀身亡。⁵⁴

Fig. 292. The Rape of Nanking---Iris Chang

In Chapter Four of Iris Chang's "Nanjing Massacre," titled "Six Weeks of Terror," there is a passage that reads:

"In order to experience sadistic pleasure, the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese (Evil locust) forces forced Chinese men to commit various acts of incest: fathers raping their own daughters, brothers raping their own sisters, sons raping their own mothers."

Similarly, in "The Blood and Tears of the Fallen City," written by a Chinese soldier named Guo Qi, he also documented four or five instances of Japanese soldiers forcing sons to commit acts of sexual assault on their own mothers when they were trapped in Nanjing.

Sadly, when these victims refused, the evil Japanese forces would immediately shoot them. Some of the victims chose to commit suicide rather than comply.

During this time, when a family in Nanjing was preparing to flee across the river, they unfortunately encountered two Japanese soldiers who first violated the

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young women and girls, and then forced the middle-aged men of the family to rape them. Unable to bear the incestuous acts, the entire family chose to throw themselves into the river.

[Remember history and never forget national shame. This hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten <https://v.douyin.com/iC3Kjhp/>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Fig. 293. The Rape of Nanking---Iris Chang

Many girls were tied to chairs, beds, and pillars, and were constantly subjected to brutal rape by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese invaders(Evil locust).

They did not survive the cruel abuse. An 11-year-old girl was raped continuously for two days and died. There were bloodstains between her legs, with swollen and torn wounds. In mass gang rapes, many children and infants cried when their mothers were raped, and were suffocated to death by vicious Japanese soldiers stuffing clothes in their mouths, or stabbed to death with bayonets. [Remember history and never forget national shame. This hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten <https://v.douyin.com/iC3Kjhp/>]

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Fig. 294. The picture shows a woman who was raped and killed during the May Day sweeping by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese invaders(Evil locust). Her intestines were all picked out by the brutal Japanese invaders. [Remember history and never forget national shame. This hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten <https://v.douyin.com/iC3Kjhp/>]

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

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一群日寇闯进一农户家
找不到年轻姑娘
就把这户人家14岁的小男孩
拖进屋里轮流鸡奸
发泄兽欲。
——魏特琳日记·1938.2.7

Fig. 295. A group of Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese invaders (Evil locust) broke into a rural household, unable to find the young girl, so they dragged the 14-year-old boy into a room, taking turns to commit a brutal act of rape, releasing their animalistic desires. :Minnie Vautrin's Diary, February 1938. [Remember history and never forget national shame. This hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten. <https://v.douyin.com/i4N5hW2/>]

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

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Fig. 298. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great German named John Rabe, Schindler of Nanjing

Chairman of the International Committee for Safe Zones and Representative of Siemens AG in Germany.

John Rabe arrived in Beijing at the age of 26. In 1911, he was hired by Siemens' Beijing branch and served as Siemens' representative in Beijing, Tianjin, and Nanjing.

At the end of 1937, during the Nanjing Massacre by the Japanese (**Evil locust**) army, John Rabe established a safety zone in Nanjing and provided shelter for more than 200,000 people in this zone, even housing more than 600 protected Chinese civilians in his own residence and small garden.

In this shocking and terrifying disaster in human history, he saved the lives of 250,000 Chinese compatriots.

In 1938, Rabe returned to Germany and carefully organized his diary and related materials.

The "**Rabe Diary**" he wrote is recognized as the most extensive and well-preserved historical document on the Nanjing Massacre discovered in recent years and has become powerful evidence of atrocities committed by the Japanese army.

Before his death, Rabe left behind a written legacy of his work in China – more than 2,000 pages of documentary material related to the Nanjing Massacre. Rabe

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meticulously printed, organized, and bound these materials, even including illustrations and other explanations.

These documents include eyewitness reports from Rabe and other foreigners, newspaper articles, radio broadcasts, photos of telegrams, and various acts of violence.

In 1996, Mrs. Reinhardt, John Rabe's granddaughter, dedicated the diary he wrote in China to the world, bringing to light the truth about the "Nanjing Massacre" that had been sealed for decades. In his diary, Rabe meticulously documented atrocities committed by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese(Evil locust) army, which debunked the official claims of peaceful governance and no massacres by the Japanese army in Nanjing. [Rabe: He sacrificed his life to save 250,000 Chinese people. 83 years later, his grandson sought help due to the epidemic. What did China do? January 27, 2022;

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/GUN7002O0552BGPP.html>],[<https://v.douyin.com/iJ DexGu7/>]

Fig. 299. Sending anti-pandemic materials to descendants of John Rabe in Germany

83 Years after the Nanjing Massacre, when the COVID-19 pandemic began to ravage the world, a doctor at Heidelberg University Hospital in Germany wrote a letter of appeal to China.

In his letter, he wrote that the situation in Germany was dire, and in order to treat his own family and patients, he urgently needed a batch of antiviral drugs, which were produced in China. He hoped China would help him.

The doctor seeking help from China was none other than Thomas Rabe, John Rabe's grandson.

After receiving his letter, the Chinese Embassy in Germany attached great importance to it and immediately contacted China's Ministry of Industry and Information Technology.

Upon learning of this news, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology

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readily agreed to Thomas Rabe's request and contacted a pharmaceutical company. When the company's leader heard that the person seeking help was Thomas Rabe, he quickly said, "We are willing to provide the drugs for free."

In no time, the medication was flown to Germany on a Chinese charter flight, accompanied by tens of thousands of masks and hundreds of sets of protective clothing, which were donated by the Nanjing government.

Upon hearing Thomas Rabe's request for help, the Nanjing government immediately mobilized resources. John Rabe helped hundreds of thousands of people in Nanjing, and now his descendants are facing difficulties. Of course, we must help them as best we can."

On April 20, 2020, all customs procedures were completed, and the supplies were shipped to the Chinese Embassy in Germany. To deliver supplies to Thomas Rabe as quickly as possible, embassy staff decided not to use regular logistics channels, as it would take about three to four days. Instead, they chose to use embassy vehicles to transport supplies and deliver them promptly.

At 6 a.m. on the 21st, embassy staff loaded the supplies into the car and set off for Heidelberg, 700 kilometers from Berlin. In the afternoon of the same day, at 2 p.m., they successfully handed over supplies to the Heidelberg government and Thomas Rabe.[Rabe: He sacrificed his life to save 250,000 Chinese people. 83 years later, his grandson sought help due to the epidemic. What did China do?January 27, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/GUN7002O0552BGPP.html>]

Fig. 300. John Rabe's Former Residence

In 1937, this was a shelter for over 650 refugees.

[During the season of eating broad beans, did you know that 80 years ago it saved many refugees in Nanjing? April 13, 2018; https://www.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_2073957]

The businessman, John Rabe, kept a 1,200-page diary that provides a rare third-party account of the atrocities. In it, he writes of digging foxholes in his backyard to shelter

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650 Chinese and of repelling Japanese troops who tried to climb over the wall, of dashing through war-torn areas to deliver rice, and of stopping Japanese soldiers from raping Chinese women. He even wrote to Hitler to complain about the Japanese actions. "These escapades were quite dangerous," he wrote in his diary. "The Japanese had pistols and bayonets and I -- as mentioned before -- had only party symbols and my swastika armband."

Mr. Rabe (pronounced RAH-bay), who died in 1950, lived and worked in China from 1908 to 1938. His diary sheds light on a heretofore little-known man, who, although a Nazi loyalist, risked his life and his status to save people who would later become his country's enemies. Indeed, Mr. Rabe's outspoken support for the Chinese upon his return to Germany appears to have ruined his career.

Some who have followed his case say that he, like Oskar Schindler, the German industrialist who protected Jews under very different circumstances, offers another example of the durability of humanitarian impulses in the cruelest of times.

Scholars say Mr. Rabe's diary, which includes reports from other foreign observers, photos and other memorabilia, is valuable not so much for revealing new historical facts, but because it provides an unusually detailed and personal account from a German witness to an incident considered among the most brutal in modern warfare. They believe the diary to be authentic, because American missionaries in China who were Mr. Rabe's contemporaries knew of his actions and supplied similar accounts of atrocities.

The diary also offers a counterweight to claims by some Japanese officials who have long denied either the existence or the scale of the massacre in Nanking, which is now known as Nanjing.

"It's an incredibly gripping and depressing narrative, done very carefully with an enormous amount of detail and drama," said William C. Kirby, a professor of modern Chinese history at Harvard University, who has read parts of the diary in German. "It will reopen this case in a very important way in that people can go through the day-by-day account and add 100 to 200 stories to what is popularly known."

The diary has only now come to light because of the efforts of Iris Chang, a Sunnyvale, Calif., author. While researching a book on the Nanjing massacre a few years ago, she stumbled upon a few references to Mr. Rabe's humanitarian efforts. She tracked down Mr. Rabe's granddaughter, Ursula Reinhardt, in Berlin, and upon discovering that Mr. Rabe had kept a diary, persuaded the family to make it public.

Mr. Rabe was ordered by Siemens to leave for the safer grounds of Wuhan, a few hundred miles west on the Yangtze River. But he refused. Instead, he became chairman of a group of about two dozen German and American missionaries, doctors and professors who established a neutral zone in Nanjing as a haven for Chinese refugees.

It was a daunting task. Mr. Rabe witnessed people who were shot, doused with gasoline and burned alive. He saw bodies of women lanced with beer bottles and bamboo sticks.

In his diary entry for Jan. 1, 1938, Mr. Rabe wrote: "The mother of a young attractive girl called out to me, and throwing herself on her knees, crying, said I should help her.

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Upon entering (the house), I saw a Japanese soldier lying completely naked on a young girl, who was crying hysterically. I yelled at this swine, in any language it would be understood, 'Happy New Year!' and he fled from there, naked and with his pants in his hand."

In another entry, referring to the Chinese he had hidden, Mr. Rabe wrote that it was hard to sleep with 650 people snoring in his backyard. On Dec. 10, with water and power failing and the city ringed by fire, he noticed that his canary, Peter, sang in rhythm to the sound of gunfire.

Upon his return to Germany in February 1938, Mr. Rabe wrote a letter to Hitler, asking him to persuade Japan to stop the atrocities. But he was arrested by the Gestapo, interrogated for three days and ordered to keep silent on the subject.

From there Mr. Rabe's life headed into a downward spiral. Between 1938 and 1945, Mr. Rabe worked on and off for the Siemens Company, including a brief stint in Afghanistan. As World War II intensified, Mr. Rabe wrote increasingly in his diary about hunger and the ravages of war; he and his family in Berlin had to eat nettles and acorn soup.

Because Mr. Rabe was one of the about 9 percent of Germans who were members of the Nazi party, he had to petition to be de-Nazified by the Allies after the war in order to hold a job. His first petition was denied, and Mr. Rabe had to appeal.

Ultimately, in June 1946, Mr. Rabe was granted de-Nazification status because of his humanitarian acts in China, according to Ms. Chang. But the investigation proved draining, and he died of a stroke in 1950.

"He was humiliated because he had to go through de-Nazification," Mrs. Reinhardt said in a telephone interview from her home in Berlin.

Mr. Rabe's diary may bolster the efforts of Chinese organizations, who contend that as many as 300,000 Chinese were killed in Nanjing massacres, to extract an apology, or possibly war reparations, from the Japanese Government. Unlike Germany, Japan has been perceived as resisting responsibility for wartime atrocities. Some high-ranking Japanese officials, including a former Minister of Justice, Shigeto Nagano, maintain the incident never happened.

[COPY from: A Nazi who saved 200,000 Chinese people during the Nanjing Massacre (bilingual in Chinese and English). 2020-04-03. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1662917257600628698>]

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Fig. 301. The content of "Rabe's Diary" is well documented and neatly sorted, with many briefs and photos neatly pasted inside.

In 1997, Rabe's Diary was published and translated into four languages: Chinese, English, Japanese, and German. It is widely recognized as the most numerous and well preserved historical material for studying the Nanjing Massacre. [Our national disaster was recorded by 10 foreigners for us. December 13, 2022. https://k.sina.com.cn/article_5505275577_14823d6b90190181o8.html]

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Fig. 302. The film "The Diary of John Rabe" is directed by Florian Gallenberger, starring Ulrich Tukur, Daniel Brühl, Steve Buscemi, Zhang Jingchu, and Kôji Yakusho.

The film is based on the wartime diary written by John Rabe, and through the legendary story of the "Chinese Schindler", it recreates the horrifying and intense memories of the Nanjing Massacre. From the perspective of an eyewitness, the film chronicles the beginning and end of the "Nanjing Massacre" and is the most complete and detailed evidence confirming the events of the "Nanjing" incident. John Rabe, using his affiliation as a member of the Nazi party, confronts the Japanese(**Evil locust**) army and emerges as a hero in the harsh reality of war. During the "Nanjing Massacre", he established the "International Security Zone", providing shelter for nearly 250,000 Chinese civilians and saving their lives.[<https://movie.douban.com/photos/photo/488185372/#title-anchor>],[[Rabe's Diary - Gallenberg Directed Film, https://baike.so.com/doc/863087-912641.html](https://baike.so.com/doc/863087-912641.html)]

Fig. 303. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American named Ms. Minnie Vautrin, Schindler of Nanjing

Ms. Minnie Vautrin was born in Secor, Illinois, United States. She graduated from the

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University of Illinois in 1912 and was sent to China by the United Christian Missionary Society that same year. She served as the principal of the Christian Girls' Middle School in Lu County, Anhui Province (Hefei). In 1916, when Jinling College for Women was founded in Nanjing, she became the head of the Education Department.

In the 1930s, Ms. Minnie Vautrin served as the president of Ginling College for Women and the head of the Education Department. She left behind a diary that detailed the atrocities of the Nanjing Massacre committed by invading Japanese forces, as well as the subsequent years of Japanese colonial rule in Nanjing. From August 12, 1937, to April 1940, she consistently wrote in her diary almost every day and regularly mailed it to her American friends to keep them informed of the current situation in China. Her friends in the United States recognized the value of Vautrin's diary and decided to have it published in *The Classmate*, a magazine in Cincinnati, Ohio. In the mid-1980s, while organizing missionary archives, researchers discovered the original manuscript of Vautrin's diary. In the early 1990s, Ms. Molly Zahniser at Yale Divinity School Library, recognizing the significant archival value of Vautrin's diary, organized and microfilmed it for research purposes by historians and archival researchers.

As Ginling College for Women, where Vautrin was located, served as a refuge for refugee women during the Nanjing Massacre, it became a crucial target for the Japanese forces' sexual violence. As the person in charge of the refugee facility, Vautrin's diary served as the most persuasive evidence in exposing the sexual crimes committed by Japanese forces. For example, on the day after the massacre began (Friday, December 17, 1937), she wrote: "Many exhausted and terrified women came, saying they had gone through a night of terror. Japanese soldiers continuously visited their homes. Girls as young as 12 and old women as aged as 60 were raped. Husbands were forced to leave their bedrooms, and pregnant wives were killed by bayonets." In another entry dated Thursday, December 16, 1937, she wrote: "I do not know how many innocent and hardworking farmers and workers were killed today. We sent all women over the age of 40 back home to be with their husbands and sons, only the daughters and daughters-in-law were allowed to stay. Tonight, we have to take care of more than 4,000 women and children. I don't know how long we can withstand this pressure. It is an indescribable horror." Vautrin herself noted that she wrote the diary "in spare moments, some were written during breaks between air raids, and others at night after a long and busy day" (September 26, 1937). However, this did not diminish its historical value; instead, it made later generations admire its personal character and charm.

Ms. Minnie Vautrin, as an important witness of the Nanjing Massacre, wrote in her diary: "We, as individuals, believe that war is a crime against humanity, a sin that goes against the spiritual essence of creation in the universe. But we can dedicate our strength to the innocent victims and to those families who were burned or looted, as well as to those who were injured by cannons or planes during the war, helping them recover." Once, she saw a Chinese boy wearing such an armband to deliver food to his sister who lived in Jinwuda. She approached the boy and said, "You don't need to wear the Rising Sun flag, you are Chinese, your country has not been lost! Remember when and why you wore this, and never forget!" With that, she helped the boy remove the armband. In

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her diary, she wrote, "From a military perspective, the occupation of Nanjing may be regarded as a victory for the Japanese army, but from a moral standpoint, it is a failure, a disgrace for the Japanese nation."

During the dark days of the Nanjing Massacre, Minnie Vautrin was seen as a guardian angel by the women of Nanjing and a spiritual pillar for the refugees to rely on. As women and children continued to pour in, the number of refugees in the Nanjing Women's Refugee Camp surpassed ten thousand in early 1938.

Under pressure from the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese, the International Committee for the Nanjing Safety Zone was forced to disband in February 1938. On May 21, 1938, the Nanjing Safety Zone was officially closed.

Long hours of labor, heavy schoolwork, and prolonged mental stress caused by the war left Vautrin constantly exhausted. In the spring of 1940, she developed depression, and her condition worsened over time. On May 19 of that year, the severely ill Vautrin left China after twenty years of service.

During her treatment in the United States, she wrote to friends, saying, "For many years, I have loved Ginling College deeply and tried my best to help her. If there is a second life, I would still serve the Chinese people."

On May 14, 1941, the one year anniversary of her departure from China, she chose this meaningful day to end her own life.

After her death, Vautrin was buried in Snowdon Cemetery in Michigan, United States. The front of her tombstone is engraved with four Chinese characters: "Golden City Eternal Life." [Minnie Vautrin's Diary. <https://baike.so.com/doc/533695-565074.html>]

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Fig. 304. What a great American, Minnie Vautrin! A person who should not be forgotten! Schindler of Nanjing

During the Nanjing Massacre, she was the director of Jinling Girls' School. The U.S. government requested her to leave, but she insisted on staying. **She protected more than 10,000 refugees from slaughter, and in order to save thousands of Chinese girls from humiliation, she was repeatedly threatened and beaten by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese (Evil locust) army.** Nanjing citizens call her "Living Bodhisattva," and her tombstone reads "Jinling Eternal Life." Her name is Minnie Vautrin, a person who should not be forgotten.

[<https://v.douyin.com/ip8Ehau/>]

An extremely conscientious, courageous and great American Ms. Minnie Vautrin

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Fig. 305. What a great American. Minnie Vautrin. A person who should not be forgotten! During the Nanjing Massacre, she was the director of Jinling Girls' School. The U.S. government requested her to leave, but she insisted on staying. She protected more than 10,000 refugees from slaughter, and in order to save thousands of Chinese girls from humiliation, she was repeatedly threatened and beaten by the Japanese army. Nanjing citizens call her "Living Bodhisattva," and her tombstone reads "Jinling Eternal Life." Her name is Minnie Vautrin, a person who should not be forgotten. [<https://v.douyin.com/ip8Ehau/>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in making a movie about 29 "Schindlers" in Nanjing who, despite threats from the Japanese army, risked their lives to save about 250,000 Chinese people, it is estimated that the box - office revenue in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will make more people around the world understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace - loving advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments. At the same time, the scale of the Nobel Fund will be further expanded, and the global film

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market will be enlivened.

Fig. 307. The New York Times bestselling account of one of history's most brutal—and forgotten—massacres, when the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese army destroyed China's capital city on the eve of World War II, "piecing together the abundant eyewitness reports into an undeniable tapestry of horror". (Adam Hochschild, Salon)

In December 1937, one of the most horrific atrocities in the long annals of wartime barbarity occurred. The Japanese army swept into the ancient city of Nanking (what was then the capital of China), and within weeks, more than 300,000 Chinese civilians and soldiers were systematically raped, tortured, and murdered. In this seminal work, Iris Chang, whose own grandparents barely escaped the massacre, tells this history from three perspectives: that of the Japanese soldiers, that of the Chinese, and that of a group of Westerners who refused to abandon the city and created a safety zone, which saved almost 300,000 Chinese.

Drawing on extensive interviews with survivors and documents brought to light for the first time, Iris Chang's classic book is the definitive history of this horrifying episode.

"The first comprehensive examination of the destruction of this Chinese imperial city...Ms. Chang, whose grandparents narrowly escaped the carnage, has skillfully excavated from oblivion the terrible events that took place." —The Wall Street Journal
"In her important new book ... Iris Chang, whose own grandparents were survivors,

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recounts the grisly massacre with understandable outrage."—Orville Schell, The New York Times Book Review

"A powerful new work of history and moral inquiry. Chang takes great care to establish an accurate accounting of the dimensions of the violence."—Chicago Tribune

"Chang vividly, methodically, records what happened, piecing together the abundant eyewitness reports into an undeniable tapestry of horror."—Adam Hochschild, Salon

"The story that Chang tells is almost to appalling for words...a carefully documented cry of moral outrage."—Houston Chronicle

"Chang reminds us that however blinding the atrocities in Nanking may be, they are not forgettable—at least without peril to civilization itself."—The Detroit News

"A compelling piece of history that speaks volumes about humankind's inhumanity in the atrocities that have been documented and offers some vestiges of hope in the individual acts of heroism that also have been uncovered."—San Jose Mercury News

"A very readable, well-organized account...Chang has rescued this episode from its undeserved obscurity."—Russell Jenkins, National Review

"Meticulously Researched...A gripping account that holds the reader's attention from beginning to end." —Nien Cheng, author of Life and Death in Shanghai

"Iris Chang's research on the Nanking holocaust yields a new and expanded telling of this World War II atrocity and reflects thorough research. The book is excellent; its story deserves to be heard."—Beatrice S. Bartlett, professor of history, Yale University.

"Heartbreaking.... An utterly compelling book. The descriptions of the atrocities raise fundamental questions not only about imperial Japanese militarism but the psychology of the torturers, rapists, and murderers."—Frederic Wakeman, director of the Institute of East Asian Studies, University of California, Berkeley

"Something beautiful, an act of justice, is occurring in America today concerning something ugly that happened long ago.... Because of Chang's book, the second rape of Nanking is ending."—George F. Will, syndicated columnist

"Anyone interested in the relation between war, self-righteousness, and the human spirit will find The Rape of Nanking of fundamental importance. It is scholarly, an exciting investigation, and a work of passion. In places it is almost unbearable to read, but it should be read only if the past is understood can the future be navigated."—Ross Terrill, author of Mao, China in Our Time, and Madame Mao

"A powerful, landmark book, riveting in its horror." —Richard Rhodes

"One of the most important books of the twentieth century, Iris Chang's The Rape of Nanking will endure as a classic among the world's histories of war."—Nancy Tong, producer and co-director of In the Name of the Emperor

[<https://www.amazon.com/Rape-Nanking-For-gotten-Holocaust-World/dp/0465068367>]

[Rev. John Magee at Daosheng Hall: After the Japanese army invaded Nanjing in December 1937, Rev. John Magee, along with Mr. Rabe, Ms. Waitzkin, and other foreigners, formed the International Committee for the Nanjing Safety Zone. He served as Chairman of the Nanjing Committee of the International Red Cross Society, protecting the Chinese people. Rev. John Magee risked his life to document the

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atrocities committed by the Japanese army in Nanjing using his own camera. This serves as crucial evidence to expose the Japanese army's atrocities to the world. #National Mourning Day# Never forget the national humiliation# Rabe saved 250,000 Chinese people. <https://v.douyin.com/iJDJhQXB/>

Fig. 308. Iris Chang's Tour Speech Reveals Japan's Crimes to the World [She let the world know about Nanjing Datu, thank Mr. Zhang for his great love# Iris Chang 's Unforgettable History # The Motherland Will Not Forget Many People Don't Know This Lady is Our Hero, Revealing Japan's Crimes to the World. On November 9, 2004, she was forced to commit suicide by drinking a bullet. <https://v.douyin.com/iedhtPC4/>]

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Fig. 309. An extremely conscientious, courageous and great American Ms. Iris Chang [Do you remember Iris Chang? She exposed the truth of the Nanjing Massacre throughout her life, but her own life was forever frozen at the age of 36# Don't forget history # Iris Chang # Iris Chang's unforgettable history # Summer Festival. 2022-07-24. <https://v.douyin.com/iedktuqM/>]

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Fig. 310. After the publication of The Rape of Nanking, right-wing Japanese extremists fiercely attacked Iris Chang, with some even sending her bullets.

I am Zhang Yijing, the mother of Iris Chang. Due to the sudden death of Iris Chang, the media reports at that time were somewhat inaccurate and exaggerated. I must clarify these misleading portrayals and make people around the world aware of the true Iris Chang.

On November 9, 2004, Iris Chang, the author of The Rape of Nanking, ended her life by shooting herself in the car. In her suicide note, she wrote that she could no longer face the future pain and torment. The Rape of Nanking will forever be a stain on human honor, and Iris Chang, who merely documented this stain, suffered severe attacks both in her personal life and spiritually.

After the publication of The Rape of Nanking, Japanese extremists fiercely attacked Iris Chang, with some even sending her bullets. However, resilient Iris Chang did not succumb to the threats. When facing interviews, she continued to eloquently describe the atrocities of the Nanking Massacre. These photos sent chills down our spines. As a researcher, Iris Chang surely had more exposure to these themes.

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Comparatively, the impact of these subjects on Iris Chang was even greater than the intimidation tactics of Japanese extremists.

Under immense psychological pressure, Iris Chang endured and tirelessly traveled around, often saying, "I want more people to know the truth." But the power of an individual is ultimately limited.

One night in April 2004, Iris Chang, in a terrible mental state, called her mother in tears. She couldn't sleep recently, plagued by nightmares all night long, and her hair was falling out in clumps, causing her to lose significant weight. Zhang's mother became extremely worried and asked, "Do you still want to continue writing?" Chunru resolutely replied, "Yes." At this point, Iris Chang was already deeply trapped in depression. To continue writing, she needed to take a large amount of medication daily to stabilize her emotions. The side effects of these medications should not be underestimated. As the dosage increased, Iris Chang 's condition worsened.

In the final week of her life, Iris Chang locked herself in her room, refusing all visits. On November 9, 2004, burdened to the extreme, Iris Chang put an end to her life in the most tragic way.

In *The Rape of Nanking*, one Japanese general exonerated himself from his brutal actions, explaining that killing Chinese people feels the same as killing pigs. Iris Chang 's book vividly portrays the atrocities committed by the Japanese army during the Nanking Massacre, including rape, abuse, and the massacre of a large number of innocent Chinese civilians. It forced the Western world to acknowledge this painful history and was recognized as the New York Times' Book of the Year.

[Iris Chang's mother: I want the world to know a real Iris Chang # history # not forgetting national shame # Nanjing Massacre # Iris Chang's unforgettable history. 2023-05-27. <https://v.douyin.com/iedBxNes/>] Iris Chang

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Fig. 316. **An extremely conscientious, courageous and great American John Magee** Footage of American priest John Magee testifying about the Nanjing Massacre at the International Military Tribunal in 1946.

[Video of Reverend John Magee testifying about the Nanjing Massacre in 1946. 2020-12-28. <https://v.douyin.com/iJDdCy8T/>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in making a movie about 29 "Schindlers" in Nanjing who, despite threats from the Japanese army, risked their lives to save about 250,000 Chinese people, it is estimated that the box - office revenue in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will make more people around the world understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating

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more peace - loving advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments. At the same time, the scale of the Nobel Fund will be further expanded, and the global film market will be enlivened.

美国牧师约翰·马吉先生，1937年12月13日，日军暴行期间，仅用一只老式摄像机，冒死拍下日军暴行过程。在日后远东军事法庭上为中国人民做证。

Fig. 317. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American John Magee
Reverend John Magee, member of the International Committee for the Safe Zone and Chairman of the Nanjing Committee of the International Red Cross.

John Magee: He was one of the priests of the Episcopal Church in America. During the Nanjing Massacre, he and several other priests took photographs and documented many of the atrocities. From his footage, it can be seen that the Japanese mercilessly slaughtered innocent civilians, including a photo where a Chinese man's intestines were ripped out.

Magee was most appalled by the Japanese soldiers indiscriminately searching for women in the streets, sparing not even nuns in temples. Even women wounded in hospitals could not escape the brutality of the Japanese.

Another American missionary, George Fitch, witnessed women being forcibly

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taken away by Japanese soldiers. Some were even raped directly. One woman was raped 37 times. The sight of their horrific condition is unbearable. Many pregnant women were gang-raped, and some even had their unborn babies killed before being raped themselves. When one woman with a child was raped by the Japanese, her five-month-old baby started crying, and in a fit of rage, the Japanese soldier suffocated the baby to death.

If the descendants of John Magee come to China, as long as the Chinese people know that their ancestors made contributions in saving the Chinese people during the Nanjing Massacre, they may be invited to drink and eat every day during their trip to China. Similarly, if China knew that their colleague had participated in an international court prosecuting Japanese war criminals, their descendants would also be treated well when they come to China. This is the karmic retribution in Buddhism – previous generations sow good deeds, and later generations reap the benefits, or later generations enjoy shade. This is also the concept of karmic retribution in Taoism.

[Today is the National Memorial Day for the Nanjing Massacre. We would like to express our gratitude to the Western international friends who provided protection for the people of Nanjing during that time. They were not the so-called living Buddhas, but simply flesh and blood individuals. Truth and great love know no boundaries of nationality or ethnicity. On December 13th, when the city of Nanjing was engulfed in flames and the land was broken, they chose not to leave. The world will forever remember the humane actions of our Western friends. Always remember. 2022-12-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iJE9PaJw/>]

Chris Majee captured a real and dynamic film of the Nanjing Massacre(or the Rape of Nanking), which can be searched on the internet

One of the 29 Oscar Schindlers in the Nanjing Massacre

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in making a movie about 29 "Schindlers" in Nanjing who, despite threats from the Japanese army, risked their lives to save about 250,000 Chinese people, it is estimated that the box - office revenue in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will make more people around the world understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace - loving advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments. At the same time, the scale of the Nobel Fund will be further expanded, and the global film market will be enlivened.

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南京大屠杀中，一个德国人
冒死救下25万中国人。
请记住他的名字:约翰.拉贝

Fig. 320. Group photo of some members of the Nanjing Safety Zone International Committee and the Nanjing Committee of the International Red Cross

A small suggestion:

Due to the atrocities committed by the Japanese army during the Nanjing Massacre, which set more than 100 records in human history for killings, rapes, and robberies, perhaps Hollywood directors could approach the subject from a different perspective and carefully portray the brave, fearless, kind, and righteous characters of the unprecedented 29 Oskar Schindlers of Nanjing. This could potentially result in a globally sensational film, not only showcasing everyone's acting talents but also achieving an extremely high attendance rate in China at least.

Some of the 29 Oscar Schindlers in the Nanjing Massacre

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Fig. 329. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American, Professor Bedes, Schindler of Nanjing

Member of the International Committee for Safe Zones and Professor of Jinling University.

In December 1957, Dr. Bates, a history professor at Jinling University and an American, was one of the initiators of the Nanjing Safety Zone International Committee (later renamed the Nanjing International Relief Committee) and also served as its final chairman. As a historian, Dr. Bates took extensive records and provided external reports regarding the atrocities committed by Japanese forces during the Nanjing Massacre. He also collected and preserved various valuable written materials. Dr. Bates ensured that the precious archival documents of the International Committee were saved.

On January 10, 1938, Dr. Bates sent out a confidential letter via a U.S. Navy tugboat heading for Hankou. The letter was copied and sent secretly. The letter began with the statement, "This short note was written hastily amidst the midst of rape, bayonetting, and indiscriminate shootings." It then proceeded to provide detailed accounts of the Japanese atrocities in Nanjing during the previous month. This letter eventually reached the hands of many individuals, both domestic and foreign. Wang Shijie, Minister of Education of the National Government at the time, recorded in his diary on February 14, "Today I crossed the Yangtze River from Hankou to Wuchang for a dinner appointment at Huazhong University. During the meal, Huang Pu, the acting president of the university, mentioned the information brought out by Professor Bates, an American, who remained in Nanjing. According to Mr. Bates' letter dated January 10, the deplorable situation of rape, looting, and slaughter of unarmed civilians by Japanese troops is beyond imagination." It is evident that Dr. Bates' letter had garnered significant attention from the Chinese government.

The Bedford Letter, which provides concrete evidence, was the first disclosure to

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the outside world of the truth about the Nanjing Massacre that took place on January 10, 1938. In this letter Bedford stated, "We feel it is a moral obligation to actively expose the truth about these atrocities. Only we or those who work with us can do that."

On April 12, 1938, Bedford clearly mentioned in a letter to a friend sent from Shanghai, "Here, the precious 'Bedford Documents' recording the Nanjing Massacre are being actively prepared for publication in the United Kingdom and the United States. This book, written by Mr. H.J. Timothy, an experienced journalist from The Manchester Guardian, is likely to be titled 'The Japanese Terror in China.' ... He has preserved a large amount of documentation that testifies to the situation in China obtained from relief organizations. These materials are published in a fair and constructive manner... Although I cannot assume legal responsibility for this work, I have been involved from the beginning, participating in planning and development, as well as proofreading all manuscripts. Additionally, the book includes a report I drafted on December 15, which was prepared for many news reporters who were still in Nanjing at that time. The appendix contains several letters I sent to the Japanese Embassy during December, including my account of the widespread terror in Nanjing over the past few weeks, which I described on January 10th." The book also quotes the diary of Fei Wusheng regarding the Japanese atrocities and includes several photographs taken by Ma Ji about Japanese atrocities.

Beitashen collaborated with Tian Boli, a journalist for The Manchester Guardian, providing him with a large amount of information and letters. In March 1938, Tian compiled the book "What War Means? The Japanese Terror in China" (published by Modern Age Books). In July 1938, a Chinese translation by Yang Ming titled "Foreigners Witnessing the Japanese Atrocities" was published in Hankou. Two Japanese translations were also published. Beitashen participated directly in the writing of this book and reviewed all manuscripts, omitting names for safety reasons. This book truthfully revealed the facts of the massacre from the perspective of foreigners in Beijing and was the earliest published original archival collection on the Nanjing Massacre. It has been translated into many languages and has had a significant impact both domestically and internationally.

The Japanese authorities tightened restrictions on the actions of Westerners in Nanjing. They warned Beitashen and others that if they continued with "malicious propaganda," they would be considered enemies of the entire Japanese army. However, Beitashen ignored these warnings and continued to expose the Japanese atrocities in Nanjing. This greatly angered the Japanese authorities, who repeatedly threatened Beitashen, accusing him of being "anti-Japanese," "sinister," and "mentally ill." They also used their controlled newspaper, The New Shenbao, to fabricate lies and attack Beitashen personally and Jinling University. Beitashen did not yield to these attacks and emphasized in his letters, "We feel it is a moral obligation to actively expose the truth of the atrocities. I do not believe that weakness will improve our situation in the world. Let us fulfill our own recognized responsibility with a kind heart and bear the consequences."

On May 3, 1946, after victory in the War of Resistance against Japan, the Far East

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International Military Tribunal began the trial of the first batch of 28 class-A war criminals, including General Matsui Iwane, the main perpetrator of the Nanjing Massacre and former commander of the Central China Area Army of the Imperial Japanese Army, as well as accomplices former Prime Minister Hirota Koki and former deputy chief of staff of the Central China Area Army Muto Shozo. To bring these executioners to justice, the Chinese side invited Bedeschi, a former member of the International Committee, to testify in court.

On July 29, Bedeschi arrived at the Tokyo court. After taking an oath, Bedeschi presented abundant and compelling evidence to accuse the Japanese military of their brutal and heinous acts in Nanjing, providing ironclad proof of the fact of the massacre that Japanese war criminals could not deny.

When Bedeschi left China in 1950, he brought back these archival documents, along with copies of his testimony at the Far East International Military Tribunal in July 1946 and reports on the trial, to the United States. They were eventually preserved as the "Bedeschi Documents" in the Special Collections of the Library of the Divinity School at Yale University. These records constitute the authentic archival documentation of the Nanjing Massacre and are the largest and most complete collection of original English documents on the Nanjing Massacre to date, serving as first-hand accounts of the massacre during that period. Bedeschi passed away in 1978.

[Translated from: The "Bedesley Documents" Recording the Nanjing Massacre. September 8, 2022. <https://www.krzzjn.com/show-404-124040.html>]

Fig. 330. In June 1938, Britain published "What war means, the Japanese terror in China," which was the earliest book to expose the Nanjing Massacre perpetrated by the Japanese army to the world. The author of this book was the British journalist Harold Timperley from The Manchester Guardian. At that time, to protect the safety of the individuals providing the information, Timperley concealed the real name of the

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sources, which caused some confusion for future researchers. However, it has been later confirmed that the significant information provider was indeed the history professor at Jinling University, Professor Bedes.

December 12, 2015. <http://news.jstv.com/a/20151212/1449898192850.shtml>

Fig. 337. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American, Dr. George Fitch, Director General of the Security Zone and Director of the Young Christian Association of the United States.

Dr. George Fitch, an American, was born in Suzhou, China in 1883. In order to commemorate his birthplace, he gave himself a Chinese name - Fei Wusheng. His father was a missionary and his mother was also a devout Christian. Growing up in China, Fitch developed a deep affection for the country. In 1900, he returned to the United States to study and obtained a doctoral degree. In 1909, he went back to Shanghai and served as a staff member of the YMCA.

In mid-November 1937, Fitch returned to Nanjing. Faced with such a dire situation, he made the brave decision to stay in Nanjing and help protect the remaining residents. Along with several other prominent foreigners who also stayed in Nanjing, he established the International Committee for the Nanjing Safety Zone, with Fitch as Executive Secretary. During the brutal massacre carried out by Japanese troops in Nanjing, Fitch and his colleagues, using their American identity, wholeheartedly assisted and protected the refugees. They also documented the numerous atrocities committed by the Japanese in Nanjing, and these written records and visual evidence became irrefutable evidence exposing the Japanese military's crimes in Nanjing after

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the war.

Fitch's diary, from December 10, 1937 to January 1938, recorded the changes and horrors in Nanjing before and after the massacre. In Fitch's mind, Nanjing was a "beautiful city that we were proud of, still having law and order." However, after the Japanese army entered Nanjing, it became a "deserted, full of killings, looting, and mostly burned city."

Before the Japanese army entered Nanjing, Fitch and staff of the safety zone were actively preparing for the construction of the zone. Fitch's diary of December 1 recorded their thoughts before the Japanese army entered the city, "We didn't feel any serious danger, thinking that the Japanese army seemed to want to avoid air raids and shelling in the refugee zone, and compared to the hell caused by the Japanese invasion, Nanjing was a heaven of order and safety." However, they never expected that a few days later Nanjing would turn into a human hell filled with killings and fear.

The atrocities perpetrated by the Japanese army in Nanjing are too numerous to be fully document. **Since their entry into the city, they have engaged in indiscriminate looting, extorting money from refugees, and robbing them of any belongings they could find, "not even sparing the last bit of bedding."** Refugee livelihood necessities, such as carts and livestock, were confiscated. They also looted stores, with Fitch witnessing "thugs setting fire to shops, while others loaded captured items onto trucks." Fitch recalls a day on January 18, where one man was shot in the arm by Japanese soldiers because he didn't have money to give them, and another was injured by soldiers for not having the strength to carry a heavy object, among many similar examples. **In order to eliminate evidence of their looting, Japanese soldiers often set fire to stores and residences after looting,** leading to multiple arson incidents in Nanjing city every day, sometimes even whole streets burning. Fitch wrote in a letter to a friend, "Nanjing has been systematically looted and burned, now reduced to an empty shell. **Most shops and Chinese houses were burned down, after the victors took whatever they wanted from them."**

Japanese brutally killed Chinese people without reason. They could capture anyone they deemed suspicious anywhere, and those with calloused hands were mistaken for Chinese soldiers and taken away to be killed. Power plant workers were mistaken for state-owned enterprise employees and were arrested and executed. Some people were cruelly killed for trying to prevent or resist the Japanese army's rape. Fitch's diary also recorded numerous horrifying scenes of piles of corpses in Nanjing City. **On December 15th, he wrote, "We were indeed driving through layers of corpses that were two to three feet thick and ninety feet long. The scene is indescribable, and I will never forget this journey."** "The stench in the city is overwhelming, and there are stray dogs feasting on corpses everywhere." **On December 22, Fey recorded, "There were 50 bodies in a muddy swamp, all ordinary people with their hands bound behind their backs. One person had his head completely chopped off. Were they practicing assassinations?"** Such brutal scenes were countless in Nanjing at that time. Source: "Nanjing Massacre and Western International Friends"

[Translated from: George Fitch: He witnessed Nanjing City being turned into a hell on

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earth by the invading Japanese army. January 23, 2019.
https://www.sohu.com/a/290943550_241223]

Fig. 338. **A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American**, Secretary of the International Committee of the Safe Zone and Professor Smythe of Jinling University.

[Bring evil to the surface: Unveiling the Nanjing Massacre through photographs and film. <https://www.krzzjn.com/show-17-1211.html>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in making a movie about 29 "Schindlers" in Nanjing who, despite threats from the Japanese army, risked their lives to save about 250,000 Chinese people, it is estimated that the box - office revenue in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will make more people around the world understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace - loving advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments. At the same time, the scale of the Nobel Fund will be further expanded, and the global film market will be enlivened.

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Fig. 341 A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great Danish Hero B.A.Sindperg, Schindler of Nanjing

[Today is the National Memorial Day for the Nanjing Massacre. We would like to express our gratitude to the Western international friends who provided protection for the people of Nanjing during that time. They were not the so-called living Buddhas, but simply flesh and blood individuals. Truth and great love know no boundaries of nationality or ethnicity. On December 13th, when the city of Nanjing was engulfed in flames and the land was broken, they chose not to leave. The world will forever remember the humane actions of our Western friends. Always remember. 2022-12-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iJE9PaJw/>]

106 days of protection, facing the evil Japanese holding knives and guns

During the Nanjing Massacre, documentary videos and photos of Japanese atrocities and inhumanity captured by Sindperg are easily searchable on the internet.

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Fig. 346. Sindberg Statue Completed, Queen of Denmark Unveiled.
[Sindberg Statue Completed, Queen of Denmark Unveiled. September 2, 2019.
<https://finance.sina.cn/2019-09-02/detail-iicezueu2823309.d.html>]

106 days of protection, facing the evil Japanese holding knives and guns

In an era of longing for peace, exploring potential material and grasping the pulse of the future will win the film.

If Hollywood directors want to make an extraordinary film, Spielberg and Dr. Karl Günther's heroic feat of rescuing more than 20,000 refugees may be suitable for a stand-alone film.

There are many typical themes in the rescue process, with outstanding character personalities, and refugees are extremely grateful. What's more important is that there are still survivors, making it easy to delve deeper into the story. The scenes of Sindberg and Dr. Karl Günther accompanying the Japanese troops for meals and drinks are enough for the director and screenwriter to portray.

The harassment of Japanese troops at the Jiangnan cement plant was also motivated by their desire to eat and drink for free. Sindberg and Dr. Karl Günthers only way to deal with these trouble-making Japanese soldiers is to "entertain and engage" them. The cost of entertaining these Japanese troops can be as high as three to four hundred yuan per month.

During the Nanjing Massacre, documentary videos and photos of Japanese atrocities and inhumanity captured by Sindperg are easily searchable on the internet.

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly

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invest in making a movie about 29 "Schindlers" in Nanjing who, despite threats from the Japanese army, risked their lives to save about 220,000 Chinese people, it is estimated that the box - office revenue in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will make more people around the world understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace - loving advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments. At the same time, the scale of the Nobel Fund will be further expanded, and the global film market will be enlivened.

Fig. 350. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great German Hero Dr. Karl Günther, Schindler of Nanjing

[2020-05-07. <https://v.douyin.com/iJUxAjRE/>]

At the end of 1937, the Japanese army invaded Nanjing, and Dr. Karl Günther from Germany was appointed as the acting director of Jiangnan Cement Factory. He arrived at the factory from Tangshan on the eve of the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese army. Together with B.A. Sindperg of Denmark's Smith Company and Chinese staff member Shen Jihua, they embarked on brave actions of self-defense and saving people. They hung or drew German and Danish flag symbols on factory gates, rooftops, and grounds, turning the factory area into a protected zone. After witnessing the brutal atrocities committed by the Japanese army against Chinese soldiers and civilians, they immediately assisted a large number of refugees and set up a "refugee camp" with their "foreigner" identity, providing as much help as they could. B.A. Sindperg brought two nurses from the Red Cross Society of Drum Tower Hospital, along with medicine and bandages, to treat the refugees' injuries and illnesses. They also organized a guard team to patrol day and night, preventing Japanese troops from entering and causing violence. Once, when the Japanese army set fire to houses in a nearby village, Dr. Karl Günther and others rushed to the scene with the German flag,

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risking danger, and argued with the Japanese army, forcing them to withdraw and allowing the fire to be extinguished.

On December 9th and 11th, 1937, the Japanese 16th Division and 13th Division successively invaded the Qixia area. Dr. Karl Günther and others accompanied these two forces, especially the 1st Battalion of the 38th Unit of the Japanese 16th Division. Shortly after the fall of Nanjing, this battalion was stationed near the Jiangnan Cement Factory and Qixia Temple, and the sword of Damocles hung conspicuously above the Jiangnan Cement Factory. After the Japanese occupation of Qixia, massacres and arson continued. On December 13, after Nanjing was occupied by the Japanese, they carried out large-scale sweeping, searching, and killing of "defeated soldiers" in the urban and rural areas of Nanjing. Dr. Karl Günther also protected some Chinese soldiers who no longer carried weapons. After the victory of the resistance war, the Jiangnan Cement Factory was preserved for the use of Dr. Karl Günther, so as not to be expelled as a general German immigrant and to report to the Nanjing authorities: "In the winter of the 26th year, many refugees from various places gathered on Mount Qixia. It is heard that among them there are not a few senior military officers who cannot retreat. They have lost government protection and live in constant fear. Thanks to Dr. Karl Günther for setting up a refugee zone in the Jiangnan Cement Factory..."

Dr. Karl Günther also led workers and refugees in burying the bodies during the occupation. In July 1937, Luo Zuwei, a veterinarian for the Nationalist Central Military Academy's Cavalry Regiment, recalled, "After the occupation, the Japanese cavalry scattered to various villages in search, setting houses on fire as they searched... The sides of the road were filled with dead bodies... Some were enemies who had been tied up and stabbed to death with bayonets... The Yao Hua Gate barracks and houses had all been burned down, and corpses were lying everywhere in the courtyard... We only approached Qixia Mountain at daybreak and saw many corpses on the side of the road... When we reached the Jiangnan Cement Factory, we heard that they were also housing refugees, so we went there first. We saw the iron gate of the factory closed, and there were workers guarding it. We asked them for shelter, and since they heard that both of us spoke in the dialect of the north, they quickly said, 'We are all fellow villagers, come in quickly.' They accommodated us in a large room and introduced us to a foreigner. Afterwards, we were led by the foreigner every day to salvage corpses by the river, and after salvaging them, we buried them on a small hill by the river. I salvaged a total of eight corpses, all charred remains that were barely recognizable. I stayed at the Jiangnan Cement Factory for about seven days, and suddenly we heard from the workers from the north that the Japanese were going to inspect the factory the next day and told us to leave quickly."

In the years of constant warfare, Japanese soldiers continued to cause violence, resulting in an increasing number of innocent Chinese villagers getting injured. However, B.A. Sindperg's attempts to bring wounded villagers into the city for medical treatment were consistently blocked by Japanese soldiers. In response, B.A. Sindperg and Dr. Karl Günther established a small hospital at the Jiangnan Cement Factory to provide free medical care for refugees. B.A. Sindperg recruited two nurses from Drum

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Tower Hospital and the International Red Cross Society, bringing back a large supply of medicines. Thoughtful Dr. Karl Günther, considering that farmers trusted traditional Chinese medicine more, proposed the idea of collaborating with three elderly Chinese doctors. The hospital saved countless lives and was a source of comfort. Xu Xinnong, who was involved in managing the refugee area at the Jiangnan cement plant, referred to the small hospital in a letter to foreign managers at Shanghai International Settlement, saying it provides medical treatment for 70-80 patients daily, with three times the number of patients being carried back. He described it as a charitable endeavor to help the sick.

According to the records of the Jiangnan Cement Factory, Dr. Karl Günther and B.A. Sindperg, with their special status, transformed the factory into the largest mobile refugee camp in Nanjing, accommodating over 20,000 refugees. In addition, they translated the refugees' pleas for help into German and sent them to the German Foreign Ministry, becoming powerful evidence in the current accusations against the Japanese military for their invasion of China and the Nanjing Massacre.

[The adventure between life and death is Dr. Karl Günther's unwavering help.

January 21, 2019; https://www.sohu.com/a/290256407_99912564],

[Schindler of Nanjing "- Descendants of Carl Jingté Come to Nanjing to Participate in the Nanjing and Tangshan Twin Cities Commemorative Exhibition. December 11, 2017. https://www.sohu.com/a/209875128_99909071]

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Fig. 352. A brave and fearless American general named Claire Lee Chennault

In April 1937, Lieutenant Claire Lee Chennault retired from military service feeling frustrated. At that time, his good friend Hubert Rock sent him a letter from China, asking if he would be willing to come to China for a job. Chen happily accepted the offer. During this period, dark clouds of war loomed as Japan attempted to occupy China. Chen had always wanted to implement his "winning through air power" theory, but his theory was not accepted by mainstream U.S. military theory, which focused on the dominance of bomber forces.

On December 7, 1941, General Chennault led the 1st and 2nd squadrons of the "American Volunteer Group" to move to Kunming. Just 12 days after the Japanese attack on Pearl Harbor, which took place on December 20, Chen Nade finally got the opportunity to showcase his skills. On that day, 10 Japanese bombers attacked, and Chen quickly sent 30 fighter planes into the sky, shooting down 6 enemy planes and damaging 3, without any casualties on his side.

That day, the mayor of Kunming led hundreds of citizens to congratulate "the great

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benefactors of the Chinese people" by beating drums and gongs. Red cloth strips, used for prayers, were tied around the necks of these squadron members by the Chinese people. In the evening, a celebration was held in honor of the American Volunteer Group in Kunming.

The next day, almost all Chinese newspapers reported the battle in front-page headlines, referring to the U.S. Volunteer Group's planes as "flying tigers." From then on, this custom-made laurel wreath of "Chinese invention" was presented to the American Volunteer Group led by General Chennault.

According to the statistics of the Chinese Air Force Command on February 16, 1945, under General Chennault's command, a total of 33,450 Japanese soldiers were killed, 494 aircraft were destroyed, and 640,900 tons of ships were sunk.

[The War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression General Chennault, wife Chen Xiangmei, and their daughter of the US Flying Tigers. 2021-11-21.<https://v.douyin.com/iJKCRMSP/>, [December 12, 2015. <https://www.toutiao.com/article/1043056970/>]

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/1043056970/>

If you have feasible dreams that can't be realized in the United States, maybe you can find opportunities in China. General Chennault's era was like this, and it should be the same now or in the future.

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Fig. 404. The great literary scholar Lu Xun in China

Elder brother Lu Xun painstakingly raised money to buy a large villa to bring the three brothers' families together, living in a mansion with 32 rooms. However, his efforts were in vain. The Japanese sister-in-law was vicious and even falsely accused Lu Xun of peeping at her while she was bathing. In order to claim exclusive ownership of this grand house, she schemed to drive the elder brother away. Surprisingly, the second brother was deceived by his Japanese wife and even wanted to physically harm the older brother. Enraged, the elder brother immediately moved out of the expensive villa. <https://v.douyin.com/iJuuf32M/>

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Fig. 405. The wife of the second brother of the great literary scholar Lu Xun, a Japanese woman who messes up a big family

Elder brother Lu Xun painstakingly raised money to buy a large villa to bring the three brothers' families together, living in a mansion with 32 rooms. However, his efforts were in vain. The Japanese sister-in-law was vicious and even falsely accused Lu Xun of peeping at her while she was bathing. In order to claim exclusive ownership of this grand house, she schemed to drive the elder brother away. Surprisingly, the second brother was deceived by his Japanese wife and even wanted to physically harm the older brother. Enraged, the elder brother immediately moved out of the expensive villa. <https://v.douyin.com/iJHkTrdd/>

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Fig. 405. The great Chinese writer Lu Xun had two younger brothers, one named Zhou Zuoren and the other named Zhou Jianren.

Initially, Lu Xun and Zhou Zuoren went to study in Japan, and Zhou Jianren also wanted to go, but the family didn't have enough money, and their mother needed someone to take care of her, so Zhou Jianren had no choice but to stay behind.

Later, Zhou Zuoren married the landlady's maid in Japan and struggled to make a living. In order to support his younger brother, Lu Xun gave up the idea of studying in Germany and returned to China to find a job. At that time, Zhou Jianren was teaching at a local school in their hometown.

During this time, Lu Xun and Zhou Jianren worked together to earn money to support Zhou Zuoren and his wife, until Zhou Zuoren brought his wife back to China.

However, no one expected that it was Zhou Zuoren's Japanese wife who not only caused discord between brothers of the Zhou family but also ruined Zhou Jianren's life.

At first, Yutaka Nobuko looked down on the Chinese people, but after marrying into the Zhou family, she realized that life in the Zhou family was much better than in Japan.

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Firstly, there was no one to restrain her in the Zhou family, and secondly, Lu Xun advised their mother to hand over the family's finances to her in order to maintain family harmony. As a result, Yutaka Nobuko became the dominator of the Zhou family.

After Yutaka Nobuko became pregnant, she even brought her own younger sister Fangzi to China to take care of her. After Fangzi settled in the Zhou family, she gradually became unwilling to return to her poor hometown in Japan. Yutaka Nobuko came up with a twisted idea to make her sister stay: marry into the Zhou family!

At that time, Lu Xun was already married, and the only one who hadn't settled down was Zhou Jianren. Zhou Jianren originally had a fiancée, but unfortunately, she passed away due to illness. He was deeply saddened, and this gave Yutaka Nobuko the opportunity to set a trap.

One night, Yutaka Nobuko deliberately got Zhou Jianren drunk and then sent her sister Fangzi into his room. When Zhou Jianren woke up the next morning, he was stunned. Many years later, Lu Xun's son, Zhou Haiying, mentioned this family secret and vividly recalled his father's dissatisfaction with the matter at that time: "It was a forced and fraudulent set-up..."

In Yutaka Nobuko's eyes, regardless of whether her sister was married or not, she still had to obey her commands. Therefore, Fangzi would often spend the whole day by her sister's side and couldn't go back until late at night. Even after Fangzi had her own child, it remained the same.

In order to maintain family harmony, Zhou Jianren endured his dissatisfaction, but his tolerance had no effect. Under Yutaka Nobuko's instigation, the relationship between the couple became increasingly strained.

One day, Zhou Zuoren, his wife, and Fangzi went out to play together. Zhou Jianren thought he could also go along, but as soon as he reached the car door, his wife gave him a disdainful look and sneered, "Are you coming too?" Zhou Zuoren and his wife stood on the side without even looking at Zhou Jianren.

This incident deeply hurt Zhou Jianren. In August 1920, after finding a job in Shanghai, he quickly packed his bags and fled the city.

[Lu Xun's third brother, Zhou Jianren, was deceived into marriage by a Japanese woman who got him drunk. Afterwards, he married a student who was 12 years younger than him. #marriage #female_growth #love #woman. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7074937764529081631>],[Why did Lu Xun's third brother marry his sister-in-law's biological sister? Years later, the son of Lu Xun revealed the truth: someone had drunk and played tricks. August 16, 2022 .<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1741328497183737614&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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1919年，鲁迅豪掷3000大洋买了一套四合院，让弟弟周作人一家也住进来，可有天弟媳妇却对周作人说：“大伯偷看我洗澡！”结果，弟弟拿起香炉砸向鲁迅，哥俩直接掰了。

鲁迅有大家长观念，所以奋斗十年后，兄弟三人凑钱3500元买房，不过他看不惯弟媳羽太信子花钱不节制，训斥她：“花钱别只看当下，也要想想未来！”

怀恨在心的信子就给老公周作人吹耳边风，结果哥俩反目成仇，直到哥哥去世，周作人才受到触动，写了不少回忆鲁迅的书。

妻贤夫祸少，只可惜当初的周作人没明白。

Fig. 406. <https://v.douyin.com/iJuUx3wf/>

Fig. 407. **The continuous negative impact on the family after the marriage of family members to evil Japanese women.**

After five years of Lu Xun's death, his wife Xu Guangping was arrested by the Japanese

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army and imprisoned for 76 days, enduring torture and humiliation. Japanese soldiers used physical violence against Xu Guangping, slapping her and kicking her to the ground. They also used their boots to step on her mercilessly. Later, not only did they use whipping, they also used the cruelest form of electric torture. When the electric current passed through Xu Guangping's body, she uncontrollably started to tremble, feeling her stomach churn. She felt that she could die at any moment. She fainted multiple times, only to be revived by being splashed with water. Faced with these despicable enemies, she stood firm and unwavering, refusing to yield. However, during the more than two months of her sister-in-law being imprisoned by the Japanese army, Lu Xun's younger brother and his Japanese wife never attempted to rescue her. They displayed extreme indifference and completely lost their basic sense of family love. It was ultimately thanks to the efforts of Lu Xun's good friend, Naoya Uchimura, Xu Guangping walked out of prison.

[Five years after Lu Xun's death, Xu Guangping was arrested by the Japanese army and imprisoned for 76 days, enduring torture and humiliation. July 30, 2023. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1772826322130091799&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 409. The backs of two Heroes.

Having endured the cruel torture inflicted by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus--- Japanese invaders(Evil locust) throughout the day, three steadfast and unyielding anti-Japanese warriors refused to divulge any valuable information. In the end, these brave individuals were ruthlessly subjected to the use of bacterial viruses by the merciless Japanese Unit 731, eventually being turned into biological specimens. Miabo Sanbei was a Japanese(Evil locust) military police officer who wrote a memoir

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recounting a cruel incident: [Kempeitai's memory: I caught four Eighth Route Army, and they were finally made into specimens. March 07, 2023; https://www.toutiao.com/article/7207804512697025036/?log_from=b11b4b1b5f50d_1680423587504]

Fig. 410. **The large iron nails used by the Japanese invaders to nail the Chinese people.** Having endured the cruel torture inflicted by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus--- Japanese invaders(Evil locust) throughout the day, three steadfast and unyielding anti-Japanese warriors refused to divulge any valuable information. In the end, these brave individuals were ruthlessly subjected to the use of bacterial viruses by the merciless Japanese(Evil locust) Unit 731, eventually being turned into biological specimens.

Miabo Sanbei was a Japanese military police officer who wrote a memoir recounting a cruel incident: [Kempeitai's memory: I caught four Eighth Route Army, and they were finally made into specimens. March 07, 2023; https://www.toutiao.com/article/7207804512697025036/?log_from=b11b4b1b5f50d_1680423587504]

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your retired parents and delay age-related dementia, why not have them research and calculate how many different types of torture were used by the infamous Japanese and the notorious Japanese Imperial Army Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre or in China?

If you want to improve your high school-aged son or daughter's cognitive and computational abilities, expose them to the complexities of society, enhance their judgment of evil forces, and develop their risk prevention skills, why not have them try

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to figure out how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese against the women they forcibly recruited as sex slaves or so-called "comfort women" during World War II? Some estimates indicate that there were at least 100 different types. Can they find them all?

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 411. The skulls of two Chinese anti-Japanese female soldiers were sawed off by evil and cruel Japanese to make water ladles.

[Don't forget national shame # Remember history # Don't forget that painful history #

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Forgetting history means betrayal # The hatred engraved in the bones of the Japanese atrocities will never be forgotten! Remember history and never forget national shame!!
<https://v.douyin.com/iJLpRryj/>

Fig. 412. This is the skull of 5,000 people from Hunan who were killed by evil and brutal Japanese invaders

[#Remembering History # Forgetting National Shame 2022-07-17.
<https://v.douyin.com/iJLqF89U/>]

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Fig. 413. The picture shows female students in Osaka undergoing military training in February 1937. [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism. June 26, 2017; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 414. Japanese children visit models of warships. Cultivating interest in the military from a young age laid the foundation for Japanese belligerence. [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism. June 26, 2017; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 415. Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japanese children undergoing military training. These people later became fanatical militarists, fighting for Japan's aggression against other countries.[Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism. June 26, 2017; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 416. [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism.

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June

26,

2017;

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 417. Japanese children undergoing military training. These people later became fanatical Militarism, fighting for Japan's aggression against other countries. . [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism.

June

26,

2017;

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 418. Under the influence of Militarism education, however, the eyes of Japanese (Evil locust) children who are just a few years old have become very scary. [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism. June 26, 2017;

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

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Fig. 419. In the national education of Japanese(Evil locust) militarism, the foreign War of aggression should start from children. The picture shows Japanese fanatical child soldiers. [Terrifying! Japanese national education under the control of Militarism. June 26, 2017; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1571231141374933&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 419. On October 15, 1939, the mother of the Shida Valley Field Artillery Corps

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in Tokyo and a group of children went to a Japanese(Evil locust) military camp for a life experience, where they were taught the principles of artillery shells by soldiers. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 420. On October 15, 1939, in the Tokyo Shida Valley Field Artillery Team, the mother and her child participated in a one-day military camp life experience. Gathering together to listen to soldiers explain battlefield first aid methods. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022;

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<https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>

Fig. 421. In February 1940, Nakamura Elementary School in Fanghe County, Tochigi Prefecture, Japan participated in a joint military flag festival, performing war games at the event, and also received praise from the Japanese Army Minister. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Do you know how American President Roosevelt and French President Charles de Gaulle evaluate Japanese people?

Fig. 422. Infant specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader 731 unit.

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The cruel Japanese military unit 731 conducted live dissection experiments on Chinese children.

[Japanese 731 Research Institute, dissecting Chinese children alive and soaking them in bottles # 731 # Japanese atrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJMwUo6j/>]

Fig. 423. Chinese child limb specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader Unit 731. The cruel Japanese military unit 731 conducted live dissection experiments on Chinese children.

[Japanese 731 Research Institute, dissecting Chinese children alive and soaking them in bottles # 731 # Japanese atrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJMwUo6j/>]

Fig. 424. Infant specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader 731 unit. The baby's internal organs were dug out.

The cruel Japanese military unit 731 conducted live dissection experiments on Chinese children.

[Japanese 731 Research Institute, dissecting Chinese children alive and soaking them in bottles # 731 # Japanese atrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJMwUo6j/>]

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Fig. 425. Japanese students wear hand-made gas masks in war games. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of

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conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022;
<https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 426. Senior Japanese girls also organized stretcher teams to participate in simulated war games. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 427. Japanese children are still using homemade airplane models to simulate

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aerial combat in war games. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 428. In August 1941, students from Musashino Cho Yingjin College in Tokyo crossed the river to capture the highlands in a simulated war during summer exercises. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

Do you know how American President Roosevelt and French President Charles de Gaulle evaluate Japanese people?

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Fig. 429 Japanese people have been trained from a young age to bow deeply, creating the illusion of being very polite and civilized around the world. During this period, Japanese people engaged in daily work such as rape, gang rape, mass slaughter, eating human flesh, grilling live people, looting gold, silver, jewelry, grain, coal, and nonferrous metals.

In October 1941, at Changye Village National School, Iwata Prefecture, Shizuoka Prefecture, Japan, graduates donated money to set up a sentry, and senior students held guns as guards.[Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream

March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 430. The Evil *Staphylococcus aureus*---Japanese (Evil locust) government indoctrinates the young Japanese female students with fanatical Militarism and lets them choose the soldiers who are going to the battlefield to marry. [Japanese soldiers have lost humanity in China and educated their children in this way within Japan. 2017-09-24; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1579426717818843793&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Fig. 431. This was a performance at Hiroshima School in Japan, where students happily

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imitated the war scenes. [Japanese soldiers have lost humanity in China and educated their children in this way within Japan. 2017-09-24; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1579426717818843793&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Fig. 432. The Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese had a deep hatred of the United States. This was during regular training at that time, Japanese students used bamboo knives to strike portraits of U.S. President Roosevelt and British Prime Minister Churchill, instilling a sense of disgust. [Japanese soldiers have lost humanity in China and educated their children in this way within Japan. 2017-09-24; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1579426717818843793&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

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Fig. 433. This is a pair of Japanese children who visited a shrine in the past. They may not yet know the concepts of love and hate, but they have been imbued with a distorted outlook on life. [Japanese soldiers have lost humanity in China and educated their children in this way within Japan. 2017-09-24; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1579426717818843793&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

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Fig. 434. This documentary was filmed in 2016 and includes narration in Chinese, Japanese, and English. It documents the testimonies of medical personnel from the Japanese Army's Unit 731, who describe how they injected syphilis and other diseases into live human subjects and subsequently performed dissections on living individuals and pregnant women. [<https://v.douyin.com/iJMcS5Xv/>]

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Fig. 435. Real footage

Japanese military doctor Shinita was cruelly vivisecting a Chinese girl solely to satisfy his curiosity about the female reproductive system.

In 1938, the China-Japanese War broke out and the unit where Niida was stationed was deployed near Dingyuan Town, Anhui Province. They began brutal human dissection experiments on Chinese people. In order to understand the structure of a woman's lower body, they forcefully restrained this young girl on the operating table. After a cruel incision in her lower abdomen, blood gushed out, leaving her severely mutilated. Due to prolonged abuse and torture by the Japanese, the poor girl contracted

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a deadly disease and was left in a state of total devastation. Because of Niida's curiosity, this innocent girl lost her life. Individuals like Niida and the members of Unit 731 have completely crossed the moral bottom line. #NeverForgetHistory #NeverForgetNationalHatred #RememberHistory #JapaneseWarCrimes.
<https://v.douyin.com/iJMvsRWf/>

Fig. 436. The inhumane atrocities of evil Japanese [Remembering National Shame # Remembering History, Saluting Martyrs, Suppressing Intuition, and Looking Directly # Remembering National Shame # Remembering History, Saluting Martyrs.<https://v.douyin.com/iedvUSFx/>]

Memories of the Japanese Army's Invasion of China: Only Four People Express Remorse out of Over Two Hundred individuals.

https://www.360kuai.com/pc/9bdda58bff00278f4?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

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Fig. 454. Japanese war criminal Taiji Ohno directly or indirectly killed 654 Chinese, raped 14 women, and personally tortured the heroic Ms. Zhao Yiman. This is the confession of Taiji Ohno, a Japanese from Kochi Prefecture. In 1935, he invaded northeastern China as a member of the Foreign Affairs Division and the Police Department of the Puppet Manchukuo Black Dragon River Police Department. During the ten years of the invasion, he commanded the Japanese police and gendarmerie to carry out widespread killings and torture of the Chinese people, as well as innocent civilians and anti-Japanese people. **This demon had a disgusting habit of consuming the brain tissue of the Chinese people.**

[2023-08-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iLURJEc4/> B@t.rE EUy:/ 12/11]

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 463. During the Nanjing Massacre, two diabolical and **Evil Staphylococcus aureus**---Japanese officers (**Evil locust**) competed to see who could kill 100 people first. In this way innocent civilians were killed, and the Japanese (**Evil locust**) officer named Tomei killed 106 civilians in the end, while another Noda killed 105 civilians. The two even thought they didn't kill enough and wanted to expand the game to 150 people.[War can best unleash the evil of human nature, and the polite Japanese actually eat human flesh. December 25th, 2016; https://www.sohu.com/a/122558081_496562]

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Fig. 464. During the Nanjing Massacre, a dog trained by the invading Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese (Evil locust) army gnawed on the body of a Chinese civilian. [Don't forget that painful history <https://v.douyin.com/iXRvVbq/>] Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

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Fig. 488. General Liu Guiwu, the heroic anti-Japanese hero, was only 36 years old when he experienced his tragic death in battle. His head was brutalized and severed by Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese forces (Evil locust), and to this day, it remains on display in a diabolical and evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese exhibition hall for tourists to see.

On April 20, 1938, General Liu Guiwu led the 6th Cavalry Division to fight in the vicinity of Wuchuan. Due to continuous combat, the soldiers were exhausted, so they stayed overnight in Hongyougangzi Village. At dawn the next day, the entire village was surrounded by thousands of Japanese troops (Evil locust), who launched a fierce attack. More than 20 enemy aircraft dropped bombs from the sky, while over 60 armored vehicles launched an assault on the ground, turning the whole Hongyougangzi Village into a sea of fire. General Ma Zhanshan, commander of the Vanguard Forces, was seriously ill at the time. Upon hearing the sound of gunfire, he climbed onto the roof to command the troops to break out. General Liu Guiwu led the charge, launching

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the first attack on Japanese (**Evil locust**) armored vehicles, with the rest of the officers and soldiers of the 6th Cavalry Division closely behind. Japanese armoured vehicles fired their guns, but the 6th Cavalry Division charged forward despite intense shelling, resulting in heavy casualties. The soldiers broke into the ranks of the Japanese infantry behind armoured vehicles and vigorously attacked with their swords, cutting hundreds of Japanese soldiers (**Evil locust**) in half. The battle was extremely fierce, with hundreds of Japanese casualties in each charge, creating a bloody path. Liu Guiwu broke out of the encirclement, but found Ma Zhanshan still trapped inside. He rode back decisively to rescue him. However, Liu Guiwu was unfortunately hit by a shell during the operation, and to prevent his subordinates from sacrificing themselves needlessly to save him, he chose to drink a bullet and sacrifice himself for the country.

When Ma Zhanshan, who had broken out of the encirclement, heard that Liu Guiwu had died, he disregarded the danger and returned to the rear. He wept bitterly over Liu's body. Due to the urgent situation, he could only order his subordinates to temporarily bury the body in the nearby rocky bank. Shortly after, when they returned to retrieve the body, they found that the head had been cruelly severed by the Japanese. Just as the enemy was about to take away General Liu's body, Liu Shuzhen, the wife of General Liu Guiwu, a heroic woman, mounted a horse, wielding dual firearms, and charged towards the Japanese position. Despite the outnumbered situation, her bravery moved the soldiers of the 6th Cavalry Division, who took up arms and followed her in charge, eventually recovering the body of General Liu Guiwu! As the Japanese had hidden General Liu's severed head, they had to carve a wooden head to be buried with his body.

[The heads of anti-Japanese heroes whose heads were cut off by the Japanese army are still kept in the Japan Exhibition Hall to this day. <https://v.douyin.com/iCeLWrM/>],
[At the age of only 36, a famous anti Japanese general died in battle and his head was brutally cut off by the Japanese army. It is still on display in Japan today.
October 25th, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HKHSU5MC05378IX6.html>]

Warvigilance:

If Japan is not truly a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized country, how can it tolerate the fact that **General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?**

If Japan's emperor is not truly a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized leader of the yakuza, how can he tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If the Japanese people are not really a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized nation, how can they tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If the Japanese government is not really a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized government, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

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If Japan really regards the invasion of China during World War II and the massacre of tens of millions of Chinese people as a serious crime that requires acknowledgement and repentance, how can they tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of the Second World War and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If the Japanese nation is not really a people who do not love peace, how can they tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch?

If Japan is not really a country that does not love peace, how can it tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch?

If the Japanese emperor was not really a peaceless emperor, how could he tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still treating it as a trophy for tourists to watch?

If Japan is really not a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized country without proper religious beliefs or a cult nation, why would they still tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head since the end of World War II, and even display it as a war trophy for tourists to admire?

If the Japanese nation is really not a nation that believes in cults, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to observe?

If the Japanese emperor is really not a cult leader, how can he tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still being displayed as a trophy for tourists to see?

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Fig. 506. "Intestine Pulling" torture of the Japanese invaders(Evil locust). The savage and evil Japanese soldiers first use bayonets to open the person's anus, dig out the large intestine, and then make the person run forward while holding onto the large intestine, causing it to be stretched longer and longer. In the end, even the internal organs are torn out together, causing the person to suffer excruciating pain, resulting in death. [At that time in Nanjing, the human nature of the Japanese army had become extinct to an unbeatable extent. <https://v.douyin.com/iC1qe8y/>]

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

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Fig. 517. On April 21, 1938, at Zhangdian Station on the Jiaozhi Railway, Japanese immigrants from the Japan Defense Women's Association bid farewell to the Japanese army.

On April 21, 1938, at Zhangdian Station on the Jiaozhi Railway in China, Japanese overseas residents from the Japanese Defense Women's Association bid farewell to the Japanese military. [Preserved in the basement, photos taken by Japanese military reporters of the invasion of China. April 29, 2019; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/EDV8MLOH0516E3BK.html>]

Japanese expatriates are a great threat in the anti-War of aggression.

Can you quickly or slowly identify these Japanese from their appearance or facial features as war criminals and non-human nature?

Can you quickly or slowly recognize from the appearance or facial features of these Japanese people that they are murderers and non-human nature tomorrow?

When you put on suits and ties for them, can you recognize from their appearance or facial features that they are tomorrow murderers and evil non-human nature?

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Fig. 654. The Living Hands Frostbite Experiment of the Evil Japanese Army

Some Human frostbite experiments conducted by Japan's Unit 731 were conducted as follows:

A woman or child, guarded by Japanese soldiers, was forced to expose their forearms and hands outdoors in Harbin, China, where the temperature was dozens of degrees below zero. The Japanese soldiers kept pouring water on their arms, causing the water to freeze on the arms, and then knocked off the ice that had formed on the hands and arms. After a long time, the woman or child was taken indoors and forced to put their stiff frozen hands in hot water. Then, the Japanese soldiers put their hands on the woman or child's arms and yanked them down hard. All the skin and flesh on the woman or child's arms peeled off, and the pale hand bones were exposed.

[How Japan plundered China's wealth. February 26, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/224186891_100011719]

6. Southeast Asian Chinese Massacre: Overseas Chinese killed at least 500,000 by evil Japanese invaders

at least 5,000 households have disappeared, at least 100,000 women have been raped, at least 10,000 tons of gold, 10,000 tons of silver, 100 tons of natural diamonds, 10 million pieces of jewelry have been looted, and at least \$100-300 million has been extorted. A large number of factories and equipment were destroyed or looted to Japan.

7. Evil Japanese invaders massacre in Taiwan: 650,000 Victim

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8. Ryukyu Massacre: Japanese invaders **killed at least 360,000** indigenous people in Ryukyu.

[Japan's Jade Crush Plan alone massacred 360,000 people in Ryukyu
May 4, 2023. <https://www.163.com/v/video/VM2UAHASR.html>]

9. The partial biochemical warfare massacre carried out by the evil Japanese invaders in China

Biochemical warfare massacre carried out by the evil Japanese invaders in China
Huabei Bacterial Massacre (Bacterial Massacre in North China) : Evil Japanese in North China: Bacteriological Warfare Massacre At least 270,000 civilians killed(excluding military deaths), over 12 million people infected
Yunnan Bacterial Warfare Massacre launched by the world's most evil Japanese In 1942, the seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese launched a large-scale Bacterial Warfare Massacre in Yunnan , resulting in the death of at least 200,000-300,000 Chinese people . The exact number of victims is difficult to determine.
Lu Xi Bacterial Warfare Massacre launched by the world's most evil Japanese During the Lu Xi Bacterial Warfare Massacre carried out by the seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese, they killed at least 500,000 – 600,000 Chinese people , created a deserted area spanning 1,500 kilometers, and 24 counties becoming uninhabited areas.
Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre The Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the death of about 650,000 Chinese people.
Guangzhou Bacterial and Biochemical Massacre launched the world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese At least 100,000 - 300,000 Cantonese died tragically from 1938 to 1945
Bacterial Massacre in Coastal Counties of Guangdong Province At least 1 million deaths in various coastal counties.

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Pestis Massacre in Eastern Inner Mongolia in August 1945

From 1945 to 1948, the most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese in the world launched the pestis massacre, a total of 47,522 cases and **39,097 deaths** occurred in the eastern region of Inner Mongolia, affecting 18 counties.

Fig.220. Survivor of the bacterial warfare in Zhegan Bacterial Massacre
Victim of Japanese biological warfare: Mao Xiaowei, an 80-year-old man, has wounds that have not healed for 70 years, with his skin infested with countless maggots. There has been no cure for decades, and one of his legs has rotted away,

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leaving only one tendon.

The evil Japanese Army airdropped fleas infected with the plague virus in the city of Quzhou.

[World War II Japan # Remembering History and Remembering National Shame # Remembering History and Strengthening Our Generation # World Peace. <https://v.douyin.com/iJmvg5mp/>]

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig. 221. The invading Japanese army carried out bacterial warfare in Quzhou, and now the victims are all old and have passed away one after another.

[The 90th anniversary of the September 18th Incident. The invading Japanese army carried out bacterial warfare in Quzhou, and now the victims are all old and have passed away one after another. What else should we do# Don't forget national shame<https://v.douyin.com/iJuGeXt9/>]

Fig 109. No compensation

[Is this a civilized era? Is today's society a civilized society? Are the Japanese civilized or barbaric? Or are they despicable? The Japanese military used bacteria that caused people's feet to rot and become infested with maggots. **Wang Xuan has been suing Japan for 25 years on behalf of the victims.** 2022-11-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6Kk6aX/06/27B@t.RkgoD:/>]

ZheGan Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Biological Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig.797. **One of the tortures of the Japanese:** The Japanese will conduct frostbite experiments on newborn babies, and then conduct live dissection experiments on the babies.

A real photo of a baby being dissected alive by an evil and brutal Japanese

When the evil Japanese frostbite their newborn baby, it was unbearable. They froze the child's hands to death until they were lifeless. This is a real image of experimental scenes conducted by the Japanese army. Conducting live anatomy experiments on children shows a complete lack of humanity. ["Japanese people even carry out human experiments on newly born babies, it is truly inhumane and unforgivable!! #NeverForgetNationalHumiliation".<https://v.douyin.com/iYjs7W8/>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

What qualifications do we have to forgive the evil Japan for our ancestors?

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

Fig.798. **One of the tortures of the Japanese:** Evil Japanese Unit 731's real documentary records consist of dissecting live humans in experiments, removing their internal organs and creating specimens of the human body.

A real photo of a living Chinese being dissected by an evil and brutal Japanese army and the organs taken out to make a specimen

[The actual historical records of the Japanese Army Unit 731 are available for download. A man named Li Xingtian was subjected to live dissection by the Japanese invaders. Laboratory insider information serves as a reminder of history and the importance of not forgetting national humiliation. <https://v.douyin.com/iJYATaHB/>]

How far apart are the genes of Japanese individuals from those of hyenas and wolves?

Do the Japanese have a little bit of humanity?

Are Japanese people not human?

Are Japanese people human?

Seeing the cruel behavior of the Japanese, one instinctively asks: Are the Japanese really still a race of humans?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

What qualifications do we have to forgive the evil Japan for our ancestors?

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Fig.799. **One of the tortures of the Japanese:** Evil records of the notorious Japanese Unit 731 capturing live Chinese subjects for human dissection experiments. They would remove the organs of living individuals and turn them into human specimens. **A real photo of a living Chinese being dissected by an evil and brutal Japanese army and the organs taken out to make a specimen**

[The actual historical records of the Japanese Army Unit 731 are available for download. A man named Li Xingtian was subjected to live dissection by the Japanese invaders. Laboratory insider information serves as a reminder of history and the importance of not forgetting national humiliation. <https://v.douyin.com/iJYATaHB/>]

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Fig.800. **One of the tortures of the Japanese:** Chinese people who have been continuously bound and escorted by the evil Japanese army.

Evil Japanese Unit 731's real documentary records consist of dissecting live humans in experiments, removing their internal organs and creating specimens of the human body.

A real photo of a living Chinese being dissected by an evil and brutal Japanese army and the organs taken out to make a specimen

[The actual historical records of the Japanese Army Unit 731 are available for download. A man named Li Xingtian was subjected to live dissection by the Japanese invaders. Laboratory insider information serves as a reminder of history and the importance of not forgetting national humiliation. <https://v.douyin.com/iJYATaHB/>]

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Fig.810.An unscrupulous nation, with only a little chance, may retaliate or even kill the benefactor. **Continuously portraying snakes and farmers' snakes**

On February 3, 1946, which happened to be the second day of the Lunar New Year, the people of Tonghua were joyfully celebrating the first Spring Festival under the leadership of the Chinese People's Government after the victory of the Anti-Japanese War.

Unfortunately, the Chinese people were too kind-hearted and treated a large number of Japanese soldiers and doctors and nurses who had participated in the war well. They surprisingly did not subject them to strict criminal investigations and even provided them with job opportunities. As a result, at one fateful moment that night, 150 Chinese soldiers were brutally murdered by Japanese female nurses using surgical knives and scissors in hospital beds.

Do you have the ability to recognize that these Japanese nurses with smooth faces could be extremely cruel criminal killers? If you don't have the ability, why are you so kind to criminals? Isn't that an injury to the victims? Where are your values? Where is your belief? Aren't you also a murderer and a criminal?

[Why can some ethnic groups never be forgiven? Remembering History # Forgetting

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National Shame <https://v.douyin.com/iJUGqCJu/>

Fig. 85-23-19. **Survivor of the bacterial warfare in Zhegan Bacterial Massacre**
Lawyer Ms. Wang Xuan quit her job with an annual salary of CNY 500,000 to force Japan to acknowledge and apologize for their use of bacteriological warfare, exhausting all her savings over 25 years and taking Japan to court 29 times. It forced Japan to acknowledge and apologize, and to include this history in textbooks.

[She is a woman who makes the Japanese itch with hatred. In order to make Japan apologize, she spent all her savings over 25 years and sued Japan 29 times, finally forcing Japan to recognize the use of biological warfare and include it in textbooks.

Salute to the heroine Wang Xuan. <https://v.douyin.com/iJaHUuQ9/>

ZheGan Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Biological Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

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Fig. 85-23-20.

Lawyer Ms. Wang Xuan quit her job with an annual salary of CNY 500,000 to force Japan to acknowledge and apologize for their use of bacteriological warfare, exhausting all her savings over 25 years and taking Japan to court 29 times. It forced Japan to acknowledge and apologize, and to include this history in textbooks.

[She is a woman who makes the Japanese itch with hatred. In order to make Japan apologize, she spent all her savings over 25 years and sued Japan 29 times, finally forcing Japan to recognize the use of biological warfare and include it in textbooks. Salute to the heroine Wang Xuan. <https://v.douyin.com/iJaHUuQ9/1>

[Isn't the current international legal system hindering justice and protecting crime? Don't these ugly regulations need to be amended immediately?](#)

[ZheGan Massacre, at Least killed 650,000](#)

[ZheGan Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000](#)

[ZheGan Biological Massacre, at Least killed 650,000](#)

[Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000](#)

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Table S6. Questioning the makers of the judicial system and politicians:	
1	Is Japan really a peace-loving country?
2	Are the Japanese really honest?
3	Are the Japanese really kind?
4	Do the Japanese really have a conscience?
5	Is Japan really a country that wants peace?
6	<p>Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the death of about 650,000 Chinese people.</p> <p>If Japan and the Japanese are really such, it is an obvious fact that the Japanese invaders carried out biochemical warfare of bacteria and viruses to massacre the Chinese people.</p> <p>On August 27, 2002, after 27 court hearings, the Tokyo District Court of Japan announced that lawyer Wang Xuan and the plaintiffs of the bacterial warfare of the Japanese invaders in China lost the lawsuit. From the first session of the Court in 1998 to 2006, it has been eight years. After eight years of litigation and more than 40 court sessions, some media commented on Wang Xuan in this way: Another eight-year war of resistance. The eight-year war of resistance that took place 60 years ago won victory, while the eight-year war of resistance in 2006 still sees no end. On July 19, 2006, lawyer Wang Xuan and members of the bacterial warfare plaintiff group once again heard the result of losing the lawsuit in the courtroom of the Tokyo District Court of Japan.</p> <p>Why did the Japanese government admit that it had carried out bacterial biochemical warfare in China only after being sued 29 times from the 20th to the 21st century, and that these people were victims of biochemical warfare? However, the evil Japanese government refused to pay any compensation to the victims.</p>
7	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue a group of criminals in the criminal country?
8	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue the criminal country in the criminal country?
9	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue the criminal country in the criminal country? Can victims get fair and just results?
10	<p>Is the maker of such ugly and evil laws and rules a pig? A stupid pig?</p> <p>If the maker is a stupid pig, what qualifications do he has to make laws and rules? If he takes bribes to make such ugly and evil laws and rules, and the evil Japanese invaders killed at least 51.80–89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, why can't the evil criminals be exterminated?</p> <p>The reason why Chinese civilization has endured for a long time is that criminals are severely punished by special means in special circumstances.</p>
11	If the maker of such ugly and evil rules appeared in ancient China, it is estimated

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	that his nine clans would be exterminated and all personal and family property would be confiscated.
12	If the judicial officials responsible for matters related to cracking down on criminals at the United Nations are unable to restrain heinous crimes, should they not be removed from their positions?
13	<p>Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the death of about 650,000 Chinese people.</p> <p>On August 27, 2002, after 27 court hearings, the Tokyo District Court of Japan announced that lawyer Wang Xuan and the plaintiffs of the bacterial warfare of the Japanese invaders in China lost the lawsuit. From the first session of the Court in 1998 to 2006, it has been eight years. After eight years of litigation and more than 40 court sessions, some media commented on Wang Xuan in this way: Another eight-year war of resistance. The eight-year war of resistance that took place 60 years ago won victory, while the eight-year war of resistance in 2006 still sees no end. On July 19, 2006, lawyer Wang Xuan and members of the bacterial warfare plaintiff group once again heard the result of losing the lawsuit in the courtroom of the Tokyo District Court of Japan.</p> <p>If Japan and the Japanese are such, it is an obvious fact that the Japanese invaders carried out biochemical warfare of bacteria and viruses to massacre the Chinese people.</p> <p>Why did the Japanese government admit that it had carried out bacterial biochemical warfare in China only after being <u>sued 29 times from the 20th to the 21st century,</u> and that these people were victims of biochemical warfare? However, the evil Japanese government refused to pay any compensation to the victims.</p> <p>You can believe that dogs don't defecate, but you must never believe that Japan is kind, and you must never believe that Japan wants world peace.</p>

	Table S7. International consensus and United Nations conventions that must be established
1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p>

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	<p>Since 1900, any criminal state or nation of war criminals that has committed crimes involving mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, trafficking in human beings, harvesting of live organs, massacres including biowarfare, as covered by the Consensus, will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next 10,000 years. Moreover, if such a war criminal State, having committed any of the aforementioned crimes against the public of another nation since 1900, has not so far provided full compensation for the losses of the victims and killed all criminals, it will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next ten thousand years.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Immigration to other countries is a latent means and tool for evil countries without conscience and empathy or countries with criminal records to commit crimes, invade, plunder wealth and annex the territory of other countries. It is an important factor leading to an increase in crime rates. It is the basis for evil countries to carry out long-term evil plans under the slogan of freedom and human rights. Farmers in China's three northeastern provinces were once deeply harmed and plundered by Japanese immigrants.</p> <p>The number of immigrants from the evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this article in any other country is prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of deaths in Nanjing during the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. Those who have immigrated must be repatriated to the criminal country.</p>
3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world</p>

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	<p>civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of 10 million people and plundering over 100 billion US dollars worth of wealth (calculated at the value of all goods or cultural artifacts in 2023 US dollars), will be prohibited from establishing any military schools, academies, or universities for the next 3000 years unless the evil country fully compensates the victimized countries and victims or their relatives and returns the plundered wealth. All military schools, academies, colleges, or universities operated by an evil country must be shut down within one year. In addition, any person from an evil country or their descendants will be prohibited from studying military subjects in any third country.</p>
4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of 10 million people and plundering over 100 billion US dollars worth of wealth (calculated at the value of all goods or cultural artifacts in 2023 US dollars), will be prohibited to have any military or self-defense forces for the next 3000 years, and only police officers who maintain social order will be allowed. The army of the victimized country can be stationed or enter anywhere in the criminal country or war criminal country at any time. All expenses shall be borne by the criminal country or war criminal country.</p>
5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries or their descendants or their overseas</p>

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	<p>descendants, causing the deaths of 200,000 people, will be prohibited from establishing any military schools, academies, or universities for the next 2000 years unless the evil country fully compensates the victimized countries and victims or their relatives and returns the plundered wealth. All military schools, academies, colleges, or universities operated by an evil country must be shut down within one year. In addition, any person from an evil country or their descendants will be prohibited from studying military subjects in any third country.</p>
6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries or their descendants or their overseas descendants, causing the deaths of 200,000 people, will be prohibited to have any military or self-defense forces for the next 2000 years, and only police officers who maintain social order will be allowed. The army of the victimized country can be stationed or enter anywhere in the criminal country or war criminal country at any time. All expenses shall be borne by the criminal country or war criminal country.</p>
7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If the officials responsible for peace at the United Nations were just a group of thoughtless and incompetent officials who can only receive salaries, that was a waste of taxpayers' wealth and they must be dismissed and punished immediately.</p>
8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of</p>

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	<p>China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If the officials responsible for peace at the United Nations were just a group of thoughtless and incompetent officials who can only receive salaries, that was a waste of taxpayers' wealth and they must be dismissed and punished immediately.</p> <p>For the victims covered by this article, as long as the State which committed the crime and/or the State which committed the war crime does not make full reparation to the victims and the victimized country, the victimized country can refuse to pay its dues to the United Nations.</p> <p>The United Nations must impose fines on criminal countries and war criminal countries such as Japan, Myanmar, Vietnam, and Indonesia according to the number of victims and property losses to offset China's dues to the United Nations.</p>
9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>In order to maintain world peace, it is necessary to establish a United Nations convention prohibiting any country from transferring weapons production lines and weapons technology to other nations.</p>
10	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>It is necessary to prohibit war criminal countries or criminal countries that have committed large-scale crimes since 1900 from providing any weapons to other countries or transferring any weapons manufacturing technology to other countries.</p>
11	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-</p>

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	<p>term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For all the criminal countries and war criminal countries that have committed the large-scale crimes referred to in this article, as long as they have not fully compensated the victims and the victimized countries, when the United Nations holds a meeting, a special group of seats for criminal countries must be set up, and only representatives of those evil countries should be confined to those seats.</p>
12	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>All criminal countries and war criminal States that have committed the crimes referred to in this article on a large scale since 1900 shall be prohibited from providing loans to any State, institution, bank or individual to criminal States, war criminal States, their companies or individuals as long as they have not made full reparation to the victims.</p>
13	<p>The international community and the United Nations should form the following conventions on the control of war criminal countries and criminal countries as mentioned above, and amend the constitutions of various countries.</p>

10. All Toyota's production lines, assets, and workers were plundered and hijacked from China.

All the assets, automotive production lines and technical staff of Toyota of Japan were obtained when the evil Japanese invaders occupied the Shenyang Automobile Factory in China and plundered all the assets of the factory. The Japanese invaders plundered huge resources and wealth from China. Japan's wealth basically came from its evil and dirty plundering from China. The Japanese invaders obtained huge investment returns in the subsequent average of 85 years.

Do you hope to establish the rule that your soul is suppressed by Japan under the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls" or [the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字塔)]? Do you hope to establish the rule that your national fortune is suppressed by Japan under the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls" or [the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一

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字塔]]? Do you hope to establish the rule that your wealth is being plundered by Japan?

日本的八纮一字镇魂塔
至今还镇压着来自中国的238块石头
八纮一字统治天下 镇压中国抗战不得翻身
狼子野心 其心可诛

Fig.811. The Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字) (unite the whole world under one sovereign by force of arms) (Also known as"Tower of Suppressing Souls")

The Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字) (Also known as"Tower of Suppressing Souls"), built in Japan in 1940, proves their ambitions. After Japan's surrender, the U.S. military forced Japan to demolish various evil buildings. The Japanese people changed the name of the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字), which had the inscription of the Unified Universe (八纮一字) (meaning: unite the whole world under one sovereign by force of arms; or "all the world under one roof"), to the "Gentle Tower"and dismantled the Statue of the Ala mitam, deceiving the American forces. However, in 1962, the Ala mitama statue was rebuilt, and Japan changed the name of the tower back to " Unified Universe " again. This name means that the whole world is under the rule of Japan. From the China-Japanese War to World War II, " Unified Universe " served as the national motto of the Great Japanese Empire. This was a national strategy established by the Japanese emperor more than a thousand years ago. The term is closely associated with State Shinto, militarism, and extreme nationalism. The explanation in the World Encyclopedia states, "Based on a sense of

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ethnic superiority, it belittles and annexes other ethnic groups. **Japan attempted to use this tower to suppress all countries worldwide from a feng shui (geomancy or geomantic omen) perspective.**" It is ironic that the 1964 Tokyo Olympics torch relay started at this location in Miyazaki City. Perhaps on that day, Japan provided enough evil and powerful spring spirit to launch another aggressive war.

The tower has an extremely dark feng shui structure layout.

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJUnhMc9/>],

[the Unified Universe Tower(八纒一字塔)..<https://baike.so.com/doc/522909-553588.html>]

This evil tower ("**Tower of Suppressing Souls**") has a very peculiar design, with its foundation built on top of spirit stones looted or stolen from various countries around the world. These spiritual stones were used to suppress the fortunes of other nations, as Japan sought to completely dominate Asia and eventually rule the world. **Publicly known instances of looting and stealing spirit stones include those from China, Korea, Singapore, the United States, Canada, Germany, Peru, the Philippines, and Russia. Despite Germany being a friendly country and ally of Japan at the time, Japan still sought to suppress Germany's fortunes.** The United States encountered many crises after World War II, which may be related to Japan using this tower to suppress the fortunes of the United States.

If the Japanese really wanted world peace, they would have destroyed these evil towers long ago. On the contrary, every year countless Japanese come here to worship Japanese war criminals and secretly make wishes to conquer Asia and the world.

After World War II, Japan surprisingly became an ally of the United States. Japan is good at secretly harming its allies. By fabricating the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan has made the United States continuously produce more than 10,000 useless nuclear weapons, costing at least \$7.2 trillion. During that period, total military expenditure exceeded \$22 trillion. Since then, the U.S. economy has been on the wrong track. While enjoying the help of the United States, Japan has never told its ally that the United States has made huge mistakes in investment directions. If these funds were used to improve the living standards of the American people, Americans would enjoy free medical care for decades. The United States could build 100,000 kilometers of high - speed railways, creating a human record in the history of high - speed railway. And the 12,000 nuclear weapons can only be decommissioned at a cost.

Warvigilance:

Table 26. 110-World First Records for the Evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls"

1	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls "[the Unified Universe Tower(八纒一字塔)] to suppress the souls of other countries.
2	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to

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	suppress the national luck of other countries.
3	During World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and evil techniques to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the souls of other countries.
4	During World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and evil techniques to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the destiny of other countries.
5	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress China's soul.
6	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress China's national luck.
7	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the American soul.
8	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of the United States.
9	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Canada.
10	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Canada's national luck.
11	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the German soul.
12	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Germany's national luck.
13	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Singapore.
14	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Singapore's national luck.
15	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the Russian soul.
16	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Russia's national luck.
17	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of South Korea.
18	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of South Korea.
19	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of North Korea.
20	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of North Korea.
21	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Peru.
22	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Peru's national luck.

Human beings should re-examine their own IQs and or kindness. The number of people with a university education today is several times that of 1945. Why have people been constantly deceived by such inferior fraud techniques for 79 years?

23	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of the Philippines.
24	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of the Philippines.
25	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized the theft and plunder of spiritual stones from China to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Chinese spirit.
26	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized the theft and plunder of spiritual stones from China to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of China.
27	In World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of China, with the intention of preventing the Chinese people from ever rising again. China has always demanded that Japan dismantle the tower, but Japan has refused to do so.
28	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the Yellow Crane Tower in Wuhan, China, to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
29	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the peak of Mount Tai in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
30	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the Ming Palace of the Ming Dynasty in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
31	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen bricks from the Great Wall of China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
32	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the Zhongshan Mausoleum in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
33	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from the United States through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the American spirit.
34	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from the United States through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of America.
35	In World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of the U.S., with the intention of preventing the American people from ever rising again.
36	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Canada through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Canadian spirit.
37	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from

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	Canada through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Canada.
38	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Germany through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the German spirit.
39	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Germany through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Germany.
40	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Singapore through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Singaporean spirit.
41	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Singapore through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Singapore.
42	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from Russia to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Russian spirit.
43	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from Russia to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Russia.
44	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from South Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the South Korean spirit.
45	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from South Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of South Korea.
46	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the North Korean spirit.
47	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of North Korea.
48	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Peruvian spirit.
49	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Peru.
50	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Philippines.
51	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to

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	oppress the destiny of the Philippines.
52	During World War II, the first evil country to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the spirits of other nations and issue ten-yuan commemorative currency in honor of the tower was Japan.
53	During World War II, the first evil country to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of other nations and issue ten-yuan commemorative currency in honor of the tower was Japan.
54	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the souls of other countries.
55	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of other countries.
56	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress China's soul.
57	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress China's national fortunes.
58	In modern history, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress destiny of other countries.
59	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the American soul.
60	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of the United States.
61	In modern history, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of the United States.
62	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Canadian soul.
63	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Canada's national fortunes.
64	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the German soul.
65	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the German national fortunes.
66	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of Singapore.
67	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Singapore's national fortunes.
68	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Russian soul.
69	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Russian national fortunes.
70	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of South Korea.
71	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing

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	Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of South Korea.
72	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of North Korea.
73	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Korean national fortunes.
74	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of Peru.
75	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Peru's national fortunes.
76	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of the Philippines.
77	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Philippine national fortunes.
78	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Chinese spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Chinese soul.
79	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Chinese spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress China's national fortunes.
80	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain American spirit stones in a special way and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of the United States The United States is constantly encountering treasury bond crisis and economic crisis. Is the national fortunes suppressed by the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls"?
81	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain American spirit stones in a special way and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress American national fortunes.
82	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Canadian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of Canada.
83	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Canadian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Canada's national fortunes.
84	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain German spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the German soul.
85	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain German spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Germany's national fortunes.
86	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Singapore's spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Singapore's soul.

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87	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Singapore's spirit stones through special means and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Singapore's national fortunes.
88	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Russian spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Russian souls.
89	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Russian spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Russia's national fortunes.
90	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Korean souls.
91	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Korean national fortunes.
92	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of North Korea
93	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a soul tower in an attempt to suppress North Korea's national fortunes.
94	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Peruvian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Peruvian souls
95	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Peruvian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Peruvian national fortunes
96	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Philippine spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress the soul of the Philippines
97	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Philippine spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress the Philippine national fortunes.
98	In modern history, the first country to build a Soul Suppression Tower in an attempt to suppress the souls of other countries was evil Japan, and the Japanese bank also issued a ten-yen currency to commemorate the Tower.
99	In modern history, the first country to build a Soul Suppression Tower in an attempt to suppress the fortunes of other nations was evil Japan, and the Japanese bank also issued a ten-yen currency to commemorate the Tower.
100	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of China.
101	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of the United States.

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102	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Canada's destiny.
103	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Germany's destiny.
104	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Australia's destiny.
105	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Singapore's destiny.
106	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of Russia.
107	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Korea's destiny.
108	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of Peru.
109	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of the Philippines.
110	In modern history, the first country to erect a soul-suppressing tower that aimed to conquer the world and suppress the destiny of other nations, deceived the global public by calling it the Tower of Peace, and transformed it into the starting point for the Olympic torchbearer symbolizing peace. However, shortly after the Olympic Games ended, the country reverted the tower's name back to its evil original name.

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Fig 181. A baby pierced by an evil Japanese bayonet. [2023-12-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAGQyRm/06/08D@h.oDlpQ:/>]

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

11. Japan's military power has returned to the top five in the world

Japan's military power has returned to the top five in the world, with more than **five stealth aircraft carriers** and a large number of fifth-generation fighter jets. Japan already has over 1400 advanced combat aircraft.

The Japanese have spent a lot of money to purchase 42 F-35B vertical takeoff and landing models (and another 105 F-35A basic models) from the United States, attempting to build a modern version of the Japanese Maritime Self-Defense Force's carrier-based aviation force. **Its aircraft carriers, Izumo and Kaga, have a full-load displacement of more than 27,000 tons**, and are the largest combat vessels ever built by the Japan Maritime Self-Defense Force. They are fully capable of taking off and landing F-35Bs. As early as October 3, 2021, Japan "invited" the F-35B short takeoff and vertical landing fighter jets of the US Marine Corps to conduct take-off and landing tests on the Izumo. Test results showed that the Izumo was fully capable of operating the F-35B.

12. After the evil Japan announced its surrender on August 15, 1945, it still secretly plundered children from China to Japan as meat or blood offerings.

In May 1945, the Japanese army entered an extremely passive situation, and the cousin of the Japanese Emperor suggested that in response to the serious food crisis, strong and healthy Chinese children should be used as food. For this reason, various Japanese military departments should kidnap children under the age of 12 in China and transport them to Japan for blood collection, soldiers, and food. Even after evil Japan announced its surrender on August 15, 1945, it still secretly plundered children from China to Japan as food or blood offerings. With the exception of some of the children who were intercepted, the whereabouts of the rest are unknown.

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Fig 231-2. In May 1945, the Japanese army entered an extremely passive situation, and the cousin of the Japanese Emperor suggested that in response to the serious food crisis, **strong and healthy Chinese children should be used as food.** For this reason, **various Japanese military departments should kidnap children under the age of 12 in China and transport them to Japan for blood collection, soldiers, and food.**

[A terrifying page in the Japanese military archives: The Japanese enjoy eating and their cruel behavior is outrageous2023-01-17. http://www.360doc.com/content/23/0117/17/9305059_1064008699.shtml#google_vignette]

13. During the War of Resistance against Japanese Aggression, in retaliation for Chinese civilians rescuing 64 American pilots, evil and ferocious Japanese invaders massacred 250,000 Chinese people using means including chemical weapons.

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Fig. 210. All members of the **James Harold Doolittle crew** have been rescued. [During the Anti-Japanese War, the Chinese military and civilians sacrificed 250,000 people only to save 64 American pilots. August 15, 2018. <https://mil.news.sina.com.cn/history/2018-08-15/doc-ihhtfwqr6266596.shtml>]

Fig. 211. **Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II.** February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

Why doesn't Hollywood make a blockbuster film about the unprecedented feat of

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sacrificing 250,000 people to save 64 American pilots?

Fig. 212. Chinese military and civilians provide international assistance to 64 US pilots.

To rescue the 64 U.S. crew members of the 13 planes led by Doolittle, 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians sacrificed their lives. This ratio of tremendous sacrifice to success is unprecedented in world history. It is hoped that Hollywood will turn these challenging rescue operations into a movie. With a talented director and enough funding, it could surely become an extraordinarily thrilling and successful blockbuster, potentially reaching unrivaled viewership ratings.

[Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

Why doesn't Hollywood make a blockbuster film about the unprecedented feat of sacrificing 250,000 people to save 64 American pilots?

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process, it is estimated that the sales in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will

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enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard-won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund.

Fig. 213. President Roosevelt personally presented the Honorary Medal to Doolittle [Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

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Fig. 214. The Propaganda of the Zhejiang Jiangxi Campaign in Japanese Newspapers. [Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to **save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process**, it is estimated that the sales in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund.

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Fig. 215. U.S. reports on Japanese military executing U.S. pilots:

Two other aircraft unfortunately crashed in Japanese-controlled areas, resulting in the deaths of two pilots and the capture of eight other crew members who suffered severe abuse. The Japanese military sentenced five of them to life imprisonment (one of whom later died of illness, and the remaining four were rescued after the war), while the other three were executed by firing squad.

[Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II.

February 8, 2018.

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process, it is estimated that the sales in China alone will exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard -

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won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund.

Fig. 216. After the war, members of the air raid team established the "Durit Association" in the U.S.

[Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018.

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process, it is estimated that the sales in China alone would exceed about CNY 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). This will enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund.

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Fig. 217. For the 50th and 70th anniversaries, the Doolittle Association invited the Chinese people who rescued them to participate in the events.

[In order to save 64 Americans, the Chinese have attracted Japan's crazy retaliation, with 250,000 soldiers and civilians sacrificed. June 21, 2017. <https://www.toutiao.com/article/6433939830006088194/>]

14. Singapore Massacre: Killed at least 170,000

The evil Japanese army openly eliminated and massacred people in Singapore who met the following nine criteria:

Please consider: out of the nine criteria set by the evil Japanese in the Singapore Massacre, which one would result in the killing of you, your family, and your friends?

Currently, Japanese people have control a large amount of Brazil's land, covering an area of one million square kilometers, which is three times the size of Japan itself. There has been constant mention online about Brazil being a target in Japan's planned annexation. If Japan were to implement their strategy of "[the Unified Universe]" the unification of the world under Japanese rule, would Brazilian football stars such as Neymar, Alves, Richarlison, Ronaldo, Ronaldinho, and others with tattoos be massacred by the Japanese?

When Japan achieves world domination, would famous tattooed football stars like Messi, Beckham, Ramos, Ibrahimovic, Cannavaro, Valverde, Griezmann, Insigne, Di Maria, Marcelo, Courtois, Rashford, Gana Cho, Simeone, Phil Foden, Ederson, renowned coach Mourinho, famous players James, Curry, Irving, Jordan, McGrady, Durant, Iverson, Mourning, Wade, Kuzma, Gordon, Garnett, Davis, Leonard, tennis star Alcaraz, be massacred by the Japanese?

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Have you ever generously donated to relief funds? If so, would you also be massacred and have your wealth plundered?

Government officials and those who might sympathize with the English would be massacred, and their wealth seized.

Anyone who possesses weapons and attempts to disrupt public order would also be massacred.

	In the Singapore Massacre, the Japanese military stipulated that the following nine categories of people must be killed. (At that time there were approximately over 700,000 Chinese people)
1	Individuals who were actively involved in the Nanyang Overseas Chinese Relief Association.
2	Wealthy individuals who generously donated to the relief association.
3	Followers of Lim Boon Keng, the leader of the Nanyang Chinese National Salvation Movement.
4	Hainanese people.
5	Chinese-born individuals who arrived in Malaya after the China-Japanese War, who were either considered to have participated in the resistance against Japan or had fled China due to their aversion to Japanese aggression and conscription.
6	Males with tattoos.
7	Individuals who assisted the British army as members of the volunteer force against the Japanese.
8	Government officials and individuals who may have pro-British sentiments.
9	Individuals who possessed weapons and attempted to disturb public order.

Please ask lawyers from the United States and Europe to estimate how much compensation the Japanese invaders should pay for killing at least 500,000 Chinese people and looting huge amounts of wealth in Singapore and Malaysia. It is time to seek justice through legal means and reduce the likelihood of future wars. It is also an opportunity to create legitimate wealth - gaining opportunities for people from all sectors of the international community through just claims.

15. Jinan Massacre: The most evil, cruel, anti-human and adept at pretending to be civilized Japan in modern history created more than 90 world records of atrocities in the JiNan Massacre.

Jinan Massacre: **17,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians, with over 2,000 people injured and an additional 5,000 people taken as prisoners. Many of the captured soldiers were killed, and the total number of casualties exceeded 20,000. Residents suffered losses of at least 29.57 million silver yuan, with over 5,000 ancient buildings and houses damaged or destroyed.**

On April 19, 1928, the Tanaka Cabinet of Japan dispatched over 5000 Japanese troops from the 6th Division to forcibly land in Qingdao under the pretext of "protecting Japanese nationals on the spot", causing a shocking "Jinan Massacre"

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both domestically and internationally.

The Jinan Massacre

On May 3, 1928, a group of Japanese broke into the Jinan Consulate General and vandalized it by force. Cai Gongshi, the head of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, stepped forward to stop them, but was cruelly killed by the Japanese invaders, who mutilated his nose, cut off his ears, and gouged out his eyes. Sixteen other diplomats were also brutally murdered. Before sacrificing himself, Cai Gongshi shouted, "Chinese people can be killed, but not humiliated." The "May 3 Massacre" was a massacre by Japanese invaders throughout the city, resulting in the death of over 17,000 Chinese people. Chinese government envoys sent for negotiations were also gunned down, which aroused great indignation among the Chinese people and condemnation from international public opinion.

"The Jinan Massacre" caused nationwide anger and resulted in the deaths of 17,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians, with over 2,000 people injured and an additional 5,000 people taken as prisoners. Many of the captured soldiers were killed, and the total number of casualties exceeded 20,000. Residents suffered losses of at least 29.57 million silver yuan, with over 5,000 ancient buildings and houses damaged or destroyed.

After the Japanese army entered Jinan, they immediately carried out a crazed massacre. Japanese army staff issued an extremely bloody standard, and **anyone who met any of the following 18 criteria was mercilessly killed:**

- 1. Those with flat or student-style hairstyles;**
- 2. Women with short haircuts;**
- 3. Those wearing straw sandals;**
- 4. Those with a belt;**
- 5. Those wearing gray clothing;**
- 6. Those with business cards indicating a Southern origin;**
- 7. Those who are afraid upon seeing them;**
- 8. Those in possession of central banknotes;**
- 9. Those who open the door slightly late during inspections;**
- 10. Those with self-defense firearms;**
- 11. Those wearing commemorative coins of the founding of the country;**
- 12. Those with military supplies at home;**
- 13. Those wearing leather shoes;**
- 14. Those with a Southern accent;**
- 15. Those carrying a camera;**
- 16. Those with gold teeth;**
- 17. Youth with student-style appearances;**
- 18. Those with flags or Nationalist Party books at home.**

Please consider: **out of the 18 criteria set by the evil Japanese in the Jinan Massacre, which one would result in the killing of you, your family, and your friends?**

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The most evil, cruel, anti-human and adept at pretending to be civilized Japan in modern history created more than 90 world records of atrocities in the JiNan Massacre.

In the history of modern world diplomacy, for the first time, 17 diplomatic personnel had their ears and noses cut off, their eyes gouged, their clothes stripped and then mercilessly beaten with whips and stabbed and hacked with bayonets. They were subjected to extreme cruelty, humiliated in every way, and then massacred in batches by machine gun fire inside the consulate premises, resulting in a great tragedy.

For the first time in modern diplomatic history, 17 diplomats had their ears and noses cut off and their eyes gouged out. They were then brutally killed by the most evil, cruel, savage, greedy, shameless, hypocritical, despicable, anti-human, adept at pretending to be polite, adept at pretending to be civilized, adept at looting, adept at stealing, and adept at concealing their true intentions, Japan, which currently holds the title for committing the most atrocious acts.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone wearing pants with a belt would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone in possession of a belt would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone wearing gray clothing would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone in possession of gray clothing would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone in possession of military supplies would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone wearing straw sandals would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first tragic event occurred when anyone with a buzz cut or student-style haircut would be killed.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where any woman who cut her hair would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone wearing leather shoes would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone carrying a camera would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

In modern world history, the first massacre occurred where anyone with gold teeth would be killed by the most evil Japanese.

The Jinan Massacre occurred in May 1928 and was a heinous crime committed by the Japanese, who were responsible for armed aggression in violation of the laws of war and humanitarian principles. The massacre of Chinese soldiers and civilians by the Japanese military in Jinan began on May 3 and is also known as the "5-3 Massacre."

However, the Japanese atrocities in Jinan actually started before May 3rd. On May 1st, the Japanese military inexplicably murdered starving refugees Song Guangzhan

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and resident Li Qinghai. On the morning of May 2, Wei Yunbin, a propaganda officer of the National Revolutionary Army, was wounded by the Japanese military and died shortly after in the hospital. Around 10 p.m., two Japanese soldiers brutally assaulted and killed Huang Yonglan, a female teacher at Merchant Port Primary School. Shortly after, the hands of a female shopkeeper were chopped off by the Japanese military. Almost simultaneously, several officers and soldiers of the National Revolutionary Army's Liu Zhi unit were stabbed to death by the Japanese military, and even their bodies were taken away by the Japanese.

By May 3, when Chiang Kai-shek was still at the headquarters listening to the Japanese praise the discipline of the National Revolutionary Army, the Japanese were preparing to launch an attack. The Japanese deployed five infantry battalions, one cavalry squadron, two artillery companies, one engineer company, and two armoured cars, totaling 3,354 troops for the 5-3 massacre. In addition, Japanese spies and overseas Chinese volunteer groups in Jinan also cooperated directly in the massacre.

According to investigations conducted by organizations like Jinan Red Cross, at that time, all Japanese soldiers, regardless of whether they encountered Chinese military or civilian personnel, would shoot and kill them. Corpses littered the streets of Jinan, with casualties including children, women, workers, vendors, students, and soldiers. After 10 o'clock, the Japanese military began shelling. Countless commercial buildings were blown up and burned down in no time.

Japanese overseas Chinese, with members of the local militia as their core, directly participated in this massacre. They conducted large-scale searches in various parts of Jinan, arresting and torturing Nationalist soldiers who were forced to take refuge, looting Chinese shops, pounding defenseless residential areas, indiscriminately killing Chinese residents, raping and killing women, and humiliating and torturing prisoners of war. Photos released by the Japanese themselves also confirmed that prisoners of war were bound with ropes and paraded through the streets while being insulted. The Japanese disregarded international norms and freely looted, destroyed Chinese diplomatic agencies, kidnapped, insulted, and killed Chinese diplomats. Even Huang Fu, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Nanjing government who participated in negotiations with Japan, followed, and his residence was surrounded. The Japanese forcibly entered his office building and conducted searches.

Cai Gongshi, director of the Diplomatic Department of the Shandong Negotiation Mission, and all 18 staff members in his office were forcibly bound and brutally humiliated by the Japanese. When Cai Gongshi proposed to negotiate with the Japanese Consul in Jinan, the Japanese cut off the ears and noses of Cai Gongshi and the others, stripped them naked, and subjected them to extreme brutal torture. In the end, except for one person who managed to escape, the remaining 17 people were all brutally killed by the Japanese.

Faced with these atrocities, the Japanese aggressors used their typical tactic of distorting the truth, falsely accusing others, and attempting to deceive public opinion.

They fabricated stories claiming that "immediately after the Southern Army occupied Jinan, some of its ill-intentioned soldiers spread propaganda leaflets in the

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city, plastered slogans on doors, electric poles, walls, and other places, with words such as 'down with imperialism' and even 'kill all Japanese.'

[<https://www.toutiao.com/article/6260622486506553602/>]

16. After World War II, records of Japanese political figures visiting Yasukuni Shrine

Fig. 231-24. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits.

<https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

Warvigilance:

After World War II, records of Japanese political figures visiting Yasukuni Shrine

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(August 18, 1945 - April 23, 2007)

The following records are incomplete:

- August 18, 1945: Prime Minister Prince Higashikuni Naruhiko visited Yasukuni Shrine on his second day in office as Prime Minister (visited once as Prime Minister).
- October 23, 1945: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the first time since becoming Prime Minister (visited twice as Prime Minister).
- November 20, 1945: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the second time since becoming Prime Minister (visited twice as Prime Minister).
- October 18, 1951: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the first time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- October 17, 1952: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the second time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- April 23, 1953: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the third time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- October 24, 1953: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the fourth time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- April 24, 1954: Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida visited for the fifth time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- April 24, 1957: Prime Minister Nobusuke Kishi visited for the first time (visited twice as Prime Minister).
- October 21, 1958: Prime Minister Nobusuke Kishi visited for the second time (visited twice as Prime Minister).
- October 10, 1960: Prime Minister Hayato Ikeda visited for the first time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- June 18, 1961: Prime Minister Hayato Ikeda visited for the second time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- November 15, 1961: Prime Minister Hayato Ikeda visited for the third time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- November 4, 1962: Prime Minister Hayato Ikeda visited for the fourth time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- September 22, 1963: Prime Minister Hayato Ikeda visited for the fifth time (visited five times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1965: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the first time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1966: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the second time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).
- April 22, 1967: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the third time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).
- April 23, 1968: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the fourth time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).
- April 22, 1969: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the fifth time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).
- October 18, 1969: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the sixth time (visited

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eleven times as Prime Minister).

- April 22, 1970: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the seventh time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).

- October 17, 1970: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the eighth time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).

- April 22, 1971: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato visited for the ninth time (visited eleven times as Prime Minister).

- October 19, 1971: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato made his tenth visit to Yasukuni Shrine (eleven times in total as Prime Minister).

- April 22, 1972: Prime Minister Eisaku Sato made his eleventh visit to Yasukuni Shrine (eleven times in total as Prime Minister).

- July 8, 1972: Prime Minister Kakuei Tanaka made his first visit to Yasukuni Shrine (five times in total as Prime Minister).

- April 23, 1973: Prime Minister Kakuei Tanaka made his second visit to Yasukuni Shrine (five times in total as Prime Minister).

- October 18, 1973: Prime Minister Kakuei Tanaka made his third visit to Yasukuni Shrine (five times in total as Prime Minister).

- April 23, 1974: Prime Minister Kakuei Tanaka's fourth visit (visited a total of five times as Prime Minister).

- October 19, 1974: Prime Minister Kakuei Tanaka's fifth visit (visited a total of five times as Prime Minister).

- April 22, 1975: Prime Minister Takeo Miki's first visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- August 15, 1975: Prime Minister Takeo Miki's second visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- October 18, 1976: Prime Minister Takeo Miki's third visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- April 21, 1977: Prime Minister Takeo Fukuda's first visit (visited a total of four times as Prime Minister).

- April 21, 1978: Prime Minister Takeo Fukuda's second visit (visited a total of four times as Prime Minister).

- August 15, 1978: Prime Minister Takeo Fukuda's third visit (visited a total of four times as Prime Minister). On October 17, 1978, during the Autumn Festival, the enshrined Class-A war criminals' plaques were placed.

- October 18, 1978: Prime Minister Takeo Fukuda's fourth visit (visited a total of four times as Prime Minister).

- April 21, 1979: Prime Minister Masayoshi Ohira's first visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- October 18, 1979: Prime Minister Masayoshi Ohira's second visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- April 21, 1980: Prime Minister Masayoshi Ohira's third visit (visited a total of three times as Prime Minister).

- August 15, 1980: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's first visit (visited a total of nine

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times as Prime Minister).

- October 18, 1980: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's second visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- November 21, 1980: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's third visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1981: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's fourth visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- August 15, 1981: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's fifth visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- October 17, 1981: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's sixth visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1982: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's seventh visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- August 15, 1982: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's eighth visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- October 18, 1982: Prime Minister Zenko Suzuki's ninth visit (visited a total of nine times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1983: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's first visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- August 15, 1983: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's second visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- October 18, 1983: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's third visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- January 5, 1984: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's fourth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- April 21, 1984: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's fifth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- August 15, 1984: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's sixth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- October 18, 1984: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's seventh visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- January 21, 1985: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's eighth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- April 22, 1985: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone's ninth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- August 15, 1985: Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone led his cabinet members in the tenth visit (visited a total of ten times as Prime Minister).
- In 1994, Prime Minister Tomiichi Murayama called for reflection on Japan's militaristic history, while seven members of his cabinet visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On August 15, 1995, eight Liberal Democratic Party members of the Murayama Cabinet, including Ryutaro Hashimoto, who served as Minister of International Trade and Industry, visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On July 29, 1996, Prime Minister Ryutaro Hashimoto visited Yasukuni Shrine on

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his birthday while serving in public office (visited once as Prime Minister).

- On April 22, 1997, 223 members of the "Association of Parliamentarians Who Visit Yasukuni Shrine" collectively visited Yasukuni Shrine, led by Keizo Obuchi, who later became Prime Minister.
- In 1997, eight Cabinet ministers visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On August 15, 1998, eight Cabinet ministers, 54 members of the National Diet, and their representatives collectively visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On August 15, 1999, eight Cabinet ministers and 54 members of the National Diet collectively visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On August 13, 2001, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the first time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On April 21, 2002, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the second time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On January 14, 2003, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the third time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On January 1, 2004, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the fourth time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On August 14, 2005, former Prime Minister Ryutaro Hashimoto and Minister of Economy, Trade and Industry Shoichi Nakagawa visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On October 17, 2005, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the fifth time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On October 18, 2005, over 100 members of the National Diet visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On April 21, 2006, 96 members of the "Association of Parliamentarians Who Visit Yasukuni Shrine" collectively visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On August 15, 2006, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine for the sixth time (visited a total of six times as Prime Minister).
- On October 18, 2006, 84 members of the "Association of Parliamentarians Who Visit Yasukuni Shrine" from the Japanese National Diet visited Yasukuni Shrine.
- On April 23, 2007, 39 members of the "Association of Parliamentarians Who Visit Yasukuni Shrine" visited Yasukuni Shrine.

<http://travel.mipang.com/bible/81354>

17. Evil Japanese Unit 731 conducted infectious disease experiments with Allied prisoners of war, and Diary of British prisoner of war Robert Petty¹¹

Japanese Unit 731 stationed in Allied Prisoner of War Camp

The Japanese Unit 731 was a special force established during World War II by imperial decree for conducting bacteriological experiments and warfare. It is well known that during the trial at the Far East International Military Tribunal after the war, evidence documents No. 3113 and No. 3114, presented by the British inspection team, revealed a glimpse of the history between the Japanese Unit 731

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and the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang. The U.S. National Archives also hold related records on this matter.
According to the records, on February 1, 1943, General Mezu, the commander of the Japanese Kwantung Army, issued a special operational order called "Commander-in-chief Guan's order C No. 98." This order required the Japanese Unit 731 to swiftly dispatch 20 personnel, including 5 officers, 5 non-commissioned officers, and 10 soldiers, along with equipment, to the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang to "conduct bacteriological tests on patients with chronic dysentery."
After receiving the order from the Kwantung Army, the Unit 731 formed a "work group" for the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp. This group arrived at the camp on February 14 of the same year and immediately set up a "workplace" inside the camp.
According to related historical materials, after the Unit 731 "work group" reported to the camp superintendent of the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp upon their arrival, they began their tense "work" on the 15th. The "work group" set up a simple workstation on the playground of the Temporary Camp in Nanda Camp, Fushun, and started conducting "physical examinations" on over 1,000 Allied prisoners of war one by one. During their time in the camp, the "work group" regularly drew blood from the prisoners of war and frequently administered injections of the so-called "vaccine." For a considerable period of time, the Unit 731 "work group" carried out a significant amount of "work" in the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp.
The head of the cholera section of Unit 731, Masao Hozumi, was one of the members sent to the "working group" in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang. After the war, during the trial of some members of Unit 731 conducted in Khabarovsk, Soviet Union, the trial record of Juuzou Tsukaesa provided further understanding of the "work" of the "working group" of Unit 731 in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang.
Prosecutor: "Can you tell us whether Unit 731 conducted investigations on the resistance of Americans to infectious diseases?"
Juuzou Tsukaesa: "I remember this happened in early 1943. At that time, I was recuperating in the Shenyang Military Hospital. A scientific worker named Soh Kozue from the unit came to see me. He talked to me about his work and said that he lived in Shenyang to study the resistance of Anglo-Saxon prisoners of war to infectious diseases. Kozue was specifically sent by Unit 731 to the Allied prisoner of war camp to investigate their resistance to infectious diseases."
Prosecutor: "Did you carry out tests on American prisoners of war for this purpose?"
Juuzou Tsukaesa: "Yes, that's correct."
During the trial, the Soviet prosecution noted that the experimental project conducted by Masao Hozumi in 1943 was titled "Blood Characteristics of American Soldiers and Their Immunity to Infectious Diseases."
Japanese Unit 731 stationed in Allied Prisoner of War Camp
Japanese Unit 731 was a special force established during World War II by imperial decree for conducting bacteriological experiments and warfare. It is well known that

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<p>during the trial at the Far East International Military Tribunal after the war, evidence documents No. 3113 and No. 3114, presented by the British inspection team, revealed a glimpse of the history between Japanese Unit 731 and the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang. The U.S. National Archives also hold related records on the matter.</p>
<p>According to the records, on February 1, 1943, General Mezu, commander of the Japanese Kwantung Army, issued a special operational order called "Commander-in-chief Guan's Order C No. 98." This order required Japanese Unit 731 to swiftly dispatch 20 personnel, including 5 officers, 5 non-commissioned officers, and 10 soldiers, along with equipment, to the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang to "conduct bacteriological tests on patients with chronic dysentery."</p>
<p>After receiving orders from the Kwantung Army, Unit 731 formed a "work group" for the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp. This group arrived at the camp on February 14 of the same year and immediately set up a "workplace" inside the camp.</p>
<p>According to related historical materials, after the Unit 731 "work group" reported to the camp superintendent of the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp upon their arrival, they began their tense "work" on the 15th. The "work group" set up a simple workstation on the playground of the temporary camp in Nanda Camp, Fushun, and started conducting "physical examinations" on over 1,000 Allied prisoners of war one by one. During their time in the camp, the "work group" regularly drew blood from prisoners of war and frequently administered injections of the so-called "vaccine." For a considerable period of time, the Unit 731 "work group" carried out a significant amount of "work" in the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp.</p>
<p>The head of the cholera section of Unit 731, Masao Hozumi, was one of the members sent to the "working group" in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang. After the war, during the trial of some members of Unit 731 conducted in Khabarovsk, Soviet Union, the trial record of Juuzou Tsukaesa provided further understanding of the "work" of the "working group" of Unit 731 in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang.</p>
<p>Prosecutor: "Can you tell us if Unit 731 conducted investigations into the resistance of Americans to infectious diseases?"</p>
<p>Juuzou Tsukaesa: "I remember this happened in early 1943. At that time, I was recuperating in the Shenyang Military Hospital. A scientific worker named Soh Kozue from the unit came to see me. He talked to me about his work and said that he lived in Shenyang to study the resistance of Anglo-Saxon prisoners of war to infectious diseases. Kozue was specifically sent by Unit 731 to the Allied prisoner of war camp to investigate their resistance to infectious diseases."</p>
<p>Prosecutor: "Did you carry out tests on American prisoners of war for this purpose?"</p>
<p>Juuzou Tsukaesa: "Yes, that's correct."</p>
<p>During the trial, the Soviet prosecution noted that the experimental project conducted by Masao Hozumi in 1943 was titled "Blood Characteristics of American Soldiers and Their Immunity to Infectious Diseases."</p>

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Diary of British prisoner of war Robert Petty

Robert Petty, a British lieutenant colonel in the army, was captured on the battlefield in Singapore and was subsequently imprisoned in an Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang until the surrender of Japan in 1945. His prisoner number was 24. During his captivity, Petty secretly recorded daily events in the camp using a unique code that only he knew, while evading the Japanese guards. Although a part of the diary was discovered and confiscated due to thorough inspections by the Japanese, most of it survived intact. In 1985, he agreed to be interviewed by ITV, where he stated, "In my diary, I truthfully recorded the reasons provided by the Japanese for the vaccinations, injections, and preventive measures they performed on us. At that time, we had no way to determine whether they were genuine or not." Petty subsequently provided the entire diary to the production team, and it was made public.

In the "Petty Diary," there are detailed records of the activities performed by Unit 731 in the prisoner of war camp:

Year: 1943

February 14: Smallpox vaccination was administered.

February 15: Two Americans died in the hospital, and the Japanese who arrived at the camp performed autopsies on the bodies.

February 20: All prisoners were tested for the presence of germs causing diarrhea and dysentery.

February 23: A funeral was held for 142 individuals. In 105 days, 186 Americans died.

February 24: The medical investigation concluded that the cause of death was ordinary diarrhea and not fatal. It was clear that this group of medical personnel claimed to provide medical treatment to prisoners while not actually taking any effective measures to cure their illnesses.

March 8: In 123 days, 194 deaths occurred.

April 19: The Japanese conducted another medical investigation.

June 4th: The Japanese carried out the third medical investigation. However, during these visits, it seemed that the medical team was not enthusiastic about actually treating prisoners' illnesses. They merely administered some "preventive vaccines" and asked many strange questions, such as the ethnic backgrounds of the prisoners. The peculiar behavior of these doctors aroused suspicions among the prisoners, as it appeared that they were not there to provide medical treatment.

June 5: 0.5cc dysentery vaccine was administered.

June 8: The number of people with diarrhea continued to increase.

June 13: 1.0cc dysentery vaccine was administered.

August 6: The number of deaths now reached 206.

August 29: Vaccination against dysentery and 1.0cc typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine was administered.

September 12: Blood tests were conducted on each prisoner.

September 19: Approximately 40cc of blood was drawn from each prisoner for erythrocyte sedimentation rate tests.

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October 9: X-ray examinations were performed on all prisoners to check for tuberculosis bacteria.
October 10: 0.5cc cholera vaccine was administered.
October 17: 1.0cc cholera vaccine was administered.
November 21: The death toll has exceeded 230.
Year: 1944
On February 6, vaccinated all prisoners of war.
On February 20, injected 0.5 cc of typhoid and paratyphoid combination vaccine.
On February 27, injected typhoid and paratyphoid combination vaccine.
On May 21, injected 0.5cc of dysentery vaccine.
On May 28, injected 1.0cc of dysentery vaccine.
On August 20, all prisoners of war were injected with 1.0cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
Year: 1945
On January 28, vaccinated all prisoners of war.
On February 27, vaccinated all prisoners of war with 0.5cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
On March 6, vaccinated all prisoners of war with 1.0cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
In this part of Piti's diary, on the one hand, we can see that between February 14th, 1943 when Unit 731 entered the prisoner of war camp and March 6th, 1945, the prisoners of war were injected with various vaccines at least 15 times in the span of two years. The frequency of injections far exceeded the normal vaccination cycle rate.
After the war, Arthur Christie, a former British prisoner of war (number 1210), testified as follows: "The group of people (referring to Unit 731 "work team") started a series of injections as soon as they arrived. Monthly body measurements also started from that time. After that, injections were given 16 times within 12 months. They seriously told us that these injections were for typhoid, paratyphoid, malaria vaccines, etc. But it is perplexing that preventive vaccination for vaccines is once every 7 years for the British army and once every 5 years for the American army. Are the injections we received really vaccines?"
Blood samples were also taken every month. They forced me to separate the blood into red blood cells and plasma using a centrifuge. Each month, 50cc of blood samples were taken from each individual, totaling 50,000cc for 1,000 people. What was all this blood being used for?
Former U.S. prisoner of war (designated as Number 190), Robert Brown, recalled: "Shortly after arriving in Fengtian, a group of Japanese doctors came to the POW camp to administer vaccines and assign numbers to us. However, many people died soon after, and at that time, a Japanese doctor named Ogi saved me. Many years later, Dr. Ogi told me that he was a member of the 731 Bacteriological Warfare Unit.
Harm done by Unit 731 to Allied prisoners of war
After the war, the United States government's post-war investigation team

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conducted a detailed investigation into what happened at the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang. They compiled a document called "The Experiences of Allied Prisoners in Manchuria," which was declassified in 2003 and is now stored in the U.S. National Archives. The document contains records of Unit 731's activities in the prisoner of war camp:

People with symptoms of intermittent fever must be reported. Their body temperature and blood must be checked, and they must be given a card recording their daily visits to the pharmacy to collect quinine. The dosage of quinine is as follows: 15 pills per day for the first 3 days, 9 pills per day for the next 10 days, and 3 pills per day for the following 10 days. This constitutes one course of treatment. Generally, after two to three weeks, patients would experience the symptoms of intermittent fever again and have to repeat treatment. Compared to U.S. treatment for this type of malaria, the dosage of quinine was absurdly low. The American treatment plan called for taking 30 to 50 pills per day. The Japanese used similar methods to treat other diseases as well. It can be seen that the "treatment" of prisoners of war may not have aimed to cure them completely, but rather to repeatedly observe their resistance to infectious diseases.

After the war, the U.S. House of Representatives held two hearings of the Committee on Veterans Affairs in 1982 and 1986. During the 1986 hearing, James Frank, a former prisoner of war (Number 843), recalled: in the spring of 1943, two Japanese officers were assigned to work with the visiting medical team, and he was one of them. The Japanese asked him to move bodies from one small house to another, and then they would be placed on autopsy tables. He witnessed the organs of these soldiers being removed, placed in special containers labeled with each prisoner's number, and detailed records being made. The specimens were taken away from the prisoner of war camp in trucks. Soon after, some prisoners were selected for testing. Japanese medical personnel asked detailed questions about the racial backgrounds of American prisoners of war, whether they were Scottish, French, British, or from other countries.

Jack Roberts, a former British prisoner of war (Number 1183), recalled: one morning in early 1943, he was in poor physical condition but didn't dare to go to the "hospital" because no one who went in ever came back. He went to the small house where bodies were stored, and there were about 340 bodies piled up there. The feet of the bodies were tagged with numbers. The Japanese asked him to carry two or three bodies to the Japanese "doctors" who lived there. They wore gas masks and always hid their faces. He and another person were ordered to lift the bodies and place them on the dissecting table. Then, the Japanese would open the abdomens of the bodies, reaching deep inside to remove organs like the stomach, gallbladder, and small intestine. They also took out things resembling liver samples and lungs. Then, they would cut open the heads and remove part of the brain.

Bruce Blythman, a former Australian prisoner of war (Number 25), worked as a doctor in the prisoner of war camp hospital. He hid a diary under a patient's bed (the Japanese never approached prisoners suffering from tuberculosis) and

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recorded three instances of the "Medical Unit of Unit 731" entering the prisoner of war camp to "work." During the first visit, the "Medical Unit of Unit 731" performed autopsies on deceased prisoners and collected samples with labels. However, during the three visits to the prisoner of war camp, they only conducted various checks, blood tests, and did not provide any valuable opinions regarding the conditions in the camp or the high death rate.

At a conference in 1986, former American prisoner of war (number 768) Greg Rodriguez testified that for over 40 years after the war, he had to visit the Veterans Administration hospital multiple times each year due to inexplicable symptoms such as fever, pain, and fatigue. One time, his temperature reached a staggering 106 degrees Fahrenheit (approximately 41 degrees Celsius). It wasn't until 10 years ago when a doctor finally diagnosed him with typhoid fever, because his blood had a significant amount of typhoid bacilli.

Greg Rodriguez's son, Langrey, was once president of the American Prisoners of War Association. In September 2003, he visited the Shenyang Allied Prisoner of War Camp where his father had been held captive. In an interview with local media, he revealed that his father had been injected with vaccines while in captivity, and his body temperature remained higher than normal in the following days. Similarly, U.S. prisoners of war experienced unexplained fever, trembling, night sweats, snake-like skin shedding, and numbness, all due to the infiltration of Unit 731 into the prisoner of war camp, where bacteria were injected into prisoners' bodies under the guise of preventive vaccinations.

On September 19, 2003, Langrey presented the Chinese media with an English certificate from the U.S. government entitled "Proof that the Prison Camp Injected Plague into American Prisoners of war." He exposed, "The evidence of vaccine injections is right here."

Thomas George Riggs, a former U.S. prisoner of war with identification number 968, recalled his experience. One night, he had a high fever and experienced alternating chills and heat. A Japanese doctor approached him and asked him to lie down on his bed, placing a mirror under his nose. Later on, a feather was inserted into his nostril. Riggs thought the Japanese were checking his breathing. However, since then, his high fever persisted, and he was plagued by illness. One minute he felt fine, and the next minute he suddenly fell ill. Initially, it lasted several months, then several years, or even longer. Riggs underwent numerous tests and examinations at the hospital, but doctors could not determine the cause of his illness. As a father of six children, he unknowingly transmitted the pathogen on to his children, affecting their physical health. From infancy, two of his daughters developed thyroid disease, and one of his sons suffered from arthritis.

Through the accounts of surviving prisoners of war, we gain a visceral understanding of the "work" of Unit 731 in the prisoner of war camps. On the surface, the purpose of Unit 731's "medical team" in the camps was to investigate the causes of prisoners' deaths and improve their health conditions. However, actual "medical work" did not prioritize prisoners' health or provide them with treatment. Treating illnesses was

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not important, even insignificant. The Allied prisoners of war had experienced the cruelty of war, transportation, and harsh living conditions in the Fushun POW camp, so falling ill was inevitable. However, apart from severely ill prisoners who died, most prisoners should have recovered, especially if given appropriate treatment. But it was precisely the "medical" treatment by Unit 731 that had lifelong effects on the prisoners' bodies.

After enduring the tests of war, death marches, and torturous transportation, over a thousand prisoners of war from countries like England and America who were held captive in the "Fushun Prisoner of War Detention Center" began to suffer from a large number of illnesses and deaths.

If the Japanese army really wanted to treat a large number of sick Allied prisoners of war and restore their health, they could easily have done so in Shenyang. There was the "Manchurian Medical University", which belonged to the local area and was ranked among the top hospitals in Japan and its occupied territories at that time. There was also the "Fengtian Army Hospital," which was under military jurisdiction and where Ishii Shiro underwent treatment.

In short, the Japanese army, under its rule, had the capability to provide treatment and there was no need to send Unit 731 to POW camps. Furthermore, Unit 731 was a special unit engaged in bacteriological warfare and did not have a medical nature. Moreover, given the tense situation in the early 1943 stage of the Second World War, Unit 731 was more focused on research and preparation for bacteriological warfare. If the sole purpose was to treat prisoners of war, why would the Japanese army easily deploy such a unit for something that was considered insignificant to them? It is even more puzzling that the Kwantung Army chose to send Unit 731 to POW camps as a way of issuing combat orders.

Investigation of Unit 731 after World War II

After Japan surrendered in August 1945, the United States Strategic Intelligence Agency formulated a mission codenamed "Operation Firebird" with the aim of liberating American prisoners of war held captive in Northeast China. Documents on this mission explicitly stated that members of the agency were to fly immediately to Harbin to rescue American and other Allied prisoners of war once they received notification of victory in the war. It is worth noting that there were no Allied prisoner of war camps in Harbin at the time, with the closest one being Shenyang. This suggests that the American government and military authorities at the time considered the possibility of Unit 731 conducting bacteriological experiments on Allied prisoners of war. American intelligence agencies were aware of the Japanese conducting bacteriological experiments near Harbin, so they firmly believed that there must be prisoners of war there. It seems that their mission to rescue prisoners of war near Harbin was not due to a lack of knowledge of the location of Allied prisoner of war camps, but rather their firm belief that some prisoners of war had already been taken to Harbin to serve as experimental subjects for the bacteriological unit.

In 1946, after the war, various American media outlets such as the "Stars and Stripes

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Pacific Edition" and "The New York Times" reported on the Ishii Unit's use of Allied prisoners of war for bacteriological experiments.

In August 1947, a U.S. government archival document indicated: "There is a possibility that a independent Soviet investigation team has discovered evidence near Fengtian suggesting that the Japanese used American prisoners of war for live bacteriological experiments, resulting in the loss of many American soldiers' lives. Moreover, these pieces of evidence are likely to have been utilized by the Soviet Union in the legal trial of Japanese prisoners of war."

In March 1956, a memorandum from the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) stated: "Mr. James Kelleher of the Department of Defense Special Action Office confirmed this further after the US military occupied Japan. He determined that the Japanese used American prisoners of war as subjects for bacteriological experiments in Manchuria between 1943 and 1944, making them undoubtedly victims... The related information is considered highly sensitive and strictly controlled."

After the publication of Shōichi Sonobe's "The Devil's Gluttony" in 1980, the issue of experiments conducted on Allied prisoners of war gained unprecedented attention. He stated, "The majority of the victims were Chinese, Koreans, and Russians, but information from various sources indicates that the victims also included British, Dutch, Australian, New Zealand, and American individuals."

(References: Declassified files from the US National Archives, such as "Experiences of Fengtian POWs," "Fengtian POW Report (February Report) - Work Report of the Temporary Epidemic Prevention and Control Group," and "List of Captured Personnel (Showa 20th Year - Surveillance Intelligence Series)"; "Trial Materials for Former Japanese Army Personnel Charged with Preparing and Using Bacteriological Weapons," Moscow Foreign Document Publishing House, 1950; (Japanese) Fuyuko Saito's "Biological Warfare Unit 731," Grassroots Publishing, 2002; (American) Daniel Barenblatt's "A Plague upon Humanity," Harper Collins Publishers, 2003.)

[Translated from the following literature. <http://dangshi.people.com.cn/n1/2020/0813/c85037-31820562.html>]¹¹

18. The prime minister of Japan believes that the military power of the United States has declined and demands to station troops in the United States.

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The screenshot shows a Baidu search page with the query '日本首相, 美国军事力量下降, 日本要在美国驻军'. The search results include a top result from 网易新闻 (NetEase News) with the headline '倒反天罡? 日本新首相刚上台首日, 要求在美国驻军, 后院迅速...' and a sub-headline '日本首相, 美国军事力量下降, 日本要在美国驻军的最新相关信息'. Below this is a featured snippet with a photo of Shigeru Ishiba and the text '要在美国驻军? 日本新首相上任不到24小时, 当众对美发...'. Another result from 千钧堂 (Qianjuntang) is visible with the headline '日本新首相出炉, 曾就台湾问题表态, 宣称要在美国建立军事基地'.

What the Japanese are doing is dragging the United States down! At the same time, they deceive the public internationally by pretending to be victims of atomic bomb explosions and obtain sympathy and other illegal benefits. **In September 2024, Japan's newly elected prime minister, Shigeru Ishiba, proposed: "The strength of the United States has declined significantly. The time is ripe to revise the Japan-US Security Treaty. The 'asymmetry' of the Japan-US alliance should be corrected. The US military can station troops in Japan, and the Self-Defense Forces of Japan should also station troops in the United States, such as Guam!"** Many Chinese media have reported this matter extensively.

19. The Japanese manufactured 4.7 million sets of Chinese military clothing in Wuhan. What is evil Japan preparing to do? (see Fig 4A.)

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据悉，最近在武汉我们的武警官兵，查获了一批日本人制造的**中国**军服，各种各样的**军服**都有。共查获了470万套，为什么日本人要偷偷的做这么多军服呢？他们要干啥呢？武汉的武警查封了一家纺织厂，当时日本人正在偷偷的制作中国各种各样的军服。国内混进这么多日本人，搞这么多军服意欲何为？给谁做的？他们穿中国军服又想干嘛呢？

Fig 4A. In recent years, in Wuhan, China, armed police officers and soldiers have seized a batch of Chinese military uniforms made by the Japanese. There are all kinds of military uniforms. A total of 4.7 million sets were seized. Why did the Japanese secretly make so many military uniforms? What are they going to do? Armed police in Wuhan have sealed off a textile factory. At that time, the Japanese were secretly making all kinds of Chinese military uniforms. Japan is a country of war criminals. Almost all Japanese people, including Japanese children, serve the aggression against China, the Asia-Pacific region and the United States and are all war criminals. Now there are so many Japanese in China. What is the intention of making so many Chinese military uniforms? What do they want to do by wearing Chinese military uniforms? Japan has a population of 126 million and can rapidly expand its military to 2-3 million. It is said that every student in Japanese schools in Brazil undergoes gun training, just like during World War II. Japan has purchased a large amount of land in Brazil. The area is more than three times that of Japan's domestic territory. Is Japan preparing to change countries?

[The Japanese are making trouble in our country again. As a result, they were caught red-handed. December 28, 2022.

<https://m.163.com/dy/article/HPKR2V3D05531ZD7.html>]

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Fig.824. The evil Japanese people use the Nanjing Guanyin statue to redeem Japanese war criminals, and decipher the world's most sinister Feng Shui organization. This Guanyin statue is constructed using ten jars of soil soaked with the blood of Chinese civilians.

The purpose of building this evil statue with the blood - stained soil of the civilians massacred in the Nanjing Massacre is to make Asia submit to Japan.

Warvigilance: If the Japanese really wanted world peace, they would have destroyed these evil towers and sculptures long ago. On the contrary, every year countless Japanese come here to worship Japanese war criminals and secretly make wishes to conquer Asia and the world.

If Japan were truly a peace loving nation, would it be so bloody and shameless?

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If the Japanese were truly a peace-loving nation, would a peace-loving nation still be so bloody and shameless in the 21st century after World War II?

In the early morning of 23 December, Hideki Tojo and six other war criminals were executed. At 7 a.m., their bodies were transported to Kuboyama crematorium, where Yoshimi Tobita, under U.S. military supervision, cremated the seven bodies and placed the ashes in seven separate urns. However, Tobita secretly manipulated the process and did not put all of the ashes in the urns. He even attempted to privately offer incense and prayers for the seven individuals, but the U.S. military discovered this and confiscated all the incense.

Unaware of Tobita's actions, the U.S. military packed the seven urns and took them away. The remaining small portion of the ashes were abandoned in a cement pit at the crematorium, which was used to dispose of unclaimed ashes. After the U.S. troops left, Tobita immediately informed Sanmoto Masami. On the night of the 25th, Sanmoto Masami, Yoshimi Tobita, and Ichikawa Iyo, wearing black cloaks, secretly infiltrated the crematorium. Guided by Tobita, they arrived at the cement pit and used bamboo poles tied to jars to retrieve some of the ashes and fragments of bones from the pile of ash at the bottom.

The stolen ashes were initially stored at Kuboyama Kogyo-ji Temple, and in May of the following year, they were finally sent to Xingya Kannon Temple in Izu-Yama, Atami City, for safekeeping. The origin of this Xingya Kannon Temple is also extraordinary. The term "Xingya" was widely used by various Japanese militaristic and colonial institutions from the Meiji Restoration until Japan's defeat in World War II. For example, in 1938, the Japanese Kono Cabinet established the "Xingya Institute," which was specifically responsible for managing daily affairs and looting of resources in the occupied Chinese territories during the war against China. Therefore, the name Xingya Kannon Temple alone indicates that it is not an ordinary Buddhist temple. What infuriates the Chinese even more is that this temple was funded and built by Matsui Iwane, one of the seven executed war criminals and mastermind behind the Nanjing Massacre, in 1940 as a memorial for the deceased Japanese soldiers and officers in the war against China.

The stolen ashes were initially stored at Kubo Mountain Kōzenji Temple, and were only sent to the Xingya Guanyin Temple in Izu Yama, Atami City in May of the second year. The origin of this Xingya Guanyin Temple is also extraordinary. The characters "Xingya" were widely used by various Japanese militaristic and colonial institutions after the Meiji Restoration until Japan's defeat in the war. For example, in 1938, Japan's Kono Cabinet established the "Xingya Academy," a specialized institution for managing daily affairs and looting of resources on Chinese territories occupied during the China-Japanese War. Therefore, from the name of Xingya Guanyin Temple, it can be seen that this is not an ordinary Buddhist temple. What angers the Chinese even more is that it was funded and built by Matsui Iwane, one of the seven executed war criminals and the main culprit of the Nanjing Massacre, in order to worship the Japanese soldiers who died in the war of aggression against China.

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The statue of Guanyin in the temple was specially made from 10 jars of blood-soaked soil taken from Nanjing Dachang Town by Matsui Iwane's men. After the temple was completed on February 24, 1940, Matsui Iwane even built a hermitage nearby and climbed the mountain every morning to worship Guanyin.

Although the ashes of these seven war criminals were sent to Xingya Guanyin Temple, due to the recent end of World War II, the Japanese people still did not dare to openly engage in worship activities, nor did they dare to publicly display the ashes. The then abbot, Itami Shinobishiki, decided to temporarily hide the ashes and "wait for the right moment."

In 1959, the so-called "Monument of the Seven Patriots" written by then Japanese Prime Minister Yoshida Shigeru was completed at Xingya Guanyin Temple. The temple believed that the "time was ripe" and publicly announced the news of the seven war criminals' ashes being located there and buried them under the monument. In 1960, another so-called "Martyrs' Tomb of the Seven Patriots" was built in Motosu, Hatono District, Aichi Prefecture, and some of the ashes were taken from Xingya Guanyin Temple and buried in the tomb. Therefore, the ashes of the seven war criminals were buried in two different places.

The initial intention of the United States was to scatter the ashes of these seven individuals into the Pacific Ocean in order to prevent their graves from becoming a "sacred place" for the revival of Japanese militarism. However, under a series of actions by the Japanese, this goal has clearly not been achieved.

After several decades of additions, the current Xingya Guanyin Temple houses the ashes of 7 Class A war criminals and 901 Class B and C war criminals, all of whom were executed after being tried by various post-war military courts. There are also a total of 160 Class A, B, and C war criminals who died in prison for various reasons and were not executed by military courts. In total, there are 1,068 individuals. It can be said that this place is a gathering place for war criminals, often referred to as the "Little Yasukuni Shrine."

In addition to places where Class A war criminals are enshrined, such as Xingya Guanyin Academy, there are also some shrines in Japan dedicated to specific Japanese war criminals and militarists. The infamous ones among them are the Naimu Shrine and the Eryu Shrine.

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJPnNp71/>],[How malicious is Matsui Shigen? After the Nanjing Massacre, 10 jars of blood and soil were excavated to create a statue of Guanyin,May 5th, 2022. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/H6JOH9K90543AHBP.html>],[Be vigilant! In Japan, there are shrines that treat war criminals as ancestral offerings, as well as these.August 25th, 2021 https://www.sohu.com/a/485497414_162522]

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Fig 85-23-14. Real camera videos [Millions of Japanese prisoners of war returned to Japan and were welcomed like heroes. 2023-09-15.

<https://v.douyin.com/iNkSw4Fa/07/23E@h.BT.Uyt:/>]

The Japanese have never had a heart of repentance for massacring the Chinese people and plundering huge amounts of wealth.

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

Greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese plundered vast amounts of gold, silver, jewels, diamonds, artifacts, and rare books, and slaughtered at least 51.80 to 89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people. Isn't Japan the real victor? The wealth was long transported back to Japan, and the people also returned safely. Aren't they very happy in their hearts?

How could Japan be considered a defeated nation? Japan did nothing more than sign a single A4-sized document of surrender, which excited the utopian nerves of kind-hearted people around the world. The biggest war criminal even openly bribed the occupying commander, General MacArthur, with beauty, and was not only spared the

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death penalty, but was astonishingly not sentenced at all. Where are human rights? Where is empathy? Where is freedom? Where is democracy?

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日本爱知县，距离东京5个小时车程，有一座风景如画的三根山，在它的山顶有一处合葬墓，说起这处合葬墓，估计包括中国在内亚洲很多国家的人会跳起来，它就是在二战结束后，被东京国际军事法庭判处死刑的7个日本甲级战犯东条英机等的合葬墓，名字叫“殉国七士墓”。在二战后的德国，全国都深刻反省了纳粹的罪行，发表纳粹的言论都要被判刑，战犯希特勒等被永远的钉死在历史的耻辱柱上，在德国不可能有希特勒的墓碑，也不允许有希特勒等战犯的任何纪念。而日本却正好相反，他们把战犯供进靖国神社，认为东京军事法庭不合法，认为日本没有错，甚至战犯的坟墓被称为“七士墓”。

Fig.830. Warvigilance: In Aichi Prefecture, Japan, a picturesque mountain called Sangen-yama can be found, which is a five-hour drive from Tokyo. At its summit, there is a collective grave known as the "Martyrs' Grave" where seven Class A Japanese war criminals, including Hideki Tojo, were buried after being sentenced to death by the Tokyo International Military Tribunal after World War II. This topic would likely to cause a strong reaction from people in many Asian countries, including China.

In post-war Germany, the entire nation deeply reflected on the crimes of the Nazis, and expressing Nazi sentiments could result in imprisonment. War criminals like Hitler were forever condemned in the annals of history, and it is impossible to find a grave monument for Hitler in Germany or any other form of commemoration for him or other war criminals. In Japan, however, the situation is quite the opposite. War criminals were enshrined in Yasukuni Shrine, as Japan considered the Tokyo Military Tribunal to be illegitimate and believed Japan was not at fault. The graves of these war criminals were even referred to as the "Seven Martyrs' Graves."

Is this "Martyrs' Cemetery of the Seven Patriots" just a tomb of clothes? Was it built by someone secretly? If you think so, you're wrong. This tomb is grand and not done in secret at all. On December 23, 1948, seven Japanese Class-A war criminals were executed by hanging, ending their lives of evil. Their bodies were cremated. Japanese lawyer Michinari Sangyo, who participated in the trial of war criminals, collected some of their remains. In 1960, he established this collective burial tomb on Sangen Mountain, with the remains buried here, directly beneath the monument. At that time, Eisaku Sato,

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the Prime Minister of Japan and also a Class-A war criminal (after serving his sentence, he returned to politics and became the heavyweight of the conservative political forces in Japan), personally wrote the inscription for the grave of these seven core war criminals as the Chief Cabinet Minister, referring to them as "martyrs of the nation." If you visit Sangen Mountain today, you will find a large 5-meter high stone monument at the entrance of the cemetery, with the words "Martyrs' Temple of the Seven Patriots" engraved on it, and behind the monument is the prominent inscription "Written by Eisaku Sato, 56th and 56th Prime Minister of Japan's Cabinet".

At Yasukuni Shrine, these seven core Class-A war criminals are only enshrined with their spirit tablets, but their actual remains are here, making this place a holy site for Japan's militaristic forces. There is a constant stream of people who come here to pay their respects, including many young people. In the cemetery area, apart from the tombstones of the seven war criminals, you can also see many memorial tablets for the Japanese army units involved in the past aggressive wars.

The past should not be forgotten, for it serves as a teacher for the future. Today, with the protection of the United States, Japan continues to display its aggressive tendencies. In the past, they occasionally issued statements and offered apologies to countries like China and Korea, but now they can't even be bothered to apologize. As a victim of Japan's aggression during World War II, China must remember the names of these seven Class-A war criminals. They are: Kenji Doihara, the mastermind behind the Nanjing Massacre; Hideki Tojo, the former prime minister responsible for invading China and starting the Pacific War; Akiyuki Muto; Shigetaro Shimada, the instigator of the Mukden Incident; Hiroki Higashikuni, who initiated the Second China-Japanese War; and Hyotaro Kimura.

In October 1941, Hideki Tojo took office as Prime Minister of Japan's Cabinet. Later that year, a decision was made at an Imperial conference to go to war with the United States, Britain, and the Netherlands. On December 7, 1941, Pearl Harbor was attacked, marking the outbreak of the Pacific War. On the same day, the Japanese army, under the command of Hideki Tojo, launched attacks on Thailand, Malaysia, the Philippines, Guam, and other places.

[Translated from: The ironclad evidence of Japanese militarism's immortality, the so-called "Tomb of Seven Martyrs" for burying Class A war criminals. Original: December 23, 2016. <https://www.toutiao.com/article/6366828454456852994/>]

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Fig.831. The Gate of Cemetery of the Seven Patriots or Tomb of Seven Martyrs [The ironclad evidence of Japanese militarism's immortality, the so-called "Tomb of Seven Martyrs" for burying Class A war criminals.Original: December 23, 2016.<https://www.toutiao.com/article/6366828454456852994/>]

Fig.828. Warvigilance: Less than a 5-hour drive from Tokyo, on the summit of Sanganesan in Aichi Prefecture, there is a "holy place" for Japanese war enthusiasts called the "Shrine of the Seven Martyrs of Loyalty and Nationalism." While Yasukuni Shrine is used by Japanese war enthusiasts to worship Class A war criminals, it does not have their memorial plaques nor does it store their ashes. In fact, the memorial

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plaques and ashes of the seven Class A war criminals, including Kenji Doihara, who were executed by hanging, are all housed in the "Shrine of the Seven Martyrs of Loyalty and Nationalism." Every spring, autumn, and especially on August 15, the day of Japan's defeat in the war, crowds of people gather there to pay their respects, creating a lively atmosphere no less than that of Yasukuni Shrine. Local residents say, "Every August 15th, many Japanese war enthusiasts and members of the Japanese underworld ride their roaring motorcycles here, just like biker gangs, fearing that others might not know." At the same time, there are also some Japanese politicians who come here to "work without leaving a name."

[The ironclad evidence of Japanese militarism's immortality, the so-called "Tomb of Seven Martyrs" for burying Class A war criminals. Original: December 23, 2016. <https://www.toutiao.com/article/6366828454456852994/>], [The most detestable Japanese invader of China, who was enshrined as "martyred" by Japan, September 6, 2016. https://www.sohu.com/a/113714618_209689]

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Fig.829. The stone tablet of the Seven Martyrs' Temple is prominently engraved with the names of invading criminals such as Hideki Tojo and Kenji Tokaihara [The most detestable Japanese invader of China, who was enshrined as "martyred" by Japan, September 6, 2016. https://www.sohu.com/a/113714618_209689]

Warvigilance:

If the Japanese really wanted world peace, they would have destroyed these evil the Seven Martyrs' Temple long ago. On the contrary, every year countless Japanese come here to worship Japanese war criminals and secretly make wishes to conquer Asia and the world.

Relevant evidence of atomic bomb psychological warfare is as follows:

1. Any discipline, once it is involved in mathematics, is bound to become a real science. Through mathematical calculations, it was estimated that Japan could be completely and permanently paralyzed due to nuclear radiation with only three atomic bombs of the power of "Little Boy." However, after the United States dropped two atomic bombs on Japan, more than half of Japan's land was supposed to be contaminated. But the truth is the opposite. The U.S. military not only could send planes to drop leaflets without considering the radioactive contaminated dust in the Japanese sky after the atomic bomb explosion, but strangely, Hiroshima and Nagasaki returned to normal after 2-3 weeks. Moreover, fertility in Hiroshima and Nagasaki has remained normal for a long time. **Apparently, Japan being bombed by atomic bombs is 100% fictional, and the US dropping atomic bombs on Japan is obviously psychological warfare.**

2. The anomalies in the film and photo material of the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Many people have seen the film and photographic material after the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. However, with little common sense and some thinking, you will find that there are many problems with these film and photo materials. After the atomic bomb explosion, who had the ability to take pictures or videos in areas with high atomic radiation and nuclear radiation? At that time, Japan did not have any anti-radiation equipment. Even scarce film materials are still problematic. You will find that some "survivors" came out of the ruins after the explosion and lined up to walk, as if they had been trained. Moreover, it is incredible to survive an atomic weapon explosion in itself. **Based on this alone, whether or not according to the FDA's process authenticity assessment rules, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was indeed psychological warfare.**

3. The confusion of the "survivors". From the end of the war to today, no one has ever been found who can directly prove that an atomic bomb explosion occurred in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Some "survivors" only saw a big fire, and some other "survivors" used the scars of their so-called "radiation burns", which were actually just traces of fire burns. No Japanese can prove with the evidence of his own experience that an atomic bomb has ever exploded in Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

4. Some Japanese people were in the city center, some victims had burns on their

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arms, no clothes on their upper body, no burns on their lower body, and their lower body pants were intact. This is a phenomenon that is completely inconsistent with the logic of experiencing the scene of the atomic bomb explosion. If experiencing the atomic bomb explosion, radiation burns will inevitably lead to the disappearance of the lower body's trousers, and the lower body will also be burned. **Based on this alone, whether or not according to the FDA's process authenticity assessment rules, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was indeed psychological warfare.**

5. In the photos, there is even a house in the explosion center area with an almost intact outer wall of the house, which is completely illogical. **Based on this alone, whether or not according to the FDA's process authenticity assessment rules, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was indeed psychological warfare.**

Fig 40.21A. Will there still be such good tree trunks and houses left in the central area of the atomic bomb explosion?

[Nine Eyewitness Accounts of the Bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki. HISTORY | AUGUST 5, 2020. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/nine-harrowing-eyewitness-accounts-bombings-hiroshima-and-nagasaki-180975480/>]

If you are a doctor of science or engineering, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected **within 60-120 seconds on base of the Fig 40.21A** , and then, after studying the relevant literature, **you should be able to judge within 15 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan**

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suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by the U.S. military.

In an atomic - bomb air - explosion, buildings would not only be destroyed by the shock wave, but also burned by high temperatures. Rooftops should be severely damaged, and white roofs and walls should have long since changed color in high temperatures. However, the structures of these several houses are relatively intact, which is obviously fabricated by the Japanese. The Japanese army may have placed some incendiary bombs or gasoline near wooden structured houses, resulting in the burning of some wooden structured houses, while the structures of brick and stone structured houses are still relatively intact.

If it were really an atomic bomb explosion, all the branches of the tree around the central area should have been basically charred, and the small branches should have been even more charred. However, the tree branches in the picture could not possibly have been the result of large-scale high-temperature burning after an atomic bomb explosion. The branches of the tree in the picture were not charred by the high temperature, and the small branch on the right side in the middle was even relatively intact. Obviously, this is the result of a fictional atomic bomb explosion.

6. The fictional death toll. At that time, because most of the major cities in Japan were bombed by American planes all day long, most citizens fled to the countryside to take shelter. The same was true in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. In fact, according to an elderly Japanese in Hiroshima, after March 1945, there were less than 50,000 citizens in Hiroshima. When he left Hiroshima for the countryside in April, there were very few people left in Hiroshima. Of course, the same is true for Nagasaki. However, the Japanese government finally claimed that the two atomic bombs ultimately caused nearly 300,000 deaths. This is obviously psychological warfare and the Japanese government played the role of victim. Based on this alone, according to the FDA's process authenticity assessment rules, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was indeed psychological warfare.

The United States has not made public that the dropping of atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki is psychological warfare, which has led to abnormal hatred of the United States in the hearts of the vast majority of Japanese people. They even hope to drop atomic bombs on the United States to retaliate against Americans. Some national media also report from time to time that Japan is attempting to use the nuclear material it possesses to build nuclear weapons. Therefore, in any case, the United States should immediately make public the truth that the implementation of the atomic bomb was psychological warfare at that time, publicize the success of this tactic, and also prompt the world to face up to the research results of British scientists. All countries should destroy nuclear weapons and maintain world peace.

7. A scientist involved in the Manhattan Project and a senior U.S. military officer revealed that the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were extraordinary information and psychological warfare carried out by the U.S. military.

At the end of 1999, a scientist who participated in the Manhattan Project and a

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senior U.S. military officer disclosed a surprising story: the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were hoaxes, extraordinary information and psychological warfare conducted by the U.S. military, a very successful "soft war."

At that time, Japan had become an isolated island with minimal contact with the outside world. The U.S. military had the capability to control communication and information systems throughout Japan, and could have disseminated a large amount of false information and scare tactics to the Japanese government and people, making it difficult for most Japanese to distinguish truth from propaganda. The U.S. military deliberately chose Hiroshima and Nagasaki because of their distance from Tokyo and limited communication when cut off from the world, making them suitable for information deception.

On August 6, 1945, the United States dropped some new type of incendiary bomb on Hiroshima, which ignited a large fire. Then, the U.S. military used electronic interference to cut off Hiroshima's external communications, and impersonated Japanese agencies to send radio messages nationwide, claiming that Hiroshima had been bombed by a massive bomb with great destructive power. Simultaneously, the U.S. military spy network in Japan began working, passing information to several important Japanese scientists to make them believe it was an atomic bomb.

8. The results of mathematical calculations show that the atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki must have been the core cause of the war

Table 1 shows that the **minimum number of nuclear bombs required to paralyze Japan after a nuclear attack is about 2-3.** If two atomic bombs explode in Japan, it can basically cripple Japan, or at least 20% of Japan will be paralyzed. **It is worth noting that on August 9, 1945, the United States dropped the "Fat Man" atomic bomb on Nagasaki. It weighed about 4.9 tons and had a TNT equivalent of 22,000 tons, which was more powerful than Hiroshima's "Little Boy" and the world's first atomic bomb.** However, no nuclear pollution was felt in Hiroshima and Nagasaki within 2-3 weeks. **Whether or not** according to FDA standards for authenticating the process, it is clear that the atomic bombing of Japan was clearly a successful psychological warfare operation. After 80 years, the disclosure of this table's data makes any secrecy seem futile. Instead, it benefits Japan, a World War II war criminal country, which wants to portray itself as a victim of a nuclear attack. It is also not conducive to nuclear disarmament, reduction of military expenditures, and normalization of the economies of various countries.

9. The Government and people of Japan misled the United Nations and its Secretary-General

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UN Photo/Yoshito Matsushige. Injured civilians, having escaped the raging inferno, gathered on a pavement west of Miyuki-bashi in Hiroshima, Japan, at about 11 a.m. on 6 August 1945.

[Guterres salutes Japanese anti-nuclear group on Nobel Peace Prize win. 11 October 2024 Peace and Security. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2024/10/1155606>]

The picture above is an on - site picture of an atomic bomb explosion posted in a press release by the United Nations Secretary - General when congratulating the Hibakusha group (atomic bomb explosion victims in Japan) on winning the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize on October 11. The green leaves of the two trees in early August still exist and are not burned. Under the high temperature irradiation of the atomic bomb, the leaves of the two trees in the picture are still intact. Isn't this the U.S. military carry out atomic bomb psychological warfare? From other marked places, it can be seen that this could not have been the scene of an atomic bomb explosion at that time.

At 5:24 a.m. on July 16, 1945, the United States carried out the first nuclear test in human history on a 30 - meter - high iron tower at the "Trinity" test site in Alamogordo, New Mexico. The "Gadget" with a plutonium charge weighing 6.1 kilograms had a TNT equivalent of 22,000 tons. In the test, due to the nuclear explosion, a high temperature of tens of millions of degrees and tens of billions of atmospheres was generated, causing a 30 meter high iron tower to be melted into gas and forming a huge crater on the ground.

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On July 16, 1945, after the first atomic bomb in the world was successfully test - detonated in the United States, scientists had to spend time evaluating the process, manufacturing new atomic bombs, and conducting atomic - bomb explosion experiments in different modes. This is in line with the scientific process. However, at 8 a.m. on August 6, 1945, the second atomic bomb of the US military was dropped on Hiroshima, and at 11 a.m. on August 9, 1945, the third atomic bomb of the United States exploded in Nagasaki. The first atomic bomb was detonated on a 30-meter - high iron tower at the "Trinity" test site in Alamogordo, New Mexico. The latter two atomic bombs were detonated by air - dropping. The US military had no experience in detonating atomic bombs by air - dropping. It was completely impossible to prepare two completely different atomic bombs for actual combat in about twenty days, transport them to the maritime military base, and then drop them on Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

It was also completely impossible for the United States to manufacture two atomic bombs with different devices simultaneously after the first atomic bomb exploded. This was completely inconsistent with the experimental procedures. Moreover, the two were detonated by air - dropping, and the devices were completely different from the first one. They had never been detonated in actual combat and were to be dropped on the enemy's cities, which were illogical and even less scientific. The United States was not facing an existential crisis and did not need to drop atomic bombs urgently. No director of a weapons experiment center would dare to disrespect the scientific process like this. But why have scientists and management experts around the world been unable to see through this for decades? Where is our philosophical view? The ruins of these two cities should have been caused by the Japanese army piling up explosives everywhere in the two cities. As a result, there are several buildings in the central areas of the supposed atomic bomb explosions that did not collapse. Moreover, if it were the real central areas of the atomic bomb explosions, the high temperature of about 6,000 degrees of the atomic bomb explosion would surely burn the trees in these areas. However, the branches around the severely damaged buildings in the central areas of the two cities did not show signs of being burned or burned down, let alone being completely burned down, indicating that this was clearly a fictional nuclear bomb explosion psychological warfare jointly carried out by the US military. Countless evidences can be clearly seen in the public pictures. There are too many evidences of the fake atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. If it were not for the so - called Japanese nuclear bomb explosion survivors who did not apologize to the global public after winning the Nobel Peace Prize this year, the author of this article would not be willing to mention too many evidences, because one piece of evidence is enough to show that Hiroshima and Nagasaki never experienced atomic - bomb explosions.

From the dual perspective of maintaining world peace and making profitable investments, it is recommended that the Nobel Foundation, investors in Europe and

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America cooperate with Hollywood to shoot "a shocking atomic bombings psychological warfare film about the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki" being a huge deception.

Making a film requires finding topics that are of great interest to the public. How the earth-shattering lie of faking the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was successful will surely arouse great interest from the public. Why are we deceived by such a low-level lie? Why are we so like novices or rookies? It is also one of the ways to maintain world peace and sustainable development from a different perspective, cultivate peace fighters, reduce nuclear weapons, promote nuclear disarmament, and achieve the goals of Mr. Nobel's four major concepts of peace. If this film can be successfully filmed, it should achieve extremely high ratings and have an excellent effect on maintaining world peace and sustainable development. It is equivalent to investors in Europe and America providing funds, Hollywood producing films, and the world holding countless peace conferences.